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D4.1 Co-creation methodology and dialogue sessions reports

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CONTENTS

1.	Introduction	6
2.	Overall analysis of the FIERCE labs	8
2.1.	Labs’ outcomes and approaches	8
2.2.	Composition of the FIERCE labs	12
2.3.	Lab’s internal dynamics	17
3.	Overview of the FIERCE labs composition	20
3.1.	Denmark	21
3.2.	Greece.....	24
3.3.	France	27
3.4.	Italy	30
3.5.	Poland.....	33
3.6.	Slovenia.....	35
3.7.	Spain	37
3.8.	Turkey.....	41
3.9.	Transnational lab	44
4.	The third co-creation cycle: preparation, agenda and description of the sessions per lab	46
4.1.	Denmark	46
4.2.	Greece.....	49
4.3.	France	51
4.4.	Italy	53
4.5.	Poland.....	57
4.6.	Slovenia.....	58
4.7.	Spain	61
4.8.	Turkey.....	62
4.9.	Transnational lab	63
5.	Analysis of lab’s internal dynamics	65
5.1.	Denmark	65
5.2.	Greece.....	67
5.3.	France	69
5.4.	Italy	71
5.5.	Poland.....	75
5.6.	Slovenia.....	76
5.7.	Spain	78
5.8.	Turkey.....	80
5.9.	Transnational lab	82
6.	Analysing the FIERCE lab’s outcomes	83
6.1.	Denmark	83
6.2.	Greece.....	86
6.3.	France	87
6.4.	Italy.....	88

6.5.	Poland	92
6.6.	Slovenia.....	93
6.7.	Spain	94
6.8.	Turkey	96
6.9.	Transnational lab: Results of the FIERCE campaign	97
7.	References	101
8.	Annex N° 1: Template to report the third lab meetings and questionnaire	102

FIGURES

Figure 1:	Labs with regular variations in the participation patterns.....	13
Figure 2:	Labs with regular variations in the participation patterns.....	14
Figure 3:	Labs with a significant drop-out	14
Figure 4:	Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third Danish Lab.....	24
Figure 5:	Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third Greek Lab	27
Figure 6:	Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third French Lab.....	30
Figure 7:	Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third Italian Lab.....	32
Figure 8:	Characteristics of organisations participating in Third Spanish Lab	41
Figure 9:	Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third Turkish Lab.....	44
Figure 10:	Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third Transnational Lab.....	46

TABLES

Table 1:	Analytical dimensions for the lab reporting templates.....	7
Table 2:	Overview of the third FIERCE co-creation cycle	10
Table 3:	Participation to FIERCE labs	12
Table 4:	Satisfaction reported by respondents to the feedback questionnaire	17
Table 5:	Participants to the third transnational lab (FIERCE partners and external participants from labs and actions)	45
Table 6:	Italian lab’s outcome - Index of the self-defence manual.....	54
Table 7:	Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Danish lab	86
Table 8:	Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Greek lab	87
Table 9:	Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – French lab	88
Table 11:	Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Italian lab	92
Table 12:	Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Slovenian lab.....	94
Table 13:	Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Spanish lab.....	96
Table 14:	Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Turkish lab	97
Table 15:	Elected MEPs signing the FIERCE charter	99
Table 16:	Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Transnational lab	100

Abbreviations

ABM	Advisory Board Members
CSE	Comprehensive Sexuality Education
DH	Disabled People's Organisations Denmark
E.A.S.T.	Essential Autonomous Struggles Transnational (E.A.S.T.)
EC	European Commission
EP	European Parliament
ESPD	Everyday Sexism Project Denmark
EU	European Union
EWL	European Lobby of Slovenia
FAMA	Feminist Antifascist Network
FDDB	The Danish DeafBlind Association
GA	Grant Agreement
GBV	Gender Based Violence
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
IGLYO	International Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, Queer and Intersex (LGBTQI) Youth & Student Organisation (IGLYO):
IPPF	International Planned Parenthood Foundation (IPPF)
IVF	in vitro fertilization
KWC	Karditsa Women's Centre
MEPs	Members of the European Parliament
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
REA	European Research Executive Agency
SIND	The Danish Association for Mental Health
SUMH	The Danish Association of Youth with Disabilities
T	Task
WP	Work Package
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

This report is integral part of the work delivered within FIERCE project’s work package (WP) 4, titled “Participatory research co-creation Labs”. WP4 has three main objectives: (i) establishing a co - creation process to connect research activities with practice and activism, (ii) support in bridging gaps between the feminist movement and allies and (iii) pilot democratic innovations co-designed and co-created in partnership with feminist actors (movements and organisations). To achieve them, WP4 is divided in two main initiatives. On one side, FIERCE labs —tasks (T) 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3—, consisting of action-oriented dialogues among feminist activists structured in three co-creation cycles, implemented in the eight countries of the project —Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain and Turkey— and one transnational lab. On the other side, FIERCE actions —T4.4—, aimed at testing democratic innovations through the financing of initiatives proposed by feminist actors, that could potentially originate also from the lab’s activities.

The present deliverable is the third version of D4.1 “Co-creation methodology and dialogue sessions reports”, focused on presenting the methodology for the co-creation labs (T4.1), as well as to report and analyse the lab sessions (T4.2 and 4.3). The three FIERCE’s co-creation cycles have been implemented between April and November 2024. Each cycle comprises a series of sessions organised as lab encounters, specifically including: an in-person meeting in each national lab, followed by two meetings within the transnational lab —one in person and one online—. It is worth highlighting that the labs aspire to transcend mere discourse. While they certainly serve as spaces for interaction and discussion among diverse stakeholders, their ultimate aim is to generate concrete policy- and politically oriented outcomes by the participating groups.

The first and second versions of the deliverable, presented in August 2023 and April 2024, described the methodology and the report of the first and second co-creation cycles of the FIERCE project. This third version of the deliverable reports the third co-creation cycle of the project, i.e., the third lab sessions of the eight national labs and the transnational lab.

This document is organised in six chapters. After this brief introduction, Chapter 2 gives an overview of the FIERCE labs’ composition in terms of the organisations conforming the lab and the sociodemographic characteristics of the participants of each lab. Chapter 3 describes the third lab in-person sessions in terms, detailing the preparation process, agenda and content of the session. Chapter 4 focuses on the lab’s internal dynamics, providing some reflections regarding the decision-making and power dynamics, the presence of controversial issues and tensions/debates, emotions inside the lab, the establishment of new alliances and some final considerations regarding intersectionality and democratic innovations. Chapter 5 centres in analysing the FIERCE lab’s outcomes, while chapter 6 includes a comparative analysis. Finally, chapter 5 presents the annexes.

Annotations on the methodology for the elaboration of D4.1

The reporting of FIERCE lab sessions from the first and second co-creation cycles was characterised by a descriptive approach, prioritising the documentation of the lab set-up process, the agenda, detailed discussions of each session, and facilitation techniques implemented by FIERCE partners. These elements were operationalised through a template for lab reports, which served as the primary input for the development of the first and second versions of D4.1. The focus on session descriptions aimed to analyse the implementation of methodological guidelines and the evolution of each lab’s discursive components towards the conceptualisation and proposal of concrete political or policy-oriented outcomes.

Following the second lab sessions, all national labs had already defined and prioritised one concrete political/policy-oriented outcome as part of the co-creation process. Most labs had also decided to

submit proposals to the FIERCE actions call (T4.4) to seek funding for their actions. This task, centred on financing feminist democratic innovations, complements the research results of WP1 and WP2 and serves as a key input for WP3. This work package focuses on developing an analytical framework for cross-country comparative policy analysis and assessing the potential of feminist movements for democratic innovations by evaluating strategies and tools for more inclusive decision-making processes.

To contribute effectively to WP3, the reporting templates for lab sessions were updated to prioritise a set of analytical dimensions related to democratic innovations identified through a literature review undertaken for the conceptualisation of the FIERCE labs. The updated lab reporting template is presented in Annex 1. The most notable differences from the previous templates are: (i) the inclusion of additional information about the composition of the lab, specifically the characteristics of the participating organisations, and (ii) new analytical dimensions in the section titled "Analysing the Lab's Internal Dynamics," which incorporates specific questions designed to prompt reflections.

To enrich the analysis, a feedback questionnaire was developed to directly collect information from lab participants. This included their sociodemographic characteristics, organisational affiliations, perceptions of lab dynamics, and general feedback. The table below summarises the analytical dimensions included in the questionnaire and reporting template, alongside the relevant bibliographical references upon which the lab methodology is based.

Analytical dimensions	Related bibliography
Decision-making and power dynamics	Elstub and Escobar (2019), hooks, (1984) Macdonald & Sánchez-Casal (2002) Valle-Ruiz et al., (2015)
Emotions	della Porta and Doerr (2018)
Alliances and critical friendship	Eschle and Maignashca (2006), Costa and Kallick (1993), Chappell and Mackay (2021)
Intersectionality	Ciccia & Roggeband, (2021).
Agonistic practices and feminist critiques to public spaces	Dean, (2017), Rosanvallon, (2008), Fraser, 1990), Martínez Palacios (2017)
Collaborative practices with institutional politics and invited spaces	Bächtiger et al. (2018), Elstub and Escobar (2019)
Participatory and deliberative practices in governance	(Vandael et al., (2018),Ansell & Torfing, (2021),Florida (2014, p. 305)

Table 1: Analytical dimensions for the lab reporting templates

It is worth noting that the questionnaire was distributed to partners in the second week of June 2024, by which time some of the third lab sessions had already occurred. Although it was recommended that the questionnaire be administered during a specific time slot within the lab sessions, this was only feasible for the Italian and transnational cases. In all other labs, the questionnaire was sent to participants after the sessions, resulting in lower response rates.

In this context, the two primary sources of information for drafting D4.1 were the analytical reports from the national labs and the participants' responses to the feedback questionnaire. While some details were included in the lab reports, Smart Venice conducted a direct analysis of the raw questionnaire responses. Unless a specific reference is made to the feedback questionnaire, reported information comes from the lab reports.

2. Overall analysis of the FIERCE labs

2.1. Labs’ outcomes and approaches

Three of the national labs centred on GBV and the anti-gender backlash —France, Greece and Turkey—, one on reproductive rights and abortion —Slovenia—, one on labour rights —Poland—, one on education —Italy—, one on care —Spain— and one on sexism and intersectionality —Denmark—. In addition, the transnational lab was also focused on the anti-gender backlash as a cross-cutting theme, which was decided at the FIERCE consortium level with the aim to select a theme potentially relevant for all labs.

The labs’ outcomes are the political/policy-oriented action collaboratively discussed, developed and implemented throughout the whole co-creation process, composed of three in-presence meetings. As explained in the first version of D4.1¹, some of these labs followed a more directed/controlled approach —Slovenia and Italy—, in which labs’ themes and the concrete outcomes were proposed by FIERCE partners after some exchanges with a core/smaller group — of lab participants—. All other national labs followed a more open/inductive approach, in which FIERCE partners proposed a theme, leaving agenda and outcomes’ setting to be jointly defined with participants during the lab. In all these cases, the first lab session was mainly focused on the diagnosis of the lab’s theme, postponing the decision of the lab’s outcome, which took place during the second lab meeting or in-between the two sessions.

The third lab’s meeting was dedicated to conclude the content-development of the lab’s outcome and, in most cases, plan the application process to the FIERCE actions call² (T4.4) which provided budget for the implementation of the actions generated in the labs, as well as external feminist actions as part of a public open call. Most of the labs’ outcomes are currently under implementation with deadline on February 2025, with the exception of the Slovenian and the transnational lab, which have already implemented their respective outcomes. In addition, the Spanish lab’s action has been suspended³ due to the low participation and adhesion to the action during the third lab (see sections 3.7, 5.7 and 6.7 for more details).

Table 2 provides an overview of the FIERCE third co-creation cycle. We observe recurring typologies of outcomes. Three of them consisted of campaigns —in Denmark, Poland and the transnational lab—. The Danish lab also organised a series of events in political festivals as part of their political action. Two labs decided to implement a network or platform as their outcome: France and Spain. The Turkish lab’s outcome is a policy brief articulating the problems Turkish civil society associations experience in their relations with Europe-wide international institutions, the Italian lab is developing a self-defence manual for teachers and activists, while the Slovenian lab implemented a public exhibition.

Finally, the Greek lab is being redefined. This lab followed the most horizontal approach, where the group of activists self-organised and co-created agenda and prioritised topics relevant for them in an assembly-based dynamic. As a result, they created detailed and specific presentations for the second and third lab sessions, focusing more on political discussions than on identifying a concrete outcome. During the third lab a proposal of outcome by AUTH, the FIERCE partner in charge was presented and participants manifested their agreement. The proposal was to collect a portfolio of the participants’ experiences with diverse expressions such as pictures, drawings, texts, sounds, among other proposals.

¹ For deepening in this classification, see chapter 5 of the first version of D4.1.

² More information on the lab’s outcomes can be found on the FIERCE project’s webpage (<https://fierce-project.eu/fierce-actions/>), which includes an overview of the actions financed under the “FIERCE actions” call. Seven actions from the national labs are being financed, along with 11 additional actions from the open call.

³ The budget that had been requested for the financing of the Spanish lab’s action is being destined to finance another feminist action that applied to the “FIERCE actions” open call.

Despite this, only one participant sent the agreed material by January 2025, therefore, the outcome proposal is being rediscussed internally by the AUTH team and at the consortium level.

The implementation of all lab outcomes as part of the “FIERCE actions” call is expected to be finalised by March 2025. The results of the implementation process, along with details of other actions from the open call (T4.4), will be outlined in deliverable 4.2, “*Report on Democratic Innovations Practices*”. This deliverable will include a booklet showcasing all implemented actions. Furthermore, engagement with the activists who participated in the labs will continue through WP5 activities. Specifically, the upcoming events of the transnational network (T5.1) include three online events and one in-person final meeting, organised back-to-back with the FIERCE final conference.

Labs	Theme	Outcome	Current status of outcome	Date
Denmark	Sexism and intersectionality, with a specific focus on people with disabilities.	Social media campaign with stories of sexism from a minority perspective, several events at political festivals, podcast on the lab’s theme	Implemented: Social media campaign implemented on March 8 th 2024 and participation in the Danish Youth Democracy Festival (September 2024)	April 26th 2024
France	Backlash & cyberviolence	Online platform of resources against the Backlash	In progress: Currently under development	July 16th
Greece	Gender-based violence, LGBTIQ+ inclusionary education	Portfolio presenting experiences of activists as part of the workshop and in their collectives: discussions elaborated in the lab (multimodal ways, such as pictures, manifestos, sounds, drawings)	In progress: Currently under discussion	June 28th-29th
Italy	Education on the differences	Self- defence manual for teachers and activists implementing education to differences	In progress: Production process of the material developed in the lab and graphic design of the manual	July 30th 2024
Slovenia	Reproductive rights, violence	Public exhibition (including podcasts)	Implemented Exhibition displayed from between May 7 th – 20 th	May 7th-20th 2024
Spain	Care	Network for care	Currently suspended	June 17th 2024
Poland	Labour rights	Social media campaign	In progress: Currently under development	June 22nd 2024
Turkey	Gender-based violence, anti-gender backlash and democratic backsliding	Policy brief articulating the problems Turkish civil society associations experience in their relations with Europe-wide international institutions	In progress: Production of the policy brief	May 10th 2024
Transnational lab	Anti-gender backlash	Campaign for the 2024 EP elections	Implemented Campaign active between April 26 th and June 4 th .	November 4th 2024

Table 2: Overview of the third FIERCE co-creation cycle

Considering the dynamics with institutional politics, most of the lab’s outcomes are framed as oppositional to current governmental politics, criticising diverse aspects of the agenda-setting and implementation of public policies. Agonistic approaches are particularly widespread in contexts where there is a conservative or right-wing government. Despite this, none of the lab’s outcomes that are actually being implemented propose a grassroots initiative entirely oppositional to institutional politics or a protest/demonstration. For example, purely agonistic outcomes proposed during the first session in Brussels included “chaos” or a “general feminist strike.” These options were discarded during the deliberative process because they were considered as non-viable for implementation within a limited time-frame as the one proposed by the labs, since they involve a more in-depth structural longer-term change.

All of the lab outcomes being implemented in the FIERCE labs are related to institutional politics to some extent, representing a feminist interpretation, framing or critique of them. The Italian, Slovenian, Spanish, French, Greek, and Polish labs are closer to national institutional politics. For instance, the self-defence handbook for teachers/activist on Education to Differences in the Italian lab criticises the approaches and lack of policies on the matter from the Ministry for Education, while to the Slovenian Lab represents a call to both institutions and citizens to defending the existing legislation on sexual and reproductive rights. The Spanish and French labs proposed influencing decision-makers and feminist policies as part of their specific objectives, while the Greek lab addressed a series of issues relevant to the national feminist movement related to institutional politics, such as the joint custody law discussed in some of the presentations.

The Turkish and transnational labs addressed European/transnational level politics. The latter developing a policy brief on GBV and anti-gender/anti-democratic backsliding aimed at international organisations, while the transnational lab targeted Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) via a communication campaign.

Finally, the Danish lab prioritised raising awareness rather than directly challenging political dynamics, favouring practical and actionable proposals, as it addressed sexism from a societal perspective in its outcomes. Its focus included testimonies of sexism experienced by people belonging to minorities — shared through a social media campaign — and managing situations of sexism via a bystander workshop developed for the Youth Democracy Festival.

Despite most of the labs adopting a feminist critical approach towards current governmental politics, their methodologies also reflected a degree of flexibility to collaborate with institutional politics, engaging in collaboration should government priorities shift towards alignment with feminist politics. Most of the collectives involved in the labs already engage with public institutions on a regular or occasional basis, suggesting that their work could align with government priorities if political shifts occurred. Considering the 50 replies received to the feedback questionnaire, only 8 respondents — from Italy, Denmark, Turkey and Spain— mentioned “no” to the question inquiring whether their organisations or collectives collaborated with public institutions.

The reverse logic —potential collaboration with the government that could evolve into a more critical approach in the future — was also proposed. For instance, in the Spanish lab, participants identified political advocacy as a viable strategy to influence care policies. This made collaboration with institutions a potential pathway, given the current political opportunity provided by the left coalition in the government. However, participants did not rule out a shift towards a more critical and accountability-focused approach if the political landscape changed.

Overall, while the labs predominantly adopted an oppositional stance with the current governmental politics, specifically critical in the governments ruled by more conservative and far-right governments,

the methodologies and outcomes tend more towards a collaborative approach with institutional politics rather than purely agonistic practices.

2.2. Composition of the FIERCE labs

The following table provides the total number of participants across the three FIERCE co-creation sessions, along with the number of respondents to the feedback questionnaire. Since the co-creation process to define, conceptualise the labs political outcomes required continuity, the invitation of new collectives was limited to exceptional cases in all labs.

The feedback questionnaire, developed by Smart Venice (SV) partners, was delivered to consortium partners by mid-June 2024, at which point some of the third lab sessions had already taken place. Although it was recommended to allocate a specific time slot within the third lab’s agenda for completing the feedback questionnaire, most responses were collected retrospectively after the sessions had concluded. SV partners recommended sending the questionnaire to all participants in the three lab sessions to collect more responses. However, this criterion was not uniformly applied across all countries. The specific criteria used to target feedback questionnaire respondents are detailed below:

- Participants in the complete co-creation cycle (unique participants in the three labs): Italy, Poland, and Spain.
- Only participants in the third lab: France, Greece, Turkey, and the transnational lab.
- Only participants actively involved in the co-creation process:
 - In Denmark, the questionnaire was sent to the 19 participants who actively engaged in the co-creation sessions and the organisation of the lab’s outcomes. Some participants from the second lab were excluded because it was organised as a public event within a political festival, and certain attendees of the public event had no involvement in the FIERCE co-creation process.
 - In Slovenia, the questionnaire was sent only to the 4 participants who were part of the core group and who were actively engaged throughout the entire co-creation process. Similarly to the Danish case, the other reported attendees participated in the events organised as labs but were not actively involved in the co-creation process.

The overall response rate was 35%, which is considered good on average: out of the 143 participants who received the feedback questionnaire, 50 responded. The labs with the highest response rates were the French, Slovenian, Italian, and transnational labs. Notably, the latter two were the only labs that allocated a dedicated time slot in their agendas for participants to complete the questionnaire.

Country	1st lab participants	2nd lab participants	3rd lab participants	Respondents feedback questionnaire	Participants received the feedback questionnaire	Response rates feedback questionnaire
Denmark	12	25	7	4	19	21%
France	9	13	9	5	9	56%
Greece	10	10	13	3	13	23%
Italy	15	12	10	12	23	52%
Poland	16	9	8	1	18	5%
Slovenia	23	12	43	3	4	75%
Spain	21	14	6	8	24	30%
Turkey	17	16	17	4	17	24%
Transnational lab	26	26	16	10	16	63%
Total	149	137	129	50	143	35%

Table 3: Participation to FIERCE labs

Participation trends

A total of 129 participants participated in the third FIERCE co-creation cycle, with a slight decrease in aggregated terms after the first cycle, and similar attendance rates in the following two sessions. There are three identifiable groups among the FIERCE labs according to the participation trends: (i) countries with oscillating participation throughout the co-creation process —France, Greece, Italy and Turkey—, (ii) countries with peaks in the participation due to the organisation of public open events —Slovenia and Denmark— and (iii) countries with a significant drop-out rate —Spain, Poland and the transnational lab—.

Four of nine labs presented an oscillating participation (Figure 1), with some sessions more or less populated according to the personal availability of the activists that were involved in the process. Turkey had the most regular pattern of participation among all national labs, followed by France which had a second meeting with more participants, to return to the initial number of the first session. The Italian lab had a slight decrease in the number of participants, going from 15 in the first meeting to 10 in the last one, which was mainly caused by the time availability of activists on the specific dates when the labs were organised or due to personal or work unforeseen events. As previously mentioned, the invitation of new collectives was limited to exceptional cases; therefore, in some cases participation slightly dropped throughout the process, such as in the case of the Italian lab. In the case of the Greek lab, one collective’s drop-off due to limited internal capacity was compensated by an additional collective invited to the third lab, as well as the Gender Equality Committee from the Thessaloniki university.

Figure 1: Labs with regular variations in the participation patterns

In Denmark and Slovenia, some of the lab sessions were organised as public events that were part of the implementation of their political outcome; thus, they presented peaks in the participation in some of the lab sessions (Figure 2). The Danish lab organised the second lab as a public roundtable in a political festival, while the Slovenian third lab was the public exhibition which consisted in their political outcome. In both cases, participants to these lab sessions report the total number of participants to these events.

Figure 2: Labs with regular variations in the participation patterns

The final identifiable group of labs considering the participation patterns were the labs with a constant drop-out throughout the lab sessions —Spain, Poland and the transnational lab— (Figure 3). Reasons behind this drop-out were different. In the Polish lab this was due to personal reasons, i.e. changes in the personal lives of participants reducing their time for activism and political action. In addition, there were some highly visible activists/leaders —well-known recognisable public characters— who dropped-out the process due to limits in their schedules.

In the Spanish lab some collectives informed of their unavailability to participate due to ideological/political reasons: for example, collectives from the Basque country discontinued their attendance as the lab was addressing care promoting a public, state-wide system of care, which they believed conflicted with their struggle for a community-led public care system. In addition, Spanish FIERCE partners reported some tension during the first lab when one participant proposed sex work as care work and the other participants did not agree, presumable causing their drop out in the following sessions. Other participants mentioned their interest of being kept informed whilst their impossibility to attend to the third meeting, while other stopped responding.

Figure 3: Labs with a significant drop-out

Finally, the case of the transnational lab, presented a relevant dropped-out because of restriction imposed by the budget limitations related to organising the FIERCE week which made it possible to invite only 2 representatives per national lab —instead of 3 like in the previous sessions—. For similar reasons, only 3 representatives of the European level organisations that took part to the first and second lab meetings —ERRC, Gender Five Plus and WIDE+—were invited to the third one.

The following paragraphs provide an overview of some characteristics of the lab participants based on information collected through the feedback questionnaire and the FIERCE lab reports. It is important to note certain limitations from the information coming from the questionnaire, as only 50 responses were received, compared to the 129 participants who took part in the third lab sessions. Unless specifically referenced, the source of the information is the lab reports.

The most common profile of the FIERCE lab participants according to the lab reports was a cisgender woman in her thirties or forties with a high degree of education (Master’s or PhD) and a long trajectory inside the feminist movement. This profile was confirmed by the feedback questionnaire responses: 45 out of the 50 respondents identified as women, with an average age of 43. Additionally, 44 respondents reported having at least a Bachelor’s Degree (25 held a Master’s Degree, and 9 had a PhD), and half of the respondents (26 out of 50) indicated being active in the feminist movement for more than 10 years.

The Turkish and French lab reports highlighted a lack of racial inclusiveness as the major critique expressed by participants. The former stressed the need to include Kurdish collectives, while the latter emphasised the importance of involving collectives representing the migrant feminist movement in France.

It is worth noting that partners in both countries attempted to ensure inclusiveness by inviting collectives and activists representing these groups. In the Turkish lab, Kurdish activists based in Kurdish-majority cities had confirmed their participation in the first lab but were unable to attend due to personal reasons. The lab could include only one Istanbul-based activist whose civil society advocacy relates to Kurdish women’s grievances. In the French lab, a collective of Black feminists participated in an online preparatory meeting for the second lab but subsequently informed the organisers of their misalignment with the lab’s priorities and decided not to participate in the session.

The Spanish lab stood out as the most diverse in terms of participant profiles. According to the lab’s report, which characterised all 24 participants involved in the co-creation process, a quarter had a migratory background from Latin America. Additionally, one participant had functional diversity, and attendees came from a broad variety of backgrounds, including activists, academics, politicians, and care workers.

Three questions to collect self-identification with intersectional characteristics were included in the feedback questionnaire asking if participants considered themselves: (i) a person with a migration or ethnic background, (ii) an LGBTIQ+ person, and (iii) a person with a disability or other chronic condition. Among the 50 respondents, 17 identified as LGBTIQ+, with representation across all labs except the Slovenian lab. Additionally, 8 respondents from all labs with exception of Slovenia and Greece, identified as having an ethnic or migratory background. Similarly, 8 respondents identified as having a chronic condition or disability, with no representation from the Greek, Polish and Slovenian labs.

Considering the organisational affiliation of the participants, around half of the participants were representing their collectives or organisations in the labs, while in four labs —Turkey, Slovenia, Poland and Spain—, attendees participated as individuals rather than representatives of their organisations. The Turkish lab agreed individual participation during the first national lab to assure the safety of the participants due to the political context. The core group of the Slovenian lab was formed by 3 activists participating on individual basis and the graphic designer who supported the elaboration of the materials for the public exhibition —Slovenian lab’s outcome. In the case of Poland and Spain attendants

to the lab sessions also participated as individuals. In the latter case, they were invited because of their background in care issues from diverse perspectives such as the social reorganisation of care, the right to care and services for independent living, the dignification and improvement of working conditions in home care, residential care services, and the household and care work sector.

In all the other four national labs, some participants decided to participate as individuals, while others representing their organisations in the lab. It is worth noting that in most cases, participants from grassroots or more radical feminist movements chose to participate in a personal capacity rather than as representatives of their collectives. Representing their collectives would have required prior deliberation and approval through an assembly process with other members.

In the case of Italy, whose lab’s theme was decided prior to the implementation of the lab, the lab was formed in close collaboration with a network working in education to differences —*Rete Educare Alle Differenze*, the largest national network working in the lab’s theme— forming a core group which recommended the contact of other actors. The Danish lab was also formed after the alliance of two organisations that had collaborated in advance —Everyday Sexism Project Denmark, SUMH and Disabled People’s Organisations Denmark (DH)—, which proposed the lab’s theme —sexism under a minority perspective, with a focus on people with disabilities— and others to be contacted. In the case of France and Greece, several feminist and LGBTIQ+ collectives were invited to be part of the lab.

Considering the replies to the feedback questionnaire, two thirds (33) of the 50 respondents declared representing their organisations in the labs. Most of them declared that their organisations and collectives define themselves as feminists (30) and following an intersectional approach (32). Regarding the level of collaboration with public institutions, most of the respondents to the questionnaire do collaborate in a regular or occasional basis —22 and 17, respectively—. In particular, only 8 of the respondents representing their collectives in the labs mentioned not having any type of collaboration with the government —2 respondents in Denmark, 2 in Italy, 2 in Turkey, 1 in Spain and 1 in the transnational lab—.

Organisations reported collaborating with public institutions through a variety of activities that can be broadly categorised into advocacy, service provision, policy development, capacity building, and education. Advocacy efforts often include lobbying ministries, participating in parliamentary hearings, and influencing laws, such as those addressing gender equality and reproductive rights. Service provision focuses on partnerships to deliver social and educational programmes, such as anti-violence services or access to sexual health education. Policy development is supported through consultation meetings, research collaborations, and the drafting of recommendations on issues like anti-GBV policies. Capacity building includes training activities for local authorities, educators, and community leaders, while education partnerships involve organising workshops, joint initiatives in schools, and curriculum alignment with public standards. Together, these activities aim to enhance social welfare, promote gender justice, and support vulnerable groups through targeted interventions.

Regarding the formation of alliances, countries where new alliances were specifically highlighted by participants were Spain, Turkey and Greece. Almost none of the organisations in the labs of Spain and Greece had worked together prior to the FIERCE project. In some other cases, organisations had previously worked together, such as in the case of Turkey, Italy and France. In other countries, such as Turkey, it was reported how the lab supported a positive confrontation —and apparently helping to solve— some existing tensions among some of the participants.

2.3. Lab’s internal dynamics

General feedback

The following table summarises the level of satisfaction declared by participants according to the 50 respondents to the questionnaire, rated from 0 to 10. The only exception to this range was the Danish lab which applied an scale from 1 to 5. In this lab three participants mentioned a satisfaction of 3 and one of 5, which has been translated to 7 and 10 to uniform the table.

Lab	Average	Median	Highest value	Lowest value	Standard Deviation
Italian lab	8.2	9.0	10.0	4.0	2.1
French lab	7.6	8.0	9.0	6.0	1.1
Turkish lab	9.5	9.5	10.0	9.0	0.6
Greek lab	9.0	9.0	10.0	8.0	1.0
Danish lab	7.5	7.0	9.0	7.0	1.0
Slovenian lab	9.0	9.0	10.0	8.0	1.0
Spanish lab	7.9	8.0	9.0	6.0	1.0
Transnational lab	8.3	8.0	10.0	6.0	1.3
Overall analysis	8.06	8.0	10.0	4.0	1.4

Table 4: Satisfaction reported by respondents to the feedback questionnaire

The overall average satisfaction score across all labs is 8.06, indicating a generally high level of satisfaction among participants. The median score matches the overall average at 8.0, further supporting this conclusion. The range (4.0 to 10.0) and the standard deviation of 1.4 suggest some variability, but not excessively so.

The Turkish lab has the highest average satisfaction score at 9.5, with a matching median of 9.5. The scores are tightly clustered between 9.0 and 10.0, as evidenced by the lowest standard deviation of 0.6. This lab stands out for its consistently high satisfaction. On the other hand, the lowest satisfaction of the labs (without considering the Danish lab due to the scale problems previously mentioned, was the French lab. This had an average satisfaction of 7.6 and a median of 8.0. Scores ranged from 6.0 to 9.0, and the standard deviation of 1.1 indicates moderate variability.

The Polish lab have not been considered in this analysis because there was only one respondent to the feedback questionnaire, making impossible to calculate the statistical measures.

Decision-making inside the labs

A first relevant determinant in the lab internal dynamics were the type of set-up process before the first lab meeting. As mentioned, two labs kick started the labs via a more directed/controlled approach, mainly Italy and Slovenia, with FIERCE partners having preparatory meetings with a core group to decide on the lab’s theme, approach and political outcome and other participants to be invited. All the other national labs and the transnational lab followed an open/inductive approach, with a broad invitation to feminist activists and collectives to the first session and an initial pre-identification of the lab’s theme. In these cases, the first session was ‘diagnostic’ aiming at framing challenges/problems/political priorities, while the outcome was decided during the second session.

Among the first type of labs set-up, in Slovenia the smaller core centralized the decision-making processes inside the lab, with other participants being invited as audience to the public events that were organised. Indeed, only the three participants belonging to the core group participated on a continuous basis throughout the whole process. In the case of the Italian lab, the core group dissolved as soon as the first meeting took place, and all lab members were actively participating in the decision-making processes. In particular, one foundation that had participated in the first core-group meeting and the first lab meeting informed their decision of dropping out the process because of time constrains.

In other national labs, some participants assumed a predominant role in the internal decision-making due to their continued participation throughout the process. This was the case of the Turkish lab, where after the first transnational lab, the three participants that had attended the meeting formed a core group working closer with Turkish FIERCE partners. They are currently leading the process of writing the policy brief they lab is implementing as political action. In the case of the Polish lab, also participants that attended the first transnational lab meeting had a predominant role in the second in-presence meeting, in which a similar methodology as in the transnational lab based on brainstorming and deliberation, was implemented to decide the outcome.

In Spain, France and the transnational lab, there were no formal participants undertaking a predominant role in the decision-making; however, participants responding to the questionnaire mentioned that some of the participants had more influence in the discussions according to their expertise and years of experience. In Denmark, one of the collectives led the lab’s dynamics, because the political action implemented was based on adapting other initiatives this collective was already implementing —social media campaigns collecting testimonies of sexism and the bystander workshops that were implemented during the Danish Youth Democracy Festival—.

The Greek lab was the one where FIERCE partners deliberately had the least active role in the lab dynamics, leaving participants to self-organise. During the first lab session, one of the participants took a leading role in the process due to the political experience this person had. As a consequence, the session was following a horizontal assembly-based dynamics in which participants prioritised the themes relevant to the lab and organised an agenda to prepare presentations as part of the second meeting.

Decision-making in most labs followed a process of discussion and consensus-building, commonly organising group discussions followed by plenary sessions. Due to the time constraints and the long time between the lab sessions, it is not possible to state that the labs implemented an actual deliberation process/methodology to reach consensus regarding the labs’ themes; however, some characteristics of deliberative processes were definitely present in some lab sessions.

Both FIERCE partners in their reports and participants responding to the questionnaire, identified some power dynamics; however, most of them felt that voices were heard and that FIERCE partners implemented techniques, such as multiple rounds of discussion, to assure balance of different standpoints and arguments. Only the French and transnational lab reported used voting as a technique in the case where it was not possible to make a decision based on informal consensus building methods.

Conflicts and tensions inside the labs

While no significant conflicts or tensions were reported across the FIERCE labs, certain disagreements and points of contention emerged, reflecting the diversity of perspectives among participants. Some labs experienced tensions associated to the generational differences in the approaches of activists, as witnessed in Poland, where older activists criticised a perceived lack of historical memory within the feminist movement. Also, in Italy discussions arose between older participants’ tendency to support their standpoints by claiming for longer experience, and younger, grassroots activists who emphasised on the newest developments in the topics of discussions. In the Italian lab there were also some tensions between an activist from a grassroots collective who commented to one of the organisers that participants from another NGO-type organisation did not respect assembly dynamics and were trying to monopolize the discourse.

Disagreements on specific issues also surfaced regarding the approaches and specific topics of discussion inside the lab. For instance, in Denmark, debates centred around pedagogical approaches and strategies to engage teenagers during the Danish Youth Festival were respectfully resolved in a follow-up meeting. In Greece, a participant from the Gender Equality Committee expressed views

contrary to the group’s stance against mandatory shared custody laws, citing personal experiences. Similarly, in Spain, differing opinions on maternity (essentialist vs. trans-inclusive perspectives) and the framing of sex work as care work sparked debate. In Slovenia, feedback revealed isolated instances of conflict, including a comment interpreted as racist during the transnational lab and another unresolved issue, both of which were addressed through dialogue and apologies.

Some tensions stemmed from broader ideological and political divisions, often related to conflicts that predated the FIERCE labs. For instance, in the Polish lab, partner reported that internal tensions inside the feminist movement could be a cause of the dropout of the lab. Despite this in some cases, exchanges taking place in the lab helped to overcome—at least partially—some of these tensions. This was the case of the Turkish lab, where partners reported the feeling of common resilience and a positive exchange between participants improving the relationship between them during the first lab.

Emotions

Across the FIERCE labs, emotions were marked by a duality of hope and resilience alongside frustration and concern, reflecting the participants’ shared contexts and challenges. A common positive thread was the sense of hope and enthusiasm stemming from the establishment of alliances, collective resilience, and the drive to counter anti-gender backlash. Participants frequently expressed gratitude and excitement for being part of meaningful networks, as seen in Denmark, where feelings of indignation about persistent sexism were counterbalanced by happiness and gratitude for the lab’s role in fostering alliances. Similarly, in Turkey, participants highlighted the resilience built during the first lab following Erdoğan’s re-election, despite dissatisfaction and frustration with the political situation.

In other labs, positive emotions were tied to a sense of collectiveness and community, such as in Greece and Slovenia, where participants felt enthusiastic and connected. Spain saw hope and empathy within the lab’s dynamics and acknowledged the left-wing coalition as a window of opportunity, yet participants expressed frustration and distrust towards the broader political climate. Italy mirrored this pattern, combining positive feelings about the lab with worry and disappointment over the government’s conservative shift. In France, initial excitement about joining the lab coexisted with concerns about broader societal contexts.

These emotional dynamics underscore the labs’ role as spaces for both solidarity and collective action, even as participants navigated the challenging realities of rising right-wing, anti-gender politics in their respective contexts.

Considerations on intersectionality

As mentioned, there is a general lack of diversity in terms of the lab’s composition, with highly-educated white women as the most common participant profile. As previously described, LGBTIQ+ people were the most represented minority in the lab, with a more limited number of people identifying as having an ethnic or migratory background as well a chronic condition or disability. In the case of the French and the Turkish labs the lack of diversity was criticised by participants, and/or a reason for drop-out or unavailability to join the Lab. Despite this, intersectionality was addressed in the labs in different ways.

In Denmark and Spain intersectionality was an essential element of the lab’s theme. In the former, choice was made to focus on sexism with a specific focus on its intersections with disabilities. In addition, intersections with an ethnic background and LGBTIQ+ rights were also addressed. In the case of the Spanish lab, the lab’s theme was care under a broad, intersectional and inter-territorial perspective, including the needs and standpoints of care givers and care receivers. As a consequence, activists and organisations representing diverse spheres of care were invited coming from various Spanish regions such as Barcelona, Basque Country, Madrid, Seville and the Canary Islands.

In other countries, such as Italy and Greece, intersectionality was addressed cross-cuttingly as part of the content developed in the lab’s outcome and as part of the discussions. In Italy for example, the use of an inclusive/non-binary language was considered an important feature of the self-defence handbook for activists, and the overall content developed was featuring reference to how patriarchy is interlocked with other systems of oppression, based on class, sexual orientation and gender identity as well as race. In the transnational lab, following an intersectional approach and trans-inclusive approach was a fundamental aspect for the invitation of networks to become part of the lab.

In other labs, such as in the Slovenian and Polish ones, intersectionality was not specifically addressed in the labs’ discussions and content developed for the outcome. In the latter though, translation of the content developed for the social media campaign to Ukrainian and English was considered, in order to be inclusive with migrants.

Considerations on democratic innovations

The FIERCE labs were evaluated by FIERCE partners as democratic innovations due to their contributions to advancing feminist perspectives and addressing democratic challenges in diverse ways. Some labs introduced novel themes or methodologies to address gaps in their national contexts. In Denmark, the lab introduced an intersectional focus, addressing the interplay between gender, disability, and ethnic/migratory backgrounds—topics rarely addressed in the Danish context. While the bystander workshop during the Danish Youth Festival was innovative, it built on an approach one of the Lab’s NGO had already implemented. In contrast, the political strategies for the festival and the social media campaign were seen as less innovative in terms of democratic impact.

Similarly, Poland’s lab addressed a gap in the feminist movement by focusing on labour rights, a theme rarely prioritised, and ensuring inclusivity for migrants, making the process more representative of diverse societal needs.

In Turkey, the lab tackled a unique theme, reframing accountability to explore how international organisations could answer to civil society organisations—a reversal of traditional dynamics. This dialogic and participatory approach was highlighted as particularly innovative, especially in Turkey’s current political climate.

Several labs showcased innovation in fostering collaboration and addressing overlooked themes. Greece brought together NGOs from diverse backgrounds to work collectively on uncommon topics in their national context, while France achieved a similar outcome by uniting collectives under a common EU-funded initiative, even if some had previously collaborated.

Slovenia’s lab stood out both for its content—an exhibition addressing threats to reproductive rights and overlooked issues like violence in reproductive healthcare—and its process, which bridged generational divides in the feminist movement to strengthen alliances. As reproductive rights are a pillar of democracy, the lab’s outcome was seen as a significant contribution to counteracting de-democratisation efforts.

Italy’s lab was innovative in terms of the outcome, a self-defence manual for teachers working in education to differences. Even if resources are available on inclusive sex education, the manual is covering a current gap in the Italian context in its focus on how to resist in a conservative political climate feature by the spread of anti-gender forces.

Spain’s lab did not innovate in the action itself (a network) but stood out for its intersectional and inter-territorial approach to care. It framed care as a democratic practice, addressing it through the perspectives of diverse communities and fostering meaningful dialogue on its role in feminist politics.

3. Overview of the FIERCE labs composition

3.1. Denmark

Participant’s demographics

The third Danish lab was held on 26 April 2024, with a total of seven participants representing six organisations, along with three researchers from Aalborg University (AAU) and two sign language interpreters whose role was to facilitate communication rather than participate in the discussion. The group demonstrated diversity in organisational roles, ranging from board members and spokespersons to volunteers and activists within their organisations. Participants’ abilities also varied; while some reported physical or mental disabilities, others did not, as noted by the Danish partners in the final report of the third lab. The age range of participants was broad, including individuals new to activism as well as those with years of experience balancing their volunteer work with professional careers. However, the group lacked diversity in terms of gender and geographical representation. Most participants identified as cisgender women, with one non-binary individual and no cisgender men, aside from a member of the AAU team. Geographically, nearly all participants were from the Copenhagen area, limiting broader representation.

According to the demographic characteristics reported in the Danish final report, the most common profile of the respondents was a white, heterosexual, cisgender woman with an average age of 33, residing in the Copenhagen area.

An attempt was made to connect online with one participant, a volunteer at the Danish Association of Youth with Disabilities; however, he could not attend the meeting due to “massive tiredness/lethargy,” which may have been related to his disability.

The questionnaire for lab participants received four responses: three respondents identified as women, while one identified as non-binary. The group included individuals aged between 26 and 49, with an average age of approximately 33 years. Regarding their engagement with feminist activism, one participant, who reported over 10 years of involvement, works part-time as a Deputy Chairperson and has an elementary school education. Two participants, each with 1–2 years of activism experience, are employed full-time in the education sector as a teacher and an assistant. One has a medium-term higher education (3–4 years), while the other has a long-term higher education degree. The fourth participant, who has been active in feminist circles for 3–4 years, is currently unemployed and seeking employment, holding a long-term higher education degree (5 years or more).

Regarding questions on self-identification with intersectional identities, one participant indicated that they identify as a person with a disability, belong to an ethnic minority background, and are a member of the LGBTQI+ community. Another participant identified as having a disability, while the remaining two participants did not associate themselves with any of these categories.

Overview of the collectives and organisations participating in the lab

The third Danish national lab, held on April 26, 2024, gathered a total of 7 participants representing 6 organisations. The majority of organisations present were affiliated with Disabled People’s Organisations Denmark (DH), a national umbrella organisation. While previous reports had described most participants as broadly representing DH, this lab clarified that two participants were directly associated with specific member organisations—The Danish DeafBlind Association (FDDB) and The Danish Association for Mental Health (SIND).

Third Danish lab, like the others, focused on the topic of sexism and intersectionality in terms of minority point of view with a specific focus on people with disabilities. Even though labs theme more focused on the disabled people, earlier collaborations with minority ethnic LGBTQ+ organisations like Sabaah has been a valuable network partner. However, due to reduced public funding, Sabaah could not send

representatives to this lab, mirroring the situation with LGBT Asylum, which remains involved through updates and planning but did not actively participate

The complete list of organisations represented at the third lab includes:

- Everyday Sexism Project Denmark (ESPD): volunteer-driven NGO created in 2015 after a web platform created by the journalist Irene Manteufel and Danish Women’s Society, inspired in the Everyday Sexism Project (created in 2012 by Laura Bates). They aim to create a safe space and document problems related to sexism, performing initiatives with policymakers and participating in projects and cooperation. ESPD does not publicly define themselves as feminists, due to their strategic aim of reaching a broader audience. However, in recent years they have developed both an intersectional and transfeminism approach whit addressing gender-based violence (GBV) in a regular way.
- Tegn Buen (name mixing the Danish terms nominate “rainbow” and “sign language”): Copenhagen based organisation founded in 1984 to represent the double minority of LGBT+ people and who are simultaneously deaf and hearing impaired. They collaborate both with organisations representing the rights of the LGBTQIA+ community and the rights of people with disabilities. Tegn Buen has been represented in all three national labs, and created podcast with one of their leading members for the FIERCE project. They do not define themselves as feminist organisation, but targeting a double minority makes them naturally intersectional approach follower.
- The Danish Association of Youth with Disabilities (SUMH): founded in 1981, umbrella organisation for young people with disabilities such as autism, blindness, muscular dystrophy, psoriasis, brain injury, and multiple sclerosis. They have a “Sexuality Committee”, which will be invited to the lab, centred on the work of sex education for young people in cooperation with schools. They do both advocacy and collaborations with public and private institutions. They are not self-defined as feminist; however, they embrace intersectional approach with a specific focus on how disabilities intersect with having a sexual life for both men, women and gender minorities.
- The Danish DeafBlind Association is the national association created in 1987 for people who impaired hearing and vision at the same time or at one. Their focus areas are both advocacy work and social activities with the members of the association. Danish Fierce Partners reported that, the organisation does not self-defined as feminist. The organisation actively collaborates with various NGOs and public institutions and participates in numerous multidisciplinary networks. Notably, it is a member of a Nordic coalition of associations for the deafblind, as well as the European Deafblind Union and the World Federation of the Deafblind.
- The Danish Association for Mental Health (SIND): is the largest national association founded in 1960, focuses on mental illness and health with members who also member of this classification, relatives to a someone who has mental illness, or professionals within this field. They do not have specific focus on gender and sexuality, and do not self-defined as feminist organisation. However, it has consistently criticised public authorities and institutions for failing to protect psychiatric patients from sexual violence and for inadequately supporting individuals with mental illnesses in reporting such incidents. While it actively participates in political forums, such as The People’s Meeting on Bornholm, to advocate within its field, there is no evidence of previous collaborations with feminist organisation
- Disabled People’s Organisations Denmark (DH): umbrella organisation founded in 1934 to promote the inclusion of people with disabilities and to promote their active and independent life. Their most general aim is to ensure that people with disabilities are included in the society as well as their ability to live an independent and active life. They established policies in terms

of people of disabilities in the fields of labour market, health care, education and accessibility. However, they have not put an emphasis on sexism and sexual harassment as an issue in their agenda before which means they do not classify themselves as feminist organisation. They are actively working to increase the focus on gender equality and sexuality-related issues in DH's own activities. Given this, their participation in the national labs may also be a reflection of DH's evolving more intersectional approach to serving the interests of disabled people.

In addition, other 2 collectives had been involved in the preparation process of the Danish lab; however, they were not able to attend to the third lab meeting.

- Sabaah: ("new day" or "new beginning" in Arabic): organisation founded in 2006 to create a community of young LGBTQIA+ people with an ethnic minority background. Since 2022 they have put a focus on the intersection with disability thanks to its contact with Tegnbyen
- LGBT Asylum: is an organisation focused in LGBTQIA+ asylum seekers.

For the third lab questionnaire, responses were received from 4 participants representing four different organisations. The majority of these organisations (3 out of 4) focused on issues related to sexism and discrimination with one organisation specifically directing its focus to disability-related matters. Regarding collaboration with public institutions, responses were varied. One organisation reported regular cooperation with public bodies, including the Central Disability Council, research institutions, and public authorities. Another one indicated occasional engagement, while the remaining two organisations stated that they did not collaborate with public institutions. No explanation was provided by the organisations that do not engage with public institutions. The organisation with occasional engagement works with public institutions focusing on the needs of STU⁴ as their target group.

When asked whether their organisation identifies as feminist, two organisations responded negatively, one affirmed their feminist stance, and the final organisation stated that while they do not explicitly identify as feminist, they advocate for equality within the sexuality committee. In terms of their approach to intersectionality, all four organisations confirmed that they follow an intersectional approach in their work. This approach is embedded in both their strategies and actions, ensuring that various interconnected aspects of discrimination—whether related to gender, sexuality, disability, or other factors—are addressed in their advocacy, outreach, and engagement efforts.

⁴ STU is a three-year youth education for young people with cognitive and physical disabilities and other young people with special needs. STU is for the age group 16 to 24. <https://uu.kk.dk/stu/in-english>

Figure 4: Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third Danish Lab

3.2. Greece

Participant’s demographics

A total of 13 participants were involved in the third Greek lab. The group was diverse in age, ranging from early twenties to mid-sixties, with most participants in their thirties and forties (the average age was 38 years old). Gender representation included 10 participants identifying as she/her and 3 as he/his, with at least one openly identifying as part of the LGBTQIA+ community. Nationally, all participants were Greek, with no representation from ethnic minorities or migrant backgrounds. Similarly, race was homogeneous, as all participants were white. Regarding socioeconomic and educational backgrounds, the participants were predominantly middle or lower-middle class. While no visible disabilities were reported, educational attainment was notably high: at least 10 participants held undergraduate degrees, 3 had completed master’s degrees, and 1 held doctoral qualifications.

The most common profile of the respondents was a white cisgender woman in her 20s or 30s, of Greek nationality, with no migrant, ethnic minority background, or visible disability, and holding at least a university degree.

Of the 13 participants, 3 responded to the questionnaire, all of whom had also attended the previous two labs. In addition, one of them also participated in the transnational lab, which he reported in some of his answers. Among these respondents, 2 are women aged 63 and 36, and one is a man aged 23. The 2 female respondents hold master’s degrees, while the male respondent has a bachelor’s degree. One of the women, who has been involved in feminist activism for over a decade, works full-time as the director of his feminist collective. The other two respondents, whose involvement in feminist activities ranges between one and three years, identified their main professions as occupational therapist and science teacher, respectively.

Considering the questions to collect information on self-identification with intersectional identities, one person identified as belonging to the LGBTQI+ community. None of the respondents come from an ethnic or migrant background, nor do they have any disabilities or chronic illnesses.

Overview of the collectives and organisations participating in the lab

The third national lab gathered a total of 16 participants, combining returning members from previous labs with new contributors, ensuring a mix of continuity and fresh perspectives. The core group included representatives from various organisations: Mesopotamia – Moschato Citizens’ Movement (2 people), Karditsa Women’s Centre (KWC) (2 people), Rainbow School (4 people), Women’s Assembly 8th March (1 person), AUTH’s research team (3 people), AUTH’s Committee on Gender and Equality issues (2 people), and Meduses (2 people). The feminist-LGBTQIA+ collective ‘Meduses’ participated though in a personal capacity rather than as official representatives and AUTH’s Committee on Gender and Equality issues attended partially, with one connecting via Zoom on the second day.

Some shifts were observed in the group’s composition. AUTH’s research team expanded to include a doctoral and a post-doctoral researcher, while the previous post-doctoral member ended her participation in the project. Regarding the DIOTIMA, represented in earlier labs, was unable to continue due to staffing constraints from human resources. Nonetheless, most of the participants had been involved in previous sessions, ensuring continuity in discussions and outputs.

Thus, the third Greek lab was organised on June 28th and 29th 2024 with 16 participants:

- Karditsa’s Women’s Centre (2 representatives): municipal feminist non-profit organisation established in 1992, focused on the “support women in the region, without any discrimination”, giving counselling and support services. They participate and implement funded projects. The centre also offers assistance to women who are victims or survivors of GBV, but also single mothers, Roma women and refugees to find balance in their private and family life through its inclusion in the National Network established by the General Secretariat for Gender Equality in Greece. It is an organisation which also part of the local ecosystem, constituted by numerous organisations, with the aim of supporting women in the most possible and efficient way.
- Rainbow School (4 representatives): non-profit organisation founded in 2009 to empower LGBTQ+ teachers, health workers and humanities teachers. They foster Comprehensive Sexuality Education (CSE), produce educational material and conduct research. After a decade of combating discrimination in education, Rainbow School attained legal status as a civil non-profit organisation, enabling it to expand its efforts and impact further.
- Women’s Assembly 8th March (1 representative): feminist collective in Thessaloniki founded in 2019 which acts as a bottom-up front alliance. Their informal membership is not limited to women and is open to non cis and non-binary identities as well. They base their ideological framework in three pillars of class-based resistance and they participate in feminist and LGBTQ+ protests and related events, as well as in workers’ strikes, antifascist interventions and antiracist festivals, among others. They co-organise and participate in both feminist and LGBTQ protests.
- Mesopotamia – Moschato Citizens’ Movement (2 representatives): local movement formed in 2002 that started as a neighbourhood collective, which dedicates to social struggles and culture. Among their initiatives there is the Solidarity and Time Bank —based on non-monetary time exchanges to cover every day needs— and the Solidarity School which they run in alliance with Rainbow School. Since 2006 they run their own space, granted by the municipality of Moschato and where the Greek Fierce lab has been hosted. Following their partnership with the Rainbow School, Mesopotamia's Solidarity School recently created a gender group which address intersectionality in gender interactions. AUTH Committee on Gender and Equality issues (2 representatives): was reconstituted in 2022 in accordance with Article 218 of Law 4957/2022, which requires the formation of similar committees at all Greek institutions. It is a formal,

institutional committee appointed by the AUTH Senate. The group is unpaid and functions as an advisory board to the institution and its administration. Its aim is to promote gender equality and oppose discrimination based on gender, race or ethnicity, religion or beliefs, state of health/disability, age, or sexual orientation at all levels of operation, as well as all academic procedures and activities.

- Meduses (2 participants): is a feminist and LGBTQIA+ collective which was established in Larissa, in 2019-2020. It is an informal, autonomous and “multicolour” group which their members do not share a common ideological background. Originally, the main object of this collective was to disseminate feminist discourse and action, but in the last years their focus shifted to provide support and solidarity for victims of domestic violence and employees’ violence in every possible term. Two members of this collective were participated to the 3rd Danish lab with their personal capacity and did not represent the collective.

In addition, the collective DIOTIMA was not able to be present in the third lab meeting, because they had run out of resources after their participation in the first two meetings. This decision had already been informed during the second lab meeting.

- DIOTIMA – Centre for Gender Rights & Equality: feminist non-profit organisation founded in 1989 fighting against GBV developing actions such as professional support, education programmes, advocacy for policy improvements, among others. Due to time constrains and human resources issues, DIOTIMA and their representation and participation to FIERCE project ended.

For the 3rd lab questionnaire, responses to the participation questionnaire were collected from three participants, each representing an organisation or movement. Of the respondents, 2 work in separate non-profit organisations, while the third is employed at an institution formed around a movement. Collectively, the organisations tackle diverse yet complementary themes. One focuses on empowering women by addressing GBV, improving childcare services, and expanding employment opportunities, to promoting equality. Another works to eliminate discrimination based on sexual orientation, advocating for institutional change to create an inclusive educational environment. The third prioritises equal rights in education and social inclusion, ensuring that learning opportunities are accessible to all. Together, these organisations contribute to fostering equality and dismantling social barriers. One of these organisations maintains consistent collaboration with public institutions, as it is integral to achieving its foundational objectives. In contrast, the other two organisations engage in occasional cooperation, focusing primarily on specific projects and initiatives. These include efforts to align educational practices with public education standards, and foster inclusivity through joint activities with municipal authorities. While all respondents embrace an intersectional approach, two focus predominantly on women’s rights, and one prioritises LGBTQI+ advocacy. As presented in the following table, among the organisations they represent, all follow an intersectional framework; however, only two explicitly define themselves as feminist organisations.

Figure 5: Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third Greek Lab

3.3. France

Participant’s demographics

A total of 9 participants were involved in the third French lab. All participants were cisgender women, aged 23 to 71, most commonly within the 30-40 age range. The majority were white and had a high level of education—all participants held at least an undergraduate degree—. According to the discussion in the lab, 2 participants self-identified as having an ethnic or migratory background—1 of Jewish descent and 1 Black—and approximately 4 were estimated to identify as LGBTQIA+. Most represented their employing organisations, while one independent journalist participated as a non-representative of any organisation.

There were 5 replies to the questionnaire for lab participants. Among them, 4 had attended at least one of the previous lab sessions, while only one was attending for the first time. All participants identified as women. Regarding their educational background, two held a bachelor’s degree, two had completed a master’s degree, and one participant had a PhD. All of the respondents were actively within the feminist movement at least for 3 years, with 2 being active for a period of 5-10 years. It is worth highlighting that the 2 participants declaring being active for more than 10 years in the feminist movement, worked full-time in their feminist organisations, while the other participants mentioned being employed in other organisations.

Considering the questions to collect information on self-identification with intersectional identities, 1 person identified as having a disability or chronic condition, 1 as having an ethnic or migratory background and 3 as belonging to the LGBTQIA+ community. It is worth noting that 1 person affirmatively identified with the three questions.

Overview of the collectives and organisations participating in the lab

The organisational composition of the third French National Lab saw several changes compared to previous labs. While the participating organisations largely remained the same, there were notable shifts among individual participants due to staff turnover within the associations and scheduling conflicts. In total, the Lab welcomed 9 participants, 6 associations continued their involvement from earlier Labs, namely *Féministes Contre le Cyberharcèlement*, *HandsAway*, *Le Planning Familial*, *Equipop*, *SOS Homophobie*, and *#NousToutes*. A new organisation, *IPAS*, which is active at the transnational level joined the lab for the first time, bringing fresh perspectives and specialised expertise in advocacy.

Individual turnover was evident in several cases. For example, Le Planning Familial sent their International Advocacy Officer along with her intern, and #NousToutes’ representative participated via Zoom. Unfortunately, the representative from Georgette Sand, who had attended the second Lab, could not participate due to scheduling issues, while the member from the “Observatoire des violences sexistes et sexuelles en politique” also cancelled at the last minute.

Following, more details on the feminist collectives, networks and organisations participating in the French FIERCE lab are provided:

- **Féministes contre le cyberharcèlement (Feminists against Cyber-Harassment):** is an NGO focused on the fight against gender-based cyber-violence and cyber-violence against minority groups. They focus on “algorithms and the use of Internet loopholes by masculinities”. It is a self-identified feminist organisation that follows an intersectional approach and particularly supports victims of cyber-violence, whom the founders describe as predominantly black and brown women online. The organisation’s key activities include advocacy aimed at French public authorities and the European Parliament to influence legislation on cyber violence.
- **Nous Toutes (All of Us):** one of the most active French feminist movements against GBV founded in 2018. Operating without formal legal status, it maintains a strong presence through local coordination. Initially centred on addressing GBV, the collective has since adopted an intersectional and trans-feminist approach. Key issues addressed by them include feminicide, rape, and sexual harassment, with an emphasis on how these inequalities disproportionately affect different groups of women.
- **Le Planning Familial (Family Planning):** NGO that defends sexual and reproductive rights, as well as the rights of the LGBTQIA+ community, employing a rights-based an intersectional approach. The main activities of the self-identified feminist organisation, are providing direct support to women and gender minorities in France, running educational initiatives, and engaging in advocacy. Le Planning is well-connected to public institutions, receiving public funding primarily from regional authorities and co-organising campaigns on abortion rights and anti-discrimination efforts.
- **SOS-Homophobie** is an LGBTQIA+ support organisation founded in 1994 that focuses on homophobia and LGBTQIA+ discrimination, providing diverse support programmes such as an anonymous hotline, testimonials on websites, school interventions, etc. It engages in educational initiatives such as school interventions and awareness campaigns, organizes public institutions, and actively advocates for LGBTQIA+ rights in collaboration with public institutions. While the organisation does not explicitly self-identified as feminist, its efforts to oppose anti-gender movements reflect a recognition of their dual threat to both LGBTQIA+ rights and feminist values.
- **HandsAway:** born in 2016 as an app enabling victims and witness of sexual violence to alert each other, in 2020 changed focus to prevent violence against young people and vulnerable groups, as well as combating street harassment. The feminist self-identified organisation adopts an intersectional approach, collaborating with organisations representing marginalised groups such as Muslim women and transgender individuals. The organisation’s activities centre on education, training and awareness campaigns, often using humour and irony to deliver impactful messages.
- **Equipop:** focused in promoting the health and rights of women and girls around the world. “The organisation combines: social and political mobilisation, project engineering, technical assistance and partnership building to promote these rights worldwide.” As a self-identified

feminist non-governmental organisation, Equipop is actively involved in shaping public policy, including contributing to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs’ official feminist strategy for 2025, which shows partnership with public institutions to advocate for feminist foreign policy.

- IPAS: is an international NGO that focuses on advocating for abortion and contraception access, especially in Africa, Asia, and the U.S. Identifying as feminist, the organisation emphasizes reproductive rights through advocacy and field reporting. The organisation’s activities include advocacy and field reporting on the state of abortion rights, and its participations in global events related to abortion rights engaging with public institutions.

In addition, other three feminist collectives had been involved in the preparation process of the French lab; however, they were not able to attend to the third lab meeting.

- Georgette Sand: feminist collective focused in women’s emancipation and in deconstructing stereotypes, intervening in schools with trainings on financial issues emancipation issues and socio-cultural stereotypes in France that operates without formal legal status. Although it does not extensively collaborate with public institutions, the collective maintains connections with feminist politicians, influenced by the union affiliations of some members. Its activities include training sessions, communication campaigns, and protests to highlight legal and fiscal inequalities faced by women.
- #StopFisha: is an NGO focused on cyber sexism and online violence. Self-identified as feminist organises support groups for cyber-violence victims and engaging in advocacy with public institutions. Unlike many other feminist organisations, #StopFisha has chosen not to participate in broader networks and ceased attending lab meetings after their initial involvement.
- L’Observatoire contre les violences sexistes et sexuelles en politique: is a feminist NGO focusing on GBV in politics, targeting male politicians accused of harming female colleagues. Self-identifying as a feminist, the NGO’s actions include protests, reports, social media campaigns, and public events to expose and challenge such violence. It is involved in various informal European networks, including the European Lesbian Conference, and collaborates with Belgian feminists which shown as examples of their intersectional approach.

To sum up, the seven organisations involved in the third French Fierce lab represent a diverse mix of approaches and structures. Of these, six are NGOs, including one international organisation (IPAS), while the seventh is a collective (Nous Toutes). Among the participating entities, five explicitly self-identify as feminist, while SOS-Homophobie does not explicitly define itself as feminist but still engages in women’s studies and LGBTQIA+ advocacy. Five of the organisations adopt an intersectional approach, addressing a wide range of issues such as GBV, reproductive rights, cyber-violence, and LGBTQIA+ rights. This shared focus on intersectionality highlights the organisations’ commitment to understanding and addressing the complex ways in which various forms of discrimination intersect and impact on individuals. Through their varied organisational forms and thematic focuses, all seven organisations contribute to advancing feminist activism and challenging systemic inequalities in their respective areas of work.

For the third lab questionnaire, responses to the feedback questionnaire were collected from 5 participants, each representing an organisation or collective). Regarding their thematic focus, 2 of the organisations focus on abortion and women's sexual and reproductive rights, while the other 3 address GBV —one specifically focused on cyber violence—. Among these, 2 organisations conduct advocacy activities primarily by lobbying French authorities, making it their core approach. The other 3 aim to raise awareness by influencing the general public through communication and social media campaigns.

When asked about their organisations' cooperation with public institutions, 2 participants reported occasional collaboration, while the other 3 indicated regular cooperation. For those who reported occasional engagement, their involvement typically includes attending consultation meetings, such as those held by the National Assembly, the High Council for Equality between Women and Men, and other public bodies. On the other hand, organisations with regular cooperation maintain ongoing relationship with public institutions across various levels. In some cases, organisations also work closely with ministries and governments to advocate for gender justice, reproductive rights and access to sexual health services. Through lobbying efforts, they aim to influence public policies and secure funding for research and capacity-building initiatives that support the defence of human rights and counter anti-right movements.

Despite differences in organisational approaches, all participating organisations identified themselves as feminists and adopted an intersectional approach in their work. The intersectional component of their advocacy is reflected in the diverse and interconnected networks and alliances they engage in regional, national and European levels. This intersectional approach is not only embedded in the organisational structure and strategy but also extends to the collaborative efforts and coalitions these organisations are part of. For instance, some engage with movements addressing femicides in collaboration with trans and sex workers' organisations, while others focus on the intersection of women's rights with broader social justice issues, including environmental and labour movements.

Figure 6: Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third French Lab

3.4. Italy

Participant's demographics

There were 10 participants to the third Italian lab. To establish the sociodemographic characteristics of the lab, the main inputs has been the replies to the questionnaire of participation to the co-creation path, which was applied during the session in a dedicated timeslot of the agenda of half an hour. In addition, it was sent via email to all the participants of the lab, which had participated to the previous sessions. In total, the questionnaire was sent to 23 unique participants to the co-creation process, collecting 12 answers: 10 of the participants attending the third lab, as well as 2 additional answers from participants to previous sessions.

All of the respondents had participated to the previous sessions of the lab, while there were only 4 new attendants. Of them, 2 were part of organisations involved since the first in-presence lab, one was a relative of a participant involved since the first lab and only one participant was completely new. This

person, an educator with many years of experience working in EAD, who was a personal contact of one of the Italian FIERCE partners and was involved because she is a Venetian feminist, which had been invited to a preparatory meeting of the FIERCE week with local feminist movements.

The most common profile of the respondent, according to the reported demographic characteristics, was a white heterosexual cisgender woman in her early 40s, with a secondary university degree (Master), active in the feminist movement for at least five years.

Considering the age distribution, 4 participants were in their early 30s, 3 participants in their early 40s, 4 participants were between 45 and 55, while one participant was 75. Regarding the gender distribution, only 2 men replied the questionnaire, while 10 of the respondents had a university degree and most of them (8) defined as “employee” their current employment situation. Some self-identification questions were included in the questionnaire with the aim to inquire about their background and intersectional identities. According to them, 1 person identified as having a disability or chronic condition, 1 as having an ethnic or migratory background and 3 as belonging to the LGBTIQ+ community.

All of the participants —with the exception of the participant that was a relative of other participant— were directly exercising EAD: 7 of the 12 respondents were school teachers, educators of trainers in this field, one is a librarian activist working in related publications and another a coordinator of an anti-violence centre (*centro antiviolenza*).

Overview of the collectives and organisations participating in the lab

Most of the participants (7 of 10) of the third Italian lab participated representing the movement, collective or organisation of belonging. In particular, they belonged to the following networks:

- Organisations belonging to the network *Educare alle Differenze*: national network of associations working to promote self-determination, build open imaginaries and cultures, combat all forms of discrimination and deconstruct stereotypes in education. The three organisations that are part of this network and participated in the lab are:
 - SCOSSE-Soluzioni comunicative studi servizi editoriali (no participants in the third Italian lab, one representative replied to the questionnaire): association founded in 2011 in Rome which focus their work for the respect of gender and sexual orientation differences, for hospitality, interculture, the rights of foreign citizens, of people with disabilities and for sentimental and sexual education. No participants in the third Italian lab, one representative replied to the questionnaire.
 - Indici Paritari (2 participants in the third Italian lab): association of teachers working for the inclusion of the lives of more women in school books and to abolish the masculine gender as inclusive language (in Italian).
 - APS Epimeleia (2 participants in the third Italian lab): association founded in 2014 as a centre for gender research and education to promote the rights and social and cultural development of women, the promotion of the right to health as a social good. They implement activities aimed at preventing and combating different forms of violence, mistreatment and abuse.
- Lucha y Siesta – Feminist and trans-feminist common good (2 participants in the third Italian lab): it is a feminist and trans-feminist space located in Rome active since 2008 working as a social and anti-violence centre and shelter for women escaping from violence. There were 2 participants in the third Italian lab. One participant in the third Italian lab.

- Lovelab Project (1 participant in the third Italian lab): local project on education to differences implemented in two municipalities in Florence.

Two of the three other attendees of the third Italian lab that were individual participants belonged one to Non Una di Meno (the largest transfeminist movement) and the other to the Italian Association of Trainers (*Associazione Italiana Formatori*).

The following organisations and networks participated in the previous meetings of the Italian lab and, even though they were not able to participate in this meeting due to other personal or work commitments, communication is still open online and they have given their availability to contribute with the last steps of the self-defence manual:

- Rete Lenford – Law for LGBTI+ rights: association founded in 2007 composed of lawyers, practitioners, jurists, students and individuals with proven experience or expertise in LGBTI+ matters who advocate for the respect of LGBTI+ rights. They engage in the prevention, protection and promotion in the field of combating discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity through giving legal advice and implementing activities for the respect of these fundamental rights.
- Social cooperative CAT: organisation of the third sector founded in 1985 in Florence working in the promotion of social work in different areas: immigration, childhood and adolescence, prostitution and human trafficking, among others (1 participant that was an educator).
- Love my way project (one respondent to the questionnaire), NGO working on the promotion of LGBTQIA+ rights.

The following figure synthesises some of the characteristics of the organisations/collectives/networks present in the Italian lab according to the 11 relevant replies of the questionnaire (one was excluded because the participant was a relative of another one not working related to the topics of the lab).

Figure 7: Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third Italian Lab

As detailed in Figure 7, almost all of the organisations, where implementing teaching or training activities in EAD, where feminist collectives (2 of the 9 defined as transfeminist) and were implementing an intersectional approach. When asked about the themes of focus in their organisations, they were broader than EAD. In particular, 4 respondents mentioned GBV. Other themes addressed were: sexual and reproductive rights, gender equality, self-determination, use of inclusive language, among others.

Considering that education to differences is implemented in public schools and closely related to the institutional guidelines defined by the Ministry of Education and Merit, 10 of 11 respondents replied having at least some sort of collaboration with public institutions. When asked about the types of activities implemented in collaboration with the public sector, most of them reported EAD in schools. One participant replied preferring the implementation of grassroots activities even if they collaborate with public institutions.

Regarding the active networks in the lab, most of the participants mentioned the Educare Alle Differenze Network. Other mentioned collectives with active alliances were: Non Una di Meno, Donne in Rete Contro la Violenza (D.i.Re), Italian Society of Historians (Società Italiana delle Storiche), Italian Society of Literary Women (Società Storica delle Letterate), National Network of Anti-Violence Centres, Network of Regional Counselling Centre Coordination, among others.

3.5. Poland

Participant’s demographics

18 participants, all of whom had taken part in the first lab, were invited to join the third lab. Of these, only 8 were able to attend. Notably, no new participants joined the third lab, as all attendees had been involved in previous sessions. A potential new addition to the group was unable to participate due to health issues. The decline in attendance was attributed to personal responsibilities, including academic commitments, as well as health-related challenges.

Among the 8 attendees, all were women who had also participated in both previous labs, ensuring continuity in discussions among participants. All of the participants declared as ‘radical’ feminists rather than ‘moderate’ ones. In the Polish context: *“This distinction, introduced by Elżbieta Korolczuk (allegedly) distinguishes the new, post-2016, wave of feminists from the older one. As scholars have described the emergence of the Polish feminist movement (eg. Mandes 2010), it originated in two places: at universities, through gender studies departments, and the more radical faction, focused on grassroots activism, street politics and street protests. The one academic Lab member was also involved in the introduction of GEPs at the Polish Academy of Sciences, having impact on institutional life; she also have been involved in more ‘official’ (i.e. state sponsored) campaigns encouraging girls and women into turning to science.”*

Out of the 8 participants in the Polish lab, only 1 responded to the questionnaire. This participant, a 37-year-old woman with a PhD, has attended the previous two labs and works as a researcher and adjunct professor. Regarding questions aimed at gathering information on self-identification with intersectional identities, she indicated that she does not identify as having a disability or as a member of the LGBTIQ+ community but acknowledged having an ethnic or migrant background. Having been involved in feminist activism for a year or less, she participated in this lab as an individual rather than as a representative of any organisation.

There was a significant number of dropouts in the lab, going from a very populated first meeting with 16 participants to a significant decrease of around half of the participants during the second and third meetings—with 9 and 8 participants, respectively—. Although all of the participants to the first meeting were contacted and most of them manifested their interest, participation to the second meeting was affected due to a seasonal flu and covid outburst in Polish. Meanwhile, they were also invited to the third meeting; however, many of them did not respond or mentioned different excuses to dismiss their participation.

Polish FIERCE partners mentioned that two possible causes of the dropout. The first one, related to the related to the ‘biographical availability’, i.e. developments in their private lives (as completing university and entering to the labour market or getting married and establishing a family); therefore, reducing

their time availability for activism and political actions. In addition, there were some of the participants ‘movement celebrities’ —*“very well recognisable, with lots of publicity and media recognition who seemed to be polarising for some other lab members”*—, who dropped out from the groups because of limits in their schedules.

Overview of the collectives and organisations participating in the lab

The group was composed of individuals with varied backgrounds and experiences, representing distinct perspectives. Among these were:

- Academic-activist hybrid representation (2 participants): These individuals brought a unique blend of scholarly insight and activism, with one playing a notable role in integrating Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) at the Polish Academy of Science.
- Political sector representation (1 participant): Although their input highlighted critical policy implications, this person had recently decided to drop back from political activism due to internal disputes over electoral positions and office allocations.
- Women’s rights activism (5 participants): these participants represented various feminist networks and organisations, contributing a range of grassroots perspectives.

All attendees to the lab participate as individuals rather than representing their collectives or organisations. Affiliations in the lab were not treated ‘officially’ because *“due to low levels of formalisation of the Polish feminist movement, however all lab participants had broad contacts with other activists and activist networks, mostly stemming from the All-Polish Women’s Strike (Ogólnopolski Strajk Kobiet), Gals for Gals (Dziewuchy Dziewuchom, later Dziewuchy) as well as numerous local networks / organisations (Trójmiejska Akcja Kobieta, One Billion Rising and others). This shows the unorganised and rhizomatic nature of Polish feminist movement with loose or multiple memberships, focused more on action rather than belonging (according to an anarchist rule, due to which membership is achieved through action rather than a formal belonging”*.

Despite this, below is included the description of some of the collectives that they belong to:

- OSK (OSK Sochaczew, OSK Rybotycze) - All Polish Women’s Strike (Ogólnopolski Strajk Kobiet) - the biggest network of feminist activists in Poland, emerged in 2016 during the preparations for the Black Protest. The notion of Women’s Strike was taken from the experiences of Icelandic women who organised a strike in 1975. It is now the biggest network with multiple local chapters.
- OBR Trójmiasto - One Billion Rising from Tricity in Poland (Gdańsk, Gdynia and Sopot) One Billion Rising is the biggest mass action to end violence against women (cisgender, transgender, and those who hold fluid identities that are subject to gender-based violence) in human history. The campaign, which launched on Valentine’s Day 2012, began as a call to action based on the staggering statistic that 1 in 3 women on the planet will be beaten or raped during her lifetime.
- WIDE + is a European network of associations and activists that fights for women’s rights, as part of a larger struggle for social justice, sustainable livelihoods and human rights, advocating for changing European policies that affect people in and outside of Europe. WIDE+ promotes inclusive and intersectional feminist movement building in Europe, in solidarity with feminists in the global South. One of the participants of the Polish lab was member of this transnational organisation.
- Różowa Skrzyneczka [Pink Box] is a loosely organised initiative to provide feminine hygiene products in public spaces (in pink boxes): mostly in schools, but also offices and other places, in order to combat exclusion of women due to economic status. These pink boxes appear in more and more schools and other public places every day.

- OTSNM - O Tym Się Nie Mówi [One Does Not Speak of This] - an initiative that produced a documentary movie under the same title to show the real circumstances of the abortion debate in Poland and gives voice to lawyers and doctors. The idea of the movie appeared after the Constitutional Tribunal declared as unconstitutional one of the clauses allowing for termination of pregnancy - when the foetus is irreversibly disfigured or otherwise challenged. The ‘pro-life’ activists tried to force their narrative as those cases (around 97% of all legal abortions conducted in Poland) were cases of fetuses with Down syndrome. The O Tym Się Nie Mówi movie aimed at showing that these were in fact more serious and usually fatal illnesses.
- LABK - Legalna Aborcja Bez Kompromisów [Legal Abortion Without Compromise] - a legal initiative to introduce legal abortion in Poland. It’s main focus is to address the population about the cause, but also to lobby among political parties to support their initiative, especially when it is being voted in the Polish parliament.
- ADT - Aborcynjny Dream Team [Abortion Dream Team] - a loose network helping with abortions, either by providing pharmacological solutions or organising trips for women in need abroad, where abortion is legal (Germany, Scandinavian countries, Czech Republic, Slovakia). According to them, since their emergence, they helped over 50,000 women in Poland to have a safe abortion.

The sole respondent to the questionnaire stated that she did not represent any organisation or collective. As a result, she chose not to answer questions related to organisational structure or content. Therefore, in the Polish case, it is not possible to draw any conclusions regarding the organisational aspects based on the questionnaire responses.

3.6. Slovenia

In Slovenia, the lab’s outcome was a public exhibition focused on sexual and reproductive rights which was titled: "Reproductive Rights: On Health, Sexuality, and Equality of Women". The exhibition and lab sessions were conceived and prepared jointly by Slovenian FIERCE partners —UL and MI— and by a core group of three feminist activists. Thus, the first and second sessions of the lab were dedicated to developing the content of the exhibition, while the inauguration of the exhibition is considered and reported in the present document as the third lab meeting. The exhibition was in place in Ljubljana between May 7th to 20th 2024.

Participant’s demographics

The core group of the Slovenian lab consisted of three feminist activists who were active in the preparation of the exhibition since the beginning of the co-creation process. One of them is the current president of the Women’s Lobby of Slovenia and she was a member of the Parliament between 1990 and 1992, promoting the inclusion of abortion in the Slovenian Constitution. Regarding the other two members: both are feminist activists and one is also a researcher studying the intersections of feminism, media, technology, and capitalism, while the other is a writer, editor and translator about feminist theory, activism and art. Both of them are feminist activists. The graphic designer that developed the exhibition posters was included as an active member of the core group. She is a socially critical author who expresses herself in various media, putting drawing in the foreground in addition to video.

The invitation to the exhibition opening was sent to individuals, feminist groups, initiatives, organisations and media. Since the opening of the feminist exhibition on May 7th with guided tour was an open event, participants did not need to register in advance. Around 20 people attended the exhibition opening and the guided tour, with a total of 10 people signing the attendance list at the reception at the end of the exhibition.

After the opening of the exhibition, other guided tours were organised:

- May 14th: one journalist of the daily newspaper Delo (1 person)
- May 16th: Consortium members of the project FemQueer: Common Strategies for Gender Equality (6 people)
- May 17th: Participants of the Feminist Anti-Fascist Network - FAMA conference titled “From the 1974 Constitution to Limiting Women's Rights”, which took place in Ljubljana between 17-19 May 2024 (35 people)
- May 18th: for a member of the FIERCE Italian project team (1 person)

In total, around 62 people attended to the guided visits of the exhibition. In addition, it is difficult to estimate how many people walking in the street accesses to the exhibition stopping to read the posters.

The opening day of the exhibition, 10 people filled a registration form. Slovenian FIERCE partners reported 7 external participants besides the core group. The group was conformed by a majority of women (9 out of 11), mostly with a high degree of superior education (at least 4 had a PhD) with different backgrounds: Academia, several are feminist activists, other are artist, are involved in politics and one was a journalist.

3 participants from Slovenia responded to the feedback questionnaire, all belonging to the core group. Among them, 2 had previously attended the earlier lab sessions, while 1 participated for the first time. All respondents identified as women, 2 were in their mid-forties and one in her seventies, while of them had a Master's degree considering their educational backgrounds. Regarding employment status, 2 participants are self-employed, while 1 is retired. In terms of their involvement in feminist activism, one participant has been active since the 1970s, another for over ten years, and the third for a period ranging from five to ten years. Notably, the participant active since the 1970s continues to work in a voluntary capacity, focusing on feminist advocacy and lobbying. When asked about their intersectional identities, none of the participants identified as having a disability or chronic condition, belonging to an ethnic or migratory background, or being part of the LGBTIQ+ community.

Overview of the collectives and organisations participating in the lab

All of the participants from the core group with exception of the President of the Women's Lobby of Slovenia were participating as individual participants. Following is an overview of the key feminist collectives and networks represented in the Slovenian FIERCE Lab. The FAMA network is described, as they were organising a conference during the day of the exhibition, where lab members were invited to present the initiative:

- **The Women's Lobby of Slovenia:** As a prominent non-governmental organisation, the Women's Lobby of Slovenia serves as a national feminist umbrella organisation, uniting NGOs, academics, and advocates for gender equality in Slovenia. As a member of the European Women's Lobby (EWL), the largest network of women's NGOs in the European Union, the Women's Lobby of Slovenia focuses on enhancing the visibility and influence of women's organisations in the country. Their key activities include lobbying for legal frameworks supporting gender equality, collaborating with public institutions such as ministries, women's parliamentary clubs, and political parties, as well as conducting research and awareness campaigns in schools. The organisation maintains active partnerships with European trade unions, the OSCE, and FAMA, reflecting its commitment to intersectional and transnational feminist solidarity.
- **Feminist Antifascist Network (FAMA):** Established on 6 December 2023, FAMA serves as a regional network uniting feminist activists, groups, and organisations from the countries of the former Yugoslavia. Created as a collective response to rising anti-feminist and anti-democratic trends in the region, FAMA operates as a platform for collaborative activism, knowledge-sharing, and collective action. Its annual conference, held in Ljubljana from 17 to 19 May 2024, brought together over 50 activists and experts to discuss and assess the state of women's

reproductive and sexual rights across the region. FAMA plays a critical role in amplifying regional feminist voices while fostering alliances across national and cultural boundaries.

Regarding organisational representation in the questionnaire, while 2 participants did not represent specific organisations, only one participant attended on behalf of an organisation, namely the *Women Lobby of Slovenia*. This organisation operates as a national feminist umbrella NGO, coordinating with the European Women’s Lobby (EWL). Its thematic focus spans all crucial gender equality issues, with primary advocacy activities centred on lobbying and promoting a legal framework to achieve tangible gender equality in daily life. Collaboration with public institutions was reported as occasional. Activities primarily include lobbying ministries, engaging with parliamentary women’s groups, collaborating with university experts, and conducting awareness-raising initiatives in schools. This organisation identifies as a feminist organisation and adheres to an intersectional approach in its work. Their networks include the EWL, Slovene and European Trade Unions, OSCE-ODIHR, the Feminist Antifascist Network (Balkan region), and the Voice of the People network, comprising over 100 NGOs in Slovenia. Each of these networks integrates intersectional perspectives into their strategies and initiatives.

3.7. Spain

Participant’s demographics

The Spanish lab was focused on care work under addressed under a broad, intersectional and inter-territorial perspective, including the perspective of care givers and care receivers. During the first lab, Spanish FIERCE partners tried establishing a core group; however, after some failed attempts, they convoked different stakeholders in the lab, inviting a variety of organisations, networks and activists from realities focused on different spheres of care. The initial invitation included described the lab’s theme, approach and the profile of participants with the invitation to suggest other collectives.

The Spanish co-creation lab experienced a progressive drop-out throughout the process with 21 external participants to the first session, 14 to the second one —11 from the first session and 3 new participants from organisations that had participated in the first lab— and only 6 during the third lab meeting. Regarding the drop-up, Spanish FIERCE partners reported that several participants communicated their reason for being unable to attend but reaffirmed their interest and commitment to join the network, while some other participants did not inform of their absence in advance. After the first lab, 3 participants from the Basque Country decided not to continue their participation because *“They anticipated that the action would focus on promoting a public, state-wide system of care, which they believed conflicted with their struggle for a community-based public care system in the Basque Country/Euskadi.”*

The feedback questionnaire was replied by 8 participants that participated at least to one of the sessions. Throughout the three sessions, there was a total of 24 participants involved: 21 women, 2 men, and 1 person identifying as trans. Most of the participants were over 30, with the older being over 60 years old. Respondents to the questionnaire had between 42 and 64 years old. Among the participants who answered the survey, the education level is high - six out of eight persons hold a master's or doctoral degree.

Considering intersectional identities, one person with functional diversity required the accompaniment of a personal assistant. In additional, on the feedback survey, 2 participants indicate having chronic disease or other functional diversity. Approximately six or seven participants had a migrant background from Latin America. In the survey, one person identified as a racialised person. In the feedback questionnaire, 1 of the 8 persons that replied it, self-identified as an LGBTIQ+ person, in addition several of the participants have been actively involved in the movement for LGBTQ+ rights with 2 having leading roles in the movement, 1 of them is focused on older people.

Regarding their employment situation, 3 advocates for migrant domestic workers' rights had worked as household and care workers themselves, 3 feminist academics are experts in care-related issues and 1 academic is experts in feminist policy in departments of feminisms and LGBTQI+ issues. In addition, 3 participants were politicians/policymakers with experience in feminist policy in departments of feminisms and LGBTQI+ issues.

Overview of the collectives and organisations participating in the lab

All of the collectives, networks and organisations involved in the Spanish lab are focused on care work issues, which has been a central theme for the Spanish feminist movement since the March 8th feminist strikers of 2018 and 2019. Diverse groups have been involved to represent an intersectional and inter-territorial perspective: *“The actors involved in the lab are diverse, yet most share a commitment to advocating for the dignification of care work and the social reorganisation of care. While their approaches and areas of focus vary across collectives, they broadly support the key demands developed through the lab: (1) the universal right to care, (2) rights and decent working conditions for household and care workers, and (3) rights, time, and financial support for those providing informal care to family and friends within the community”*. They have been classified by Spanish FIERCE partners as:

- Euskal Herriko Neska Gazteak: feminist movement that participated in the organisation of the general feminist care strike in the Basque Country (November 2023).
- Euskal Herriko Bilgune Feminista: feminist movement that participated in the organisation of the general feminist care strike in the Basque Country (November 2023).
- AFUS (*Asamblea Feminista Unitaria Sevilla*): is a feminist assembly that was created with the aim of strengthening the feminist movement in the region. It was formed shortly before 8M 2018, with the aim of bringing together and coordinating different women's collectives for the organisation of the strike. The assembly is a non-partisan, non-mixed space, with the aim of overthrowing patriarchy and all other oppressive systems. Emphasis on mutual support and daily needs. They describe themselves as inclusive and diverse, and wanting to be more diverse every day. Participation in AFUS assemblies is on an individual level.
- Farmamundi: NGO for international cooperation promoting integral health and pharmaceutical aid. It promotes universal access to health through sustainable social transformation. It is the first non-profit organisation in Spain specialising in pharmaceutical supply and aid to humanitarian organisations and developing countries.

Activists from the migrant domestic workers' movement

- SEDOAC: domestic workers' association that demands full equality and the exercise of social, political, labour and civil rights for domestic workers.
- Territorio Doméstico: is a feminist and mestizo collective of women, many of them - but not all - domestic workers, who demand rights, visibility and social reorganisation of care work. This collective has been a key actor in the struggle for the recognition of rights of domestic workers and for the various policy reforms that have been carried out in the field. They have also played an important role in putting domestic workers rights and the reorganisation of care on the feminist agenda and in the 8M demonstration and strikes. Occasional collaboration with public institutions includes participation in the Working group on care with the Ministry of Equality, and a project to make a film supported by the Women's Institute.
- La Comala: is a non-profit worker cooperative created in 2017. This cooperative aims to put care in the centre. It offers household and care services and promotes decent working conditions. The organisations in a workers' cooperative was chosen for its principles and values, the democratic functioning and the high degree of participation of the members. It is a question of satisfying people's needs as opposed to economic profit, and an alternative to self-employment

under decent conditions. Worker-members contribute to the social security system, which gives them access to more benefits and subsidised vocational training, coverage against professional accidents and all the other benefits of a working person.

Activists advocating to include better working conditions in care services

- Association of Home Care Workers in Madrid (*Asociación de Trabajadoras de Atención Domiciliaria*): not information found about the collective.
- ELA trade union (Basque Country): Euskal Langileen Alkartasuna – Basque Workers Solidarity (ELA, Basque Country): Trade Union that has mobilised claims for improving care, particularly residential care for older people, and better working conditions for care workers. They participated in the organisation of the general care strike in the Basque Country (November 2023). The Union also organise workers in other sectors.

Activists from the LGBTIQ+ rights movement

- Foundation 26 December: non-profit, state-wide organisation. It was created to advocate the visibility of older LGTBIQ+ people, and it promotes support and services adapted to this collective. The name refers to 26 December 1978, the day of the ratification of the modification of Law 16/1970 on Dangerousness and Social Rehabilitation, a landmark for the LGTBIQ+ community and their struggle for equal rights.
- La Morada: is a feminist co-housing project, an initiative formed mainly by people with dissident identities. It seeks to reconstruct and reorganise care and to support a model of living together that goes beyond the institution of the nuclear family. They promote feminism, sustainability, community and solidarity in everyday life. The co-housing project started in 2018 when they formed a housing cooperative. This involved a protest criticising the housing market; finding a place to live has become expensive and many women are excluded.

Activists from the disability movement

- Forum of Independent Living: Forum of Independent Living is a community made up of people from all over Spain, and beyond. It was founded in mid-2001 with the aim of promoting the Independent Living movement in Spain, which emerged in the USA in 1960s and is now deeply rooted in Europe. They are members of the European Network for Independent Living (ENIL). They are a forum for philosophical reflection and struggle for the rights of people with functional diversity. There is no formal organisational structure or formal membership, the forum has no legal status. Participation is direct and based on equality. Their advocacy is largely online, but they also hold face-to-face meetings for general participation and participate in conferences etc.

Activists promoting a rights-based approaches to care and dignified care within the community

- A3 Calles: is a service cooperative for local care. It started in 2019 and in 2021 it was restarted after a break during the first phase of the covid pandemic crisis. They aim to create a self-managed experience of dignified care and demand that public administrations provide policies and sufficient funding to meet the needs of citizens and their right to be cared for.
- ACUFADE (Canary Islands): a non-profit Association of Carers, Relatives and Friends of People with Dependency, Alzheimer, and other Dementias. ACUFADE is constituted as a feminist entity that bases its efforts and exercises on the achievement of the principles of transversality, intersectionality, equal opportunities and co-responsibility in care. It is also committed to sustainability and care for the environment, integrating the Sustainable Development Goals in its practice. They work for the wellbeing of older people and people with disabilities, and the people who care for them. They provide care services, hold training sessions, carry out studies

etc. Collaboration agreements signed with the Canarian public administration are mainly aimed at providing/financing social action services or projects. Acufade participates in the international networks with EUROCARES, and feminist networks such as Red Tenerife Violeta and Red Tenerife Solidaria.

Politicians

- Barcelona en Comú (2 members) in the Department of Feminisms and LGTBIQ
- Más Madrid: A councillor from the party that positions as a green and feminist alternative.

Other non-governmental organisations (NGOs)

- Platform for Children’s rights: alliance of non-profit, plural, democratic and politically and religiously independent entities that work to achieve full compliance with the rights of children and adolescents.
- Association of Single Mothers by Choice: non-governmental, not-for-profit, state-wide organisation for single mothers who chose to have children and form a single-parent family. They advocate the non-discrimination of these families.

From the aforementioned organisations, the ones that were present in the third lab were: Territorio Domestico, ACUFADE, the Association Single Mothers by Choice, Farmamundi. In addition, two academic experts on care participated. It is worth highlighting that most of these participants decided to participate as individuals and not as representatives of their organisations in the lab.

Regarding these organisations, they employ a wide range of strategies and tactics: *“from those more directly involved in the provision of care services, such as La Comala and A3Calles to those with a strong focus on feminist activism and/or policy demands, like Territorio Doméstico, Euskal Herriko Bilgune Feminista or AFUS.”*

Regarding the feminist affiliation of the collectives involved in the lab, Spanish FIERCE partners reported that all of the organisations involved in the Spanish lab recognised themselves as part of broader feminist struggles; however, that for some the term “feminism” is not central in their activism: *“Examples include La Comala, A3Calles, and the Foundation 26th of December. This may be because their work is more practical, focusing on organising care services, or because their main focus is different (such as focus on ageing and LGTBIQ+ rights). Nonetheless their work aligns with feminist values.”*

Despite this, all of the collectives involved in the lab are rooted in *intersectional feminism* and a trans-inclusive approach, which was ratified by the 8 respondents to the survey. *“The way organisations, groups, and collectives frame this perspective varies, influenced by the specific nature of their work. In some cases, intersectional feminism is not explicitly mentioned as such in their public descriptions. Despite this, during the lab sessions and in the final survey, the participants expressed alignment with intersectional feminist principles”.*

Regarding the work with public institutions, *“many of the participants emphasised the goal of influencing public policy. Feminist advocacy is generally not only intersectional but also anti-institutional in nature, but several organisations and collectives acknowledged the importance of engaging with political representatives, the value of having institutional allies, and the potential for collaboration with institutions in specific contexts. The relationship between organisations and public institutions varies. The survey revealed that some organisations frequently collaborate with public institutions, while domestic workers’ collectives do so only occasionally or rarely”.*

Regarding the alliances with other collectives, it is common that Spanish feminist collectives ally with other local grassroots groups, such as domestic workers’ organisations, housing rights groups, environmental groups, LGTBIQ+ groups, and anti-racist groups. The following figure presents the

characteristics of the organisations in terms of feminist affiliation, implementation of an intersectional approach and collaboration with the government.

Figure 8: Characteristics of organisations participating in Third Spanish Lab

3.8. Turkey

Participant’s demographics

The third lab meeting brought together 17 external participants, the majority of whom had attended the second lab. In addition to the core group, composed by 3 feminist activists that had participated to the transnational lab sessions, two additional participants were invited in quality of experts, to present on the workings of Europe-wide international organisations and how civil society organisations engage with them. In addition, two new participants were invited, who had also been interviewed in WP2 and that had been unable to attend the two prior labs due to other commitments. These two new participants were familiar with the project's goals. Another two participants who joined for the first time, are from organisations that had previously been represented by others in earlier labs.

The most common profile of the participants in the third lab was a middle-aged woman, primarily in their 30s or 40s, with substantial experience in feminist activism and civil society initiatives. Most participants were long-term contributors to the project, representing feminist collectives or organisations and demonstrating familiarity with the national lab's objectives.

The feedback questionnaire for lab participants was filled by 4 participants to the third Turkish lab. Among them, 3 had attended to both of the previous lab sessions, while only one had participated only to one of the previous sessions. Respondents ranged in age from 30 to 57, with 3 in their 30s and one in their 50s. All 4 participants who responded to the questionnaire identified their gender as woman. Regarding their educational background, one held a bachelor’s degree, two completed a master’s degree, and one participant had a PhD. All of the respondents were actively within the feminist movement at least from 5 years, with one being active for a period of 5-10 years and the other 3 for more than 10 years. Considering the latter, one of them worked full-time in the civil society organisations, another one mentioned being self-employed as an architect, and last one is currently unemployed and searching for a job.

Considering the questions to collect information on self-identification with intersectional identities, 1 person identified as having a disability or chronic condition, and another as having an ethnic or migratory background while also belonging to the LGBTIQ+ community.

Overview of the collectives and organisations participating in the lab

Similarly, to the first two labs, participants were convoked as individual activists —not being asked to participate in representing the organisations, and taking direct, individual contact. The motivation for this was to avoid internal conflicts due to the context of polarization inside the feminist movement and in the country —characterised by a conservative government that is cutting individual freedoms and openly opposing and attacking supporters of feminist issues and gender equality actions. For the same reason, participants were not asked to self-identify their gender, ethnicity, or religiosity openly in the lab. It is worth remarking that it was decided not to include the name of the participating organisations in the deliverables for security reasons, considering the increasing repression of feminist activists are suffering due to the far-right political regime.

Despite participating as individuals in the third Turkish lab, the 17 participants involved were part of a wide range of organisations and collectives. While most participants were involved in feminist activism, some also spoke about their collectives activities within the transnational arena. Several of the participants had experience with more than one collective. The following outlines the types of collectives, their focus areas, and the repertoires of action and networks they engage with. Among the participating organisations and collectives, 10 of them primarily focused on women's issues, while 2 or more also concentrated on LGBTQIA+ topics. In total, it can be estimated that at least 12 organisations were involved in the lab.

There were 17 participants from 12+ organisations inside the Turkish lab focusing on different thematic areas:

- 2 Collectives as larger platforms:

Out of all the collectives that participated in the lab, two of them can be considered larger platforms, where feminist and women's organisations can become members. One platform/collective is an international network of women's civil society organisations across European countries, with formal membership and delegates chosen to represent the network. This platform primarily focuses on lobbying EU bodies to promote gender equality in all policies and decisions. The second platform/collective, based in Turkey, began with a focus on GBV and child sexual abuse and has grown to include broader topics, such as legal issues and covered threats to gender equality in public discourses. Its range of action includes national campaigns, press releases, data production, and lobbying opposition parties which have representatives in the parliament.

- 3 organisations/foundations which have broader approach:

Among the organisations represented in the lab, three stand out for their dedication to women's rights and gender equality. These organisations address a broad spectrum of issues, including combating discrimination, promoting women's human rights, and fostering solidarity. Their activities encompass organizing campaigns, providing training sessions, and collaborating with public institutions, particularly municipalities, to deliver women's rights seminars. One organisation is distinguished by its history of international advocacy, including contributions to CEDAW shadow reports, while another prioritizes support for refugee women through targeted initiatives. Additionally, one manages women-only spaces to enhance solidarity and empowerment.

- 2 collectives for knowledge production

The other two participants work with two different collectives and focus on knowledge production through online platforms and research. One produces feminist knowledge globally, including writing and research by collective members, and distributes funding to various

women’s groups. The other focuses on the intersectional experiences of pious women and runs projects in collaboration with municipalities.

- 3 single-issue organisations:

The organisations represented in the lab include two focused on combating violence against women, providing survivor support, and engaging in advocacy. One specializes in femicide cases, monitoring trials, supporting survivors, and publishing related data. The other is notable for organizing a national conference that connects women’s organisations across the country. A third organisation focuses on menstrual rights, providing advocacy and services to women in poverty and disaster-stricken areas.

- 2 or more collectives focuses on LGBT people:

Finally, other organisations focus on LGBTQI+ rights, organizing advocacy work and contributing to social policies to prevent discrimination. These groups also run legal and psychological support services and provide outreach for at-risk youth.

Out of the 17 participants, 4 responded to the feedback questionnaire. As previously mentioned, they participated in the lab as individuals, not representing their collectives and networks; however, the replies to the questionnaire included questions about their organisations, providing valuable insights for the analysis. 2 of the respondents work for civil society organisations: one focuses on women’s rights in general, while the other is dedicated to menstrual justice in Türkiye. The other two participants are affiliated with platforms; one addresses law-related issues, including the withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention, the civil code, and alimony, while the other focuses on violence against women and LGBTQI+ equality in Turkish society.

All four organisations/collectives identify themselves as feminist and adopt an intersectional approach in their work however, only two reports an occasional cooperation with public institutions (Figure 9). One of the two collaborates with institutions to ensure the sustainability of menstrual products by organizing fieldwork, informational activities, and menstrual care kit distribution. The other works to combat violence against women, conducting self-defence workshops on the days like November 25th and March 8th, in collaboration with municipalities, as part of its efforts. The remaining two organisations do not engage in direct cooperation with public institutions. Instead, one focuses on advocacy campaigns targeting policymaking through social media platforms, addressing issues in a broader context. The other platform which has no legal status specialises in organising campaigns on advocacy processes for legal matters, concentrating on the Istanbul Convention’s process and alimony rights.

Figure 9: Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third Turkish Lab

3.9. Transnational lab

The transnational lab was organised as a space of encounter between all national labs and EU level feminist actors. This process started in Brussels on September 19th 2023 with the first lab meeting, where it was decided to implement a campaign for the European Parliament (EP) 2024 elections. The content of the campaign —titled “Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe”⁵— was developed collaboratively inside the lab in a two-day in-presence event in Madrid on February 7th and 8th 2024. After the selection of a team of communication consultants, and the refinement of the content developed in Madrid, the campaign was active between April and June 2024. Two online events were organised as part of the campaign:

- Launching event on April 26th 2024: 94 people registered and 47 connected to the event.
- Pre-electoral event of the campaign on June 4th 2024: 66 registrants and 49 connected participants.

The participation to the online events of the campaign could have been reduced in comparison to the roundtable due to events saturation during the elections season as reported by activists participating in the Lab and also leading several candidates, particularly high-profile/top-of-list ones, to decline the invitation due to other campaign commitments. Additionally, a technical issue arose during the campaign’s launch event when the Zoom link sent to registered participants malfunctioned. This necessitated real-time updates to the invitations, and many participants were re-contacted during the event itself. The issue was communicated bilaterally with some event organisers.

After the conclusion of the campaign with the EP 2024 elections, the third lab was organised jointly with the FIERCE winter school (T5.2) and the launch of the transnational network (T5.1) in the FIERCE week between November 4th and 7th. The third transnational lab took place during the first day of the FIERCE week, with 34 total participants.

A total of 15 representatives of FIERCE partners participated in the first transnational, 2 members of the advisory board (ABM) and 1 member of the Push Back Lash sister projects. In addition, the indication was given to FIERCE partners to invite two members of each national lab, which led to the participation of 10 members from the FIERCE national labs. There were 3 participants from the FIERCE actions open

⁵ The campaign’s webpage can be accessed at the following link: <https://campaign.fierce-project.eu/>.

call (T4.4) from Greece, Poland and Spain. It is worth noting that additional FIERCE actions representatives from other countries attended to the following days of the winter school.

Finally, 3 members from EU level feminist organisations were invited from the organisations that had continuous participation to the first and second transnational lab:

- **WIDE+:** network of associations and activists that promotes inclusive and intersectional feminist movement building in Europe, in solidarity with feminists in the global South. There was 1 member in the third transnational lab.
- **European Roma Rights Centre (ERRC):** “Roma-led international public interest law organisation working to combat anti-Romani racism and human rights abuse of Roma through strategic litigation, research and policy development, advocacy and human rights education.” There was 1 member in the third transnational lab.
- **IPAS:** international organisation “with a comprehensive approach that centres the needs of those who seek abortion care. (building) ... sustainable abortion ecosystems that address all factors impacting a person’s ability to access abortion”. There was 1 member in the third transnational lab.
- **Gender Five Plus:** an independent European Feminist Think Tank, committed to European integration and a future built on gender equality, peace, respect for human rights and sustainability. There were invited and one member had confirmed her participation; however, this person dropped-out due to personal circumstances. She gave a presentation during the launch of the transnational network, on the last day of the transnational network.

Table 5 summarises the participation of FIERCE partners and external participants coming from FIERCE labs and actions.

Country	FIERCE actions	FIERCE labs	FIERCE partners
Denmark		2	2
France		2	2
Greece	1	1	2
Italy		1	3
Poland	1	1	1
Slovenia		1	2
Spain	1	1	2
Turkey		1	1
EU level feminist organisations		3	
Total general	3	13	15

Table 5: Participants to the third transnational lab (FIERCE partners and external participants from labs and actions)

It is worth mentioning that other European-wide feminist organisations participated to the previous meetings of the transnational lab:

- **European Women’s Lobby (EWL):** largest umbrella organisation of women's associations in the EU.
- **Essential Autonomous Struggles Transnational (E.A.S.T.):** Network composed mostly of women, migrants, workers and activists from grassroots movements born out of the struggles on social reproduction triggered by the pandemic crisis of Covid-19.
- **International Planned Parenthood Foundation (IPPF) – Europe**

- International Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans, Queer and Intersex (LGBTQI) Youth & Student Organisation (IGLYO): member-based network dedicated to LGBTQI youth and their rights with 115 member organisations in 39 countries belonging to the Council of Europe.

Of the participants that attended the third transnational lab, 16 filled the feedback questionnaire: 6 belonging to the FIERCE project —partner or ABM— and 10 external participants. All of the respondents identified as women, the average age was 42, ranging between 27 and 58. The level of education of the respondents was high: the 6 participants related to the project all had a PhD, while all 9 of the external participants a Master’s Degree and only 1 a Bachelor’s Degree. Regarding the self-identification with intersectional characteristics, 3 participants self-identified as having a disability or chronic condition, 4 as having an ethnical/migratory background and 7 as LGBTQI+. All of them mentioned being active inside the feminist movement: 3 from 1-5 years, 5 between 5-10 years and 8 for more than 10 years.

Regarding the organisations and collectives of the external participants that replied to the questionnaire (10), almost all of them declared usually (3) or occasionally (5) working with the government in activities such as: advocacy activities with the public institutions, parliamentarians, bilateral agencies and research activities. One of the respondents mentioned implementing “*Political work in making/changing law (for example consent-based sex law, stealthing and stalking)*”. Of the respondents, 5 mentioned their organisations mentioned being feminist —1 mentioned being LGBTQI+ focused and another respondent mentioned she being an individual feminist— and 8 being intersectional (see Figure 10

Figure 10: Characteristics of organisations participating in the Third Transnational Lab

4. The third co-creation cycle: preparation, agenda and description of the sessions per lab

4.1. Denmark

Preparation of the third lab meeting

During the second national lab in December 2023, it was decided to implement different initiatives as part of the lab’s outcome: a social media campaign with stories of sexism from a minority perspective for March 8th, participate in several events at political festivals and to produce a podcast on the lab’s theme.

AAU worked with the network members to prepare the agenda and ensure seamless participation in advance of the lab. After invitations were distributed, attendance confirmations started to come in the

weeks before the event. Six organisations were represented at the meeting, including ESPD, Tegnbyen, SUMH, FDDDB, SIND, and DH, despite a lower attendance than previous labs. To provide accessibility for participants, three AAU researchers—the Danish FIERCE partner—were also present, assisted by two sign language interpreters.

During the preparation of the lab, it had been agreed during the second lab that ESPD would be the one to coordinate the social media campaigns which focused on collecting personal stories about sexism from a minority perspective. Other lab members would be invited to contribute.

Regarding the preparation for the other lab’s outcomes, in particular the participation in political events, the date of the third lab was strategically timed just days before the application deadline for the Danish Youth Democracy Festival in Copenhagen, scheduled for September 2024. This presented an opportunity to align the network’s activities with the event application requirements. While the application details were deliberately kept flexible, the network’s anticipated participation in the festival was expected to build on the insights and collaborations fostered during the lab.

About a week before the meeting, participants received the lab agenda, details about the FIERCE campaign, and instructions on how to submit proposals that met the requirements to be considered FIERCE activities. In addition, ESPD was invited to present an overview of the 8 March campaign during the lab, highlighting key takeaways and metrics such as video views and the impact of the social media reels.

The decision to reduce the lab duration to three hours, including lunch, reflected careful consideration of participant needs, particularly those of volunteers and individuals with some of the diversely-abled participants (with mental disabilities). Breaks were included to support accessibility and inclusivity, reaffirming the network’s commitment to fostering an environment where all voices could contribute meaningfully.

Agenda and description of the lab sessions

The third Danish lab, organised on April 26th 2024 was organised in four main agenda slots, starting with an informal lunch, followed by a round of introductions and sharing of expectations. The third time slot was the evaluation of the social media campaign leading up to March 8th which had been implemented by ESPD, as well as a brainstorming about the FIERCE action at the Danish Youth Democracy Festival. During the conception of the agenda, Danish FIERCE partners had included a session to brainstorm about new possible political outcomes of the network; however, they had the impression that participants wanted to be more concrete in the preparation of new activities; therefore, finished the lab focusing exclusively on the preparation of the festival, which was the proposal to present in the FIERCE actions call. After the two introductory sessions, FIERCE Danish partners presented a summary of the previous work and the ideas collected in the “idea bank” they implemented during the second lab, which was a platform to brainstorm about possible political outcomes to be implemented as part of the network.

The third session of the agenda, ESPD’s presentation of the March 8th social media campaign about stories of sexism from a minority perspective and through intersectional lens had two objectives: (i) To collect anonymised stories about experiencing sexism from a minority perspective and through an intersectional lens; and (ii) To educate a wider public about how sexism can be expressed in various intersections between social belongings and identities, and how this negatively affects minorities in distinct ways. The most widespread goal of the campaign and the association is that *“that sexism is not only expressed through violent crimes but also through every day, and at times seemingly unharmed, behaviour which supports broader sexist structures and practices in society”*. This campaign managed to collect a limited number of personal stories (16); however, gained considerable attention, with 83,000

views in the most popular video. A limitation to the campaign was the inclusion of marginalised groups; however, it was proposed in the lab to repeat this campaign annually in weeks leading up to March 8th to start popularising the topic and raising awareness.

The last session in the agenda, dedicated to work on the action at the Danish Youth Democracy Festival, which takes place during two regular weekdays in Copenhagen and targets teenagers and young adults in their 20s. It was recommended to arrange what the festival organisers call a “pop-up activity,” which is a shorter event taking place either on a stage or an open square, instead of a permanent which was considerably expensive and required the permanent presence of someone the two days of the festival.

A brainstorming session followed, generating ideas for a FIERCE action at the festival. Suggestions included interactive elements like speech bubbles for sharing experiences of sexism from a minority perspective, provocative questions, video displays, quizzes, and informational pamphlets. ESPD proposed organizing a workshop on topics such as respectful flirting and bystander intervention, using engaging methods like role-playing in relatable settings to address sexism through an intersectional lens. Time constraints led to an agreement to continue planning in an online meeting, allowing broader participation and input from network members. The session concluded with a commitment to collaborative development of the activity.

Follow-up meeting in May

Despite sending multiple reminders, only representatives from ESPD and The Danish Association of Youth with Disabilities participated in the online meeting in late May. Few other participants expressed interest but were unable to attend, leading to the assumption that the network trusted those present to finalise decisions.

During the meeting, it was agreed to organise a workshop on bystander intervention against sexism, building on ESPD’s expertise with similar workshops. This workshop would focus specifically on sexism affecting minorities, where it intersects with other forms of discrimination, such as class, race, sexuality, and disability. ESPD committed to drafting scenarios highlighting these intersections and designing activities to provoke thoughtful engagement and deeper understanding among participants. Other organisations in the network would have opportunities to review and suggest changes to the draft in preparation for a detailed discussion in a planning meeting scheduled for August.

Following the meeting, a brief presentation of the workshop was submitted to The Danish Youth Democracy Festival organisers, allowing for its inclusion in the official programme. It was also announced that classes from elementary and high schools could sign up for the workshop in advance, ensuring a more structured audience. The AAU team elaborated the workshop’s title and description, finalising them through email correspondence with the network.

The workshop, titled “*What do you do when somebody experiences discrimination? Get advice at bystander workshop,*” was described as follows: “Does your class want to become everyday heroes by reacting to discrimination? Be part of a workshop where we focus on what all of us can do of big and small things to intervene in discrimination affecting people with different backgrounds. We will talk about which kinds of discrimination you can be exposed to when you have a specific gender or sexuality while at the same time having, for instance, a disability, being fat, or belonging to an ethnic minority. And we will help each other in intervening when we see someone being exposed to this kind of discrimination.”

4.2. Greece

Preparation of the third lab meeting

The Greek lab has been the one following the most horizontal approach among all FIERCE national labs. Since its setting up, FIERCE Greek partners —AUTH— have followed an approach promoting the self-organisation and more active role of the participants, mostly being focused in the organisation and the logistics of the sessions. After being convoked to the first lab, participants self-organised during the session, with one of them who had political experience actively conducting the facilitation of the session and proposing a methodology based on assembly dynamics. Participants identified a series of relevant topics for the Greek feminist movement and organised an agenda for the second lab meeting, identifying organisations and collectives responsible for delivering thematic presentations. This was implemented during the second lab, organised on December 2023, where it was decided to go in-depth on some of the topics.

As a result, a thematic agenda for the third lab was proposed collectively by the participants. In particular, it was agreed to prepare further presentations and discussion about GBV, and critical analysis of the 2021 mandatory joint custody law, which was scheduled to be discussed in the second lab but was transferred to the third due to lack of time. In preparation for the third Greek lab, initial communication was carried out via email by FIERCE Greek partners on April 15th, 2024. This email reiterated decisions made collectively during the second lab regarding the location and agenda of the third lab, which was to take place at AUTH’s premises in Thessaloniki.

The response to this initial communication was largely affirmative. All the collectives that had participated in the second lab meeting attended the third in-presence session with the exception of DIOTIMA due to human resources issues which did not allow them to dedicate more time to the lab. It is worth highlighting that their decision had already been informed during the second lab meeting. Collectives that continued their participation were: Karditsa Women’s Centre (KWC), the Rainbow School, the Women’s Assembly 8th March and Mesopotamia – Moschato Citizens’.

During the first invitation email, FIERCE Greek partners proposed inviting additional groups to contribute to discussions on GBV, including the grassroots feminist and LGBTQIA+ collective ‘Meduses,’ an LGBTQIA+ group from Thessaloniki, and the students’ NGO ‘Phylis.’ Suggestions for agenda contributions were encouraged to maintain an open and collaborative approach.

Notably, the Karditsa Women’s Centre strongly supported inviting ‘Meduses’ and a member of AUTH’s official Gender Equality Committee. Further coordination led to confirmations from Meduses (with two members participating as individuals) and two representatives from the AUTH Gender Equality Committee. Unfortunately, no response was received from ‘Phylis,’ and LGBTQIA+ groups in Thessaloniki were unable to participate due to their involvement in the Euro Pride event held during the same week. The dates of the third lab were finalised as June 28-29, 2024, based on collective availability.

To ensure consensus and a well-structured agenda, additional communication occurred between participant groups the FIERCE Greek partners, emphasising collective decision-making, with all groups invited to propose changes or additions. For instance, the Solidarity School Mesopotamia initiated a new presentation on intersectionality and their work, which was incorporated into the agenda.

Unlike in the previous labs, during the preparation of the third encounter, FIERCE partners had a more active coordination role because the meeting was organised in AUTH facilities and because Greek partners had direct contacts with the new participants invited. In addition, close collaboration also took place with the Women’s Assembly 8th March, the only other Thessaloniki-based group, to facilitate co-hosting responsibilities: *“Crucially, the entire preparation was determined by the agenda which emerged*

through the free, very loosely co-ordinated collective interaction of all participant groups during the first and the second lab. This collective process, which unfolded on equal terms and almost ‘spontaneously’, with very little intervention on the part of the AUTH research team, was the mainspring of power which laid down the agenda of the third lab and informed its realization”.

Agenda and description of the lab sessions

The Greek lab’s agenda was structured in two days, starting in the evening of June 28th with two thematic sessions, one by the collective Meduses about “grassroots activist responses to GBV in local contexts in present-day Greece” and one by Solidarity School Mesopotamia on intersectional approaches to gender equality. The first day of the lab concluded with a dinner. On June 29th, the focus shifted more towards institutional and legislative dimensions, with the AUTH Gender Equality Committee presenting their challenges and progress with the implementation of their gender equality plan and the Women’s Assembly 8th March presenting about the mandatory joint custody law and the ratification of the 190 Convention of the International Labour Organisation by the Greek parliament. The agenda was proposed to conclude with a deliberation on the lab’s outcome.

First day of the lab

After a first introductory presentation of attendees to the meeting, the session in June 28th started with a presentation by the feminist and LGBTQIA+ collective Meduses based on Larisa. The methodology in this session was an informal presentation by the two members of the collective present in the lab followed by an open discussion where the other members of the lab shared experiences and reflections on GBV.

The Meduses Collective was established in Larissa, Greece, around 2019-2020, born out of the need to resist and fight against various forms of violence, especially GBV. Its members come from diverse ideological backgrounds, which has allowed them to engage in productive discussions and learn how to communicate effectively with one another. They are not only femininities. They also have LGBTQIA+. Their assemblies are attended by approximately ten people. Over the past four years, the collective has focused on several key areas, including incidents of employer and domestic violence, providing victims with legal, social, and financial support, and aiming to empower them towards long-term autonomy. They also addressed a rape incident and attempted character assassination of a survivor, making interventions to change the local atmosphere. Discussion with participants took place around four main thematic topics: locality and fear, migrants, the recent history of feminist collectives in Greece, the current state and challenges, as well as Antifeminist and Anti-Gender reaction and feminist/LGBTQIA+ responses-

The second session of the first day of the lab was a presentation on ‘Intersectionality and Solidarity: Creating Safe Spaces in Neighborhoods’ by two members of the Mesopotamia Solidarity School. This collective was founded in 2013-2014 as a solidarity network based on intersectionality, operating as a social structure of autonomous action rather than a feminist organisation. They presented some of their initiatives, focusing in the Solidarity School, which offers educational and training services to people of all ages, including supportive tuition for high school students. Other key initiatives of Mesopotamia include the Solidarity Basket and the Cinema Club. In 2021, a Gender, Sexual Orientation, and Gender Identity Group was established, operating in the same collaborative, participatory manner as other structures within the collective.

Second day of the lab

There were two thematic presentations on the second day of the third Greek lab. The first one was delivered by the AUTH Gender Equality Committee, who presented the process of the constitution of the committee, the AUTH Gender Equality Action Plan and the failures in its implantation. This process

was triggered by two institutional pressures: new national legislation stipulation the establishment of such committees at all Greek universities, EU directives and threats to reduce EU funding to universities that lack such structures addressing gender equality within the university. Despite this, after the elaboration of the document, the implementation has not been successful due to a chronic lack of serious engagement with gender equality issues, institutional inertia and a lack of will to implement the Gender Equality Plan.

The second thematic agenda slot was focused on the mandatory shared custody law and was subdivided in two presentations. The first one, by the Women’s Assembly 8 March, was focused on “joint custody and ‘Chatzidakis’ law”. This law has contributed to the rise of the far-right, particularly affecting family and labour rights which had been established in the 1980s through labour and feminist movements- Right-wing minister Vوريدis seeking to dismantle progressive legislation. The joint custody law, which mandates that children spend at least 30% of their time with each parent, often forces women, especially those in abusive relationships, to remain tied to their marriages. Despite opposition from feminist groups, the law was passed in 2021 with support from major political parties, including New Democracy and SYRIZA. The campaign surrounding the law was heavily influenced by conservative forces, including the Orthodox Church and the ‘Active Dads’ group, which pushed a narrative centred on traditional family values. On the other hand, the ‘Chatzidakis’ law is a bill that passed and it targets trade unions. The law pretends to implement a directive of the International Labour Organisation calling on enterprises to reject any type of racist behaviour, of homophobic and transphobic discourse. However, it limits the action of trade-unions and its potential action in reporting violence situations to the employee and the police. The final presentation was made was one of the FIERCE Greek partners, who focused on the antifeminist practices and discourses around the custody law, as well as the feminist counter-mobilisations.

4.3. France

Preparation of the third lab meeting

Following the second National Lab in December 2023, the third French Lab was organised six months later with the aim to finish the preparation of the lab’s outcome: the prototype of the digital platform to fight against the anti-gender backlash. Originally scheduled for June 21st, the meeting, was postponed due to political instability in France, including the dissolution of Parliament by President Macron and the legislative elections. In this period, feminist activists were considerably busy campaigning for the support of the left coalitions in view of the legislative elections.

Between the two in-presence meetings, engagement was maintained thanks to the multiple FIERCE activities, including the interviews implemented as part of WP2 and the implementation of the FIERCE campaign implemented as part of the transnational lab. The French FIERCE partner, European Alternatives, coordinated with Lab members to support the campaign, helping with its dissemination information, which gained visibility through partnerships with movements like #NousToutes during the European elections.

A preparation Zoom meeting was held on June 21st, which served as a space for discussion and resource sharing in the context of political tension. During this meeting, participants developed a channel to mobilize against the far right and co-create social media campaigns for leftist coalitions. This prompted a focus on combating the far right in the agenda for the rescheduled Lab on July 16, 2024. The July meeting was structured into three parts: a roundtable on recent feminist news, a presentation of FIERCE’s research results, and a discussion on refining the digital platform and its diffusion strategy.

Agenda and description of the lab sessions

As planned during the preparatory period before the lab, the agenda was organized in three main thematic sessions: (i) review of feminist news and updates on the work of each feminist collective participating in the lab during the last six months, (ii) FIERCE preliminary research results and (iii) discussion on the development and the diffusion strategy of the lab’s outcome, the platform to combat anti-gender backlash. Following, more detail on the agenda sessions is provided.

Agenda session 1 (10:00-11:30): update on the organisations’ mobilisations and activities

The first session of the day, dedicated to updates from the associations, showcased a wealth of activities and reflections from the past six months. HandsAway highlighted their intensified school training efforts despite an audit by the Île-de-France region and shared their internal exploration of practising intersectionality in a predominantly white collective. Feminists Against Cyberharassment announced organisational growth following a successful fundraising campaign, enabling increased advocacy, including efforts to address sexist biases in AI training models, raise awareness about the racialised nature of cyberviolence, and mobilise against the far-right through the "Feminist Alert" campaign. IPAS reported on their global reproductive justice advocacy, warning of geopolitical threats to abortion rights, particularly in Europe, and shared insights from the Equipop Symposium on feminist approaches to sexual health and reproductive rights.

Equipop reflected on heightened media focus on masculinist topics during the constitutionalisation of abortion in France, their publication of a report on the far-right’s impact on women’s rights, and their collaboration on a policy brief on feminist funding. Le Planning Familial recounted their advocacy for constitutionalising abortion rights, participation in international meetings where conservative rhetoric was prevalent, and their analysis of political party platforms on women’s rights, which influenced party responses. Lastly, the independent journalist criticised the French media’s failure to adequately address or understand anti-gender movements and called for targeted media training. The session concluded with a reflection on the evolving public and media receptiveness to feminist arguments linking anti-gender movements to the far-right, recognising progress during recent elections and reaffirming the need for sustained feminist action against far-right threats.

Agenda session 2 (11:30-13:00): presentation of the preliminary FIERCE research results

Different advancements of the project were presented: the chapter analysing French feminism between 2010 to 2021, the chapter on anti-gender movements, as well as the three policy briefs elaborated as part of the project and the possibility to merging the FIERCE policy briefs with the ones being developed by Planning Familial and Equipop. The session concluded with identifying the need to remain active in the field, ensuring no obstacles to simultaneous publications or organizing various events against anti-gender movements.

Agenda session 3 (14:00-15:00) and last session (15:00-17:00): presentation of the platform and Q&A session

The afternoon sessions of the agenda were focused on working related to the lab’s outcome: the platform to fight against the anti-gender backlash. Initially, this session started with a presentation, collective brainstorming and Q&A session about the platform. This was presented as a resource to understand feminist terms (e.g. backlash, anti-gender, etc), it will be built reusing existing tools and recommendations included in the FIERCE policy briefs and mapping operational methods, tactics of feminist movements and cataloguing other types of existing resources.

During the last session, the group discussed about possible options to present a proposal to the FIERCE action’s call, with the aim to promote and strengthen the platform. As a result of the work, four options emerged:

1. A launching event for the platform to be organised in Paris, also aimed at fundraising.

2. A program to promote the platform in 2024/2025 across France: hire a person to travel around France promoting the platform. This option was valued as beneficial because it could allow to help strengthen FIERCE's local and associative network and to focus on municipal elections and the rise of the far right outside Paris.
3. A training module “Feminists Against the Far Right and Anti-Gender Groups” co-created with #NousToutes: in this option the funding would be used to compensate for the time spent on developing the training, but would not use the entire available budget.
4. Invest in the services of a facilitator to secure funding for a feminist network in France focused on combating the far right. This includes establishing a more frequent cycle of FIERCE meetings, co-structuring the network, and ensuring its sustainability through funding for operational needs such as training for less institutionalised associations and secretarial services.

The group has applied to the FIERCE actions. After the lab not having taken a final decision, French FIERCE partners decided to develop the platform inhouse. The webpage will be linked to the FIERCE project’s webpage. The available funding of the FIERCE actions call will be used for implementing the platform itself, as well as to develop a training programme.

4.4. Italy

Preparation of the third lab’s meeting

The third Italian lab meeting took place on July 1st 2024 in the feminist association Il Giardino dei Ciliegi in Florence (Via dell'Agnolo, 5, 50018 Firenze). This meeting was focused on finishing the co-writing process of the self-defence manual for teachers implementing education to differences (EAD for the Italian *educare alle differenze*), which is understood in the Italian context as education on gender+ inequalities encompassing awareness raising on sexism and homo-transphobia.

Table 6 presents the table of contents of the manual, which had been co-created with the participants in previous sessions of the lab. In particular, the objective of the third lab was to finish the content development of the last three chapters (5, 6 and 7).

Chapters of the self-defence manual	
1.	Introduction: diagnostic elements of the first lab (brief description)
2.	Our notion of self-defence
2.1.	What is self-defence in this manual
2.2.	Who exercises it
2.3.	Objectives of the manual
3.	Self-defence against attacks/violence experienced in school relationships and techniques of resistance/assertion against the obstacles of EAD (Education Against Discrimination) present in the school environment.
3.1.	With the school management
3.2.	With the parents
3.3.	With other teachers
3.4.	With students (supporting anti-gender ideology)
4.	Self-defence against "external" attacks/violence (public opinion, media, politicians) and techniques of resistance/assertion against external obstacles of EAD.
5.	Discursive traps: what to do when language is depoliticised, feminist terms are emptied, or there are situations of conceptual appropriation.
6.	Self-care, prevention
6.1.	How to take care of oneself (e.g., to take care of psychological well-being)
6.2.	Building communities and convivial situations among colleagues
7.	Other resources for self-defence
7.1.	List of organisations and networks working in EAD at national, regional, and local levels
7.2.	List of relevant regulations
7.3.	List of lawyers to contact

Table 6: Italian lab’s outcome - Index of the self-defence manual

All preparatory work for this session was completely organised by Italian FIERCE partners because, since the structure had already been agreed with lab participants, no follow-up meetings between the second and third lab were organised. The second lab had taken place on December 14th 2023 and had been focused on the content development of chapters 3 and 4 of the aforementioned table of contents.

All communication between the second and third lab sessions were via email. Besides the invitation email to the third in-presence session of the Italian lab, there were a series of communications to lab participants regarding the transnational lab. This lab, launched on September 19th 2023 in Brussels, implemented the “Five FIERCE claims for a Feminist Europe” campaign targeting candidates to the 2024 European Parliament (EP elections) as political outcome. The campaign’s content and communication strategy were discussed in Madrid during the second in-presence meeting of the transnational national on February 7th and 8th 2024. As part of the diffusion strategy, it was agreed that feminists collectives could sign it as “partners”, showing their logos as the promoters of the campaign. Thus, it was agreed at the project consortium to ask national labs for their support to the campaign. In addition, the campaign’s charter —a manifesto detailing the campaign claims— was shared with them and asked for their support in the diffusion. As a result of these series of communications two of the Italian lab members subscribed the campaign as partners: Indici Paritari and Love My Way.

Agenda and description of the lab sessions

Following the agenda of the third Italian lab is presented. After the initial presentation of the agenda and an initial round of introductions among the participants, a discussion began about the worsening contextual and political conditions for carrying out Education to Differences projects and activities in schools. Some of the participants shared experiences they faced during last months while implementing their initiatives, and general recommendations for the manual were identified.

After the introductory session, the third lab’s agenda was structured according to the lab’s objective: work on the content-development of chapters 5, 6, and 7:

- Addressing the use of language: when it is emptied, depoliticised, and distorted
- Working on self-care, mutual care, and prevention
- Identifying additional resources for self-defence

Thematic session 1 - Chapter 5 “Discursive Traps”: Working on the use of language

The work session began by presenting the concept of "discursive traps," defined as:

- Words/phrases that are depoliticised and stripped of their political charge through a dynamic of superficial and/or distorted appropriation of EAD themes and topics. For example, key terms such as patriarchy, gender, violence, feminism, consent, and intersectionality are often diluted in this process. This dynamic commonly involves replacing terms with softer equivalents, such as using "egalitarian" instead of "feminist," "diversity" instead of "intersectionality," or "bullying" instead of "GBV."
- Explicit distortion and instrumentalization of concepts and themes to delegitimise or improperly "re-legitimise" racist agendas. An example of distortion might be linking EAD to paedophilia or "encouraging" homosexuality. Another example could occur in a school with a high proportion of students from migrant backgrounds, where right-wing teachers or parents propose activities (within or adjacent to EAD) that perpetuate stereotypes about Islam and African populations, promoting a "national" model of gender equality as opposed to "the others."

To work on counter-argumentation and response strategies against "discursive traps," participants engaged in a role-play and discussion dynamic in two subgroups, based on a hypothetical scenario: *"Two parents attend a school meeting, expressing concern that their child is learning about concepts of gender and sexuality at school. They claim this undermines the values of the traditional family."* Participants were asked to take on different roles — teachers promoting EAD and individuals opposed to it — and simulate a dialogue, while other participants observed and took notes. After the role-play, each subgroup conducted a brainstorming session to reflect on the arguments used to contest, distort, or depoliticise EAD and transfeminist concepts.

The two groups approached the activity differently. In one group, participants expressed discomfort with impersonating roles for the role-play exercise. Instead, they proposed collectively interpreting the roles of the teacher and the anti-gender actor, focusing on suggesting specific phrases and responses to counter arguments. As a result of this group's work, a list of common phrases/attacks was identified alongside corresponding responses and counterarguments. There was a high level of agreement among participants, and no conflicts arose during the exercise.

In contrast, the second group carried out the role-play exercise, with two participants assuming the central roles of a teacher promoting Education to Differences (EAD) and an anti-gender parent. The scenario began with the participant playing the teacher presenting an EAD project, coordinated with

colleagues, to the parents of their students. After the presentation, the participant playing the anti-gender parent—who is, in reality, a teacher implementing EAD—began provoking the teacher repeatedly. During the interaction, the participant in the teacher role, who initially responded with calm and rational arguments, eventually reacted to the provocations with an extreme example and an angry tone, leading to some tension among the participants. The role-play concluded with the participant playing the teacher appealing to a series of norms and specific technical competencies.

The work session on discursive traps concluded with a plenary discussion. However, some tension between participants persisted during this session. Further details on these dynamics are provided in Section 5.4.

Thematic session 2 - Chapter 6: Self-care and prevention

The need for care, both individual and collective, is crucial in a work context like that faced by teachers involved in education to differences, who endure constant attacks and must exercise ongoing resistance in a hostile environment. The sustainability of EAD work depends on paying attention to self-care and caring for others.

To identify care strategies, a collective brainstorming session was conducted in plenary, guided by the following questions:

- What are the main emotional and psychological challenges you face in EAD work/activism?
- What individual care strategies do you adopt? How can moments of self-care be integrated into daily routines?
- What collective care strategies do you adopt? How can spaces for mutual support be created?
- What are the main barriers preventing the adoption of self-care practices in schools?
- How can a culture of self-care and prevention be promoted in schools?
- What useful resources have you found to exercise care?

Among the strategies of self-care, participants emphasised the importance of legitimising one’s position by affirming personal values and recognising and respecting anger as a valid emotion. They also emphasised the importance of the collective dimension for care. Indeed, belonging to collectives and forming alliances was identified as valuable to foster mutual support, sharing experiences, build resilience and improve resistance. Participants stressed the importance of non-judgemental spaces in schools and cited initiatives such as artistic workshops, yoga or mindfulness.

Thematic session 3 - Chapter 7: Other resources for self-defence

The activity was conducted as a collective brainstorming session on a poster to gather information on:

- Organisations and networks working on EAD at the national, regional, and local levels
- Relevant regulations
- Lawyers which could be contacted

As a result of the activity a series of resources were identified that will be included as annexes in the manual.

Next steps

The self-defence manual for teachers implementing EAD is currently under the process of copyediting by Chayn, as part of the implementation of the Italian FIERCE action. Agreed next steps for the finalisation of the manual are the elaboration of the final draft, sharing it with all lab participants to collect feedback and organising a final feedback meeting. The final version of the text will be ready by

mid- February 2025 and the graphic design and final version of the manual will be completed by mid-March 2025.

4.5. Poland

Preparation of the third lab meeting

The third national Polish Lab was organised through communication with two project members from the University of Gdansk and individuals included in the mailing list created after the first lab. A messenger group was set up to facilitate coordination, while urgent matters were addressed through direct phone calls to expedite the process.

As with the previous two labs, the location for the third lab was offered free of charge by a cultural institution in Warsaw. According to the Polish lab review, certain group members displayed lower levels of engagement compared to others. When prompted to participate more actively, some offered a range of reasons for their limited involvement. While the Polish FIERCE partners preparing the report could not pinpoint the exact reasons for this, they speculated that it might be linked to internal splits and conflicts within feminist movements following the 2023 elections.

In addition to this, several online meetings were held, primarily via Zoom and Google Meet, involving both national and international law participants. However, some participants failed to respond to emails, while others stated that due to personal reasons, they were unable to attend either physical or online meetings.

Agenda and description of the lab sessions

The third Polish meeting was organised on June 22nd 2024, two weeks after the European Parliament (EP) elections of 2024 and the same of the third equality parade in Warsaw in 2024. This showed some conflicts inside the LGBT community, which organised different Equality Parades: the first one in early June organised by anarchist circles and having an anti-capitalist approach, opposing to large corporations and pinkwashing. The other two parades —June 15th and 22nd— were the result of a division in the association organising the equality parade in Warsaw. The largest one was on the 15th was organised *“by the 'old' association with a 'new' board”*.

The lab’s agenda was organised starting with two brief sessions (comprehensively 1 hour) dedicated to analyse political European and Polish context, specifically the first one focused in the reflection about the FIERCE transnational lab in Madrid and the EP elections, while the second about the current situation in the Polish feminist movement, focusing on cooperation with political parties and future prospects. After them, the agenda focused on the work on the lab’s outcome. In particular before lunch, the concept outlined in the previous workshop was further developed. After the lunch break, the lab was focused on planning the campaign details, setting objectives and distributing tasks among the participants.

The initial discussions analysing the three political elections that had taken place between 2023 and 2024 identified a widespread disillusionment with political parties, their prioritisation of personnel over principles, and their failure to adequately support feminist and grassroots movements. Divisions and differences within the women's community were a recurring theme, as was the lack of allies in the political system in relation to political developments. Below, are included some of the reflections included about the political elections:

- Parliamentary Elections (October 2023): unprecedented voter turnout exceeding 70%, saw the ruling Law and Justice party cede power to a liberal-left coalition (Civic Coalition, Third Way, and the Left). The surge in turnout, especially among young voters and women, was driven by pro-participation campaigns like Initiative East and Hush Already Were. However, the new

coalition government, formed on December 13, 2023, failed to deliver on key feminist and progressive demands, such as civil unions, abortion rights, and access to the 'after pill,' leading to growing disappointment among voters and feminist organisations like the Women's Strike.

- Local Elections (April 2024): Turnout dropped to 50%, with a significant decline in participation from young voters and women. Participants attributed this to disillusionment with the government and inadequate party support for feminist candidates. Examples highlighted included unequal funding and lack of promotion for local candidates, many of whom came from grassroots movements. In some cases, local activists were replaced by party-aligned candidates with limited connections to the communities. The Left's controversial decisions in selecting candidates, such as the mayoral choice in Gdansk, caused internal divisions and vote-splitting. The fallout included a wave of resignations from political parties, with activists citing frustration over prioritisation of "stools" (positions) over ideals.
- Europarliamentary Elections (June 2024): marked by an even lower turnout of 40.5%, revealed increasing support for far-right groups like the Confederation and deepening crises within the ruling coalition. Feminist issues were marginalised in public debates, which were dominated by conflicts between Law and Justice and the Civic Coalition. Candidates faced challenges such as a lack of support from party leadership and being imposed on districts with no prior connection.

After this analysis, the lab centred in working related to the lab's outcome. During the second lab, two social media campaigns had been proposed. The first idea was to include the requirement for equal pay in the Polish Labor Code, assuring equal pay by gender in identical positions. The second was a graphic campaign for labour market equality, which would be displayed on public transportation throughout the country, highlighting the unequal treatment of men and women in the labour market. It was discussed to develop a combined campaign focused on equality in the labour market. Specific content for the campaign was planned, developing proposal for the graphic materials on the following topics:

- 'Emotionality' of women
- Breaks at work to feed kids and be able to leave work early
- The unacceptability of job interviews where you ask about children and parenting plans.
- Discrimination against women 50+ in the labour market
- Agreeing to work on Saturdays for parents of young children
- Pay equality and anti-discrimination measures reference to the wage gap.
- Sexist jokes in the workplace.

Discussion during the lab also considered the target population of the campaign, the dissemination channels, key performance indicators and setting a new social media account to implement the campaign.

4.6. Slovenia

Preparation of the third lab meeting

Preparations for the third National Lab in Slovenia commenced in autumn 2023 and gained momentum in early 2024 through the combined efforts of the core group, consisting of three feminist activists, and the project team members. In January 2024, designer Vesna Bukovec joined the team to contribute to the visual and structural development of the Lab's primary outcome: a feminist exhibition on reproductive rights, complete with an official opening and guided tour.

The direction of the third Lab was shaped during the first National Lab held in June 2023, where it was collectively decided that the central outcome would focus on five thematic areas: the right to abortion, the right to contraception, sexual education, artificial insemination and parenthood, and violence in

reproductive health. The fifth theme was further explored during the second National Lab, held on 19 December 2023, where participants brainstormed potential sub-themes for the exhibition.

The timeline for the feminist exhibition was meticulously planned with the core group, with an agreement to present the exhibition as street posters in central Ljubljana. In autumn 2023, the core group initiated discussions with design collaborators until finding the, ultimately selecting Vesna Bukovec, who officially joined the team in January 2024. The exhibition was conceived as a public intervention to engage a wider audience. To realise this vision, discussions were initiated with Tam Tam d.o.o., a company managing public poster spaces in Ljubljana and beyond. The exhibition was scheduled to be displayed from 7 to 20 May 2024 across five prominent locations in the city centre. Technical details and logistical arrangements were finalised in collaboration with Tam Tam d.o.o.

Content and photographic materials for the exhibition began to be collected in late summer 2023 and continued until the end of the year, involving active contributions from both core group members and project team members. Additionally, the team reached out to the weekly magazine Mladina to gain access to their extensive photo archive, which provided valuable visual materials for the thematic areas.

On 17 January 2024, a pivotal meeting was held between the designer, the core group, and project team members to review the collected materials and outline the content for the exhibition posters. It was decided that each poster would be bilingual (Slovenian and English) and would include a QR code that visitors could scan for supplementary information and resources related to the five thematic areas. The team set a March 2024 deadline to finalise content and visual materials for the 18 posters. During this period, the designer created original illustrations, particularly for the theme of violence in reproductive health, where visual resources were lacking. Content preparation was carried out collaboratively through a series of long Zoom meetings in late January and February 2024, culminating in polished texts that were proofread in Slovenian and translated into English.

By early April 2024, the final poster designs were completed and reviewed internally by both the project team and the core group. Feedback was consolidated and shared with the designer, who delivered a revised and final version. Upon final approval, the posters were sent to Tam Tam d.o.o. for printing and display. Concurrently, the team prepared short accompanying texts for each thematic area, including contextual overviews and additional online resources in both Slovenian and English.

At the end of April 2024, invitations to the exhibition's opening and guided tours, scheduled for 7 May at 5 PM, were distributed. Invitations were sent via email, Facebook, the Peace Institute's webpage, and through the networks of core group members. Recipients included feminist activists, groups, organisations, policymakers, media representatives, and contributors who played a role in the exhibition's development. In early May 2024, with additional funding secured outside the FIERCE project, an online version of the exhibition was also launched, designed and implemented by the designer Vesna Bukovec and made accessible at <https://reproduktivne-pravice.mirovni-institut.si/>.

Agenda and description of the lab sessions

The opening of the exhibition "Reproductive Rights: On Health, Sexuality, and Equality of Women" started with welcoming remarks from Živa Humer, a project team member, and Sonja Lokar, a member of the core group. Each thematic area was then introduced and discussed with the Lab participants.

The limited participation during the inauguration of the exhibition and guided tours allowed for the discussion of the different topics included in the exhibition: *“The main emphasis was that this year marks the 50th anniversary since Yugoslavia became the first country in the world to define a new human right—the right to freely decide on the birth of children—in Article 191 of the SFRY Constitution. Slovenia is the only country of the former Yugoslavia that has successfully preserved this right both*

constitutionally and in practice. In the other countries of the former Yugoslavia, the situation regarding reproductive rights has deteriorated severely over the past few decades”.

The content of the exhibition was displayed in 18 posters, covering 5 thematic areas, each one highlighting three milestones and challenges. The exhibition included photos and graphic material elaborated by the designer presenting the five pivotal themes of the exhibition:

- The rights to abortion: since the 1960s, the United Nations debated population policies to address fertility rates in the global North and South. Feminist politicians, particularly Slovenian leader Vida Tomšič, successfully reframed this issue, introducing the concept of the "wanted child," which prioritised human freedom of choice in parenthood and collective wellbeing. In 1974, the Socialist Federative Republic of Yugoslavia became the first country to enshrine the right to abortion in its Constitution. After Slovenia's independence in 1991, feminist movements secured this right in the new Constitution through public demonstrations, resulting in Article 55. Currently, these constitutional right faces growing opposition from religious anti-abortion groups and conservative lawyers.
- The right to protection: since the 1950s, politician Vida Tomšič and her husband Franc Novak, a gynaecologist, promoted the production of contraceptives as well as the programme for the development of contraception clinics in Slovenia. Milestones include the first contraception clinic in Yugoslavia (1955) and the introduction of contraceptive pills (1964). Post-1991, reproductive rights faced challenges, with attempts to impose co-payments for hormonal contraception in 2013 and 2016. Public resistance, led by feminist groups, successfully defended these rights, underscoring the need for their ongoing protection.
- Artificial insemination and parenthood: In 1983, Ljubljana's Gynaecological Clinic became one of the first to successfully carry out in vitro fertilisation (IVF), marking a milestone in reproductive medicine. By 1984, the first IVF twins were born, and today, Slovenia leads globally in artificial insemination, with nearly 1,000 children conceived through the procedure each year. The legal framework began with the 1977 *Health Measures in Exercising Freedom of Choice in Childbearing Act*. However, the 1999 *Infertility Treatment and Procedures of Biomedically-Assisted Procreation Act* controversially restricted artificial insemination to women in heterosexual relationships. Attempts to restore access for all women succeeded briefly in 2001 but were overturned in a referendum following opposition from right-wing parties. Since then, the restrictive Act has remained in force, despite multiple constitutional review attempts.
- Sexual education: Sexual education was introduced in Slovenia during the 1960s as part of Health Promotion and Education, focusing on biological aspects of sexuality, contraception, interpersonal relationships, and safe sex. Today, while young people access sexual information through various channels, including schools, they feel formal education lacks focus on topics such as intimacy, sexual identity, orientation, consent, and sexual violence. Since 1985, sexual education has been confined to biology classes.
- Violence in reproductive health: this was the topic of the second Slovenian lab, collecting personal stories of participants which had experienced it. Discriminatory practices in healthcare institutions undermine women's right to safe and informed reproductive health decisions. Key issues include inadequate preventive care during gynaecological check-ups, insufficient explanation of diagnoses, and obstacles to accessing legal abortion services, such as deterrence or conscientious objection by medical personnel. Conditions like endometriosis and polycystic ovary syndrome are frequently underestimated, delaying diagnosis and treatment. Structural gaps include a lack of gynaecological counselling for young people, insufficient specialists, and barriers to timely access to check-ups and contraceptives. Obstetric violence is another concern, encompassing inappropriate or harmful attitudes and procedures during childbirth.

4.7. Spain

Preparation of the third lab meeting

The Spanish co-creation sessions were titled as “An intersectional approach to care: Initiatives and proposals for action” and were focused on addressing care from a broad, intersectional and inter-territorial perspective including the perspectives of care givers and care recipients. The first lab was focused on a diagnosis of the situation in the country, while the second lab was dedicated to define the proposal for action which was decided as a network for care that would follow the following objectives:

1. To have a space for exchange and state-wide action on the universal right to care.
2. To be connected, and be able to share information, activities and strategies with network participants.
3. To facilitate advocacy for the adoption and implementation of public care policies.
4. To raise awareness of the importance of care in the socio-economic system.

After sending an online poll, the date was agreed on June 17th 2024. An online meeting was held to prepare the third lab’s meeting, with the aim to brainstorm on the issues that should be discussed during the session. The session was dedicated to discuss about the structure of the network, demands and the official launch in a public event what was intended to be presented for the FIERCE actions call.

Only four participants accepted the invitation: 3 activists and 1 academic, which made FIERCE partners rethink the approach of the network: *“Important feedback and critical points came out of this meeting. The participants emphasised the idea of sustainability over time, and the need to (re)formulate realistic, short- and medium-term objectives. This meeting helped us rethink the content of the working sessions, in a way that focused more on concrete steps, short term tasks, and medium-term goals.”*

Agenda and description of the lab sessions

On June 17th the third Spanish lab was implemented with 10 participants, 6 external and 4 members of UCM, the Spanish FIERCE partner. The meeting started clarifying that the objective for the session was to identify concrete steps, tolls and commitments for the creation and platform of care. A recap was presented during the first session of the agenda, recapitulating the main agreements developed in the previous labs and the decision to establish a care network for as the lab’s political outcome.

During the second session a work in groups was proposed to brainstorm on the needs for the network (commitment of participants, driving group, new participating organisations/individuals, funding sources, website and social networks, etc.) and the organisation (working groups, decision-making, upcoming meetings and periodicity). During the plenary session, some operational aspects were identified to implement the network such as: a name, a logo, a Twitter/X account, an email account and an online repository to share materials. It was proposed that the network meet every three months mainly in an online format.

During the third agenda session, the work was focused on the basic demands of the network, discussing around three main areas:

- The universal right to care (including care services for all who need them, the right to independent living, and the right to voice and participation).
- Rights and decent working conditions for care workers.
- Rights, time, and income for those providing care to families and communities.

These demands were unanimously endorsed as the foundation for the network's advocacy efforts, with suggestions for rewording to better reflect independent living perspectives. The concluding discussion focused on ensuring the network’s sustainability through clear objectives, a realistic operational structure, and prioritised commitments. Immediate next steps included creating a shared drive for

resources, establishing communication channels (email and social media accounts), and drafting an endorsement statement to formalise membership. An online meeting was scheduled for September or October, with plans for an in-person meeting later in the year, setting the stage for continued collaboration and actionable progress.

4.8. Turkey

Preparation of the third lab meeting

In preparation for the third national lab, three online meetings were held with the core group, which had been established with three of the lab participants that attended to the first transnational lab in Brussels. A WhatsApp group was also created to facilitate ongoing communication and sharing of information and new ideas which can be added to the upcoming lab. These meetings aimed to evaluate the outcomes of the first and second labs, assess what had been achieved, and identify areas requiring further attention. It was concluded that continuity in participation would significantly contribute to the success of the third meeting. Therefore, the decision was made to invite the original group of participants to the previous lab meetings, including those who could not attend the second lab, with the understanding that they would be updated prior to the third lab.

During the second lab meeting, the lab’s outcome decided was to write a policy brief addressing the challenges civil society organisations face in their interactions with Europe-wide international institutions. While several lab participants had experience with international organisations, including the EU, it was noted that many needed a more comprehensive understanding of how these bodies work and the networks they are connected to. As a result, FIERCE partner jointly with the core group of activists decided to invite two activists/experts, who had worked with these institutions to make dedicated presentations in the lab.

The third organisation meeting with the core group was used to begin structuring the agenda and planning the third lab’s agenda, with small group sessions to develop the content of the policy brief. The planning was finalised via email exchanges. Parallely, invitations and reminders were sent to the other lab participants. The final task before the lab day was to organise the attendees into groups, considering both complementary experiences and observations from previous labs on which groups worked most effectively.

Agenda and description of the lab sessions

The third Turkish lab meeting took place on May 10th 2024 and was organised in four main sessions. The first one dedicated to the presentation by the two invited experts on “EU mechanisms and feminist lobbying: challenges and opportunities”. The second and third sessions, were organised as work group activities with collective discussions about policy proposals on mechanisms and instruments for supporting feminist civil society organisations and how to support feminist civil society’s ability to hold public institutions and processes accountable, respectively. Finally, the last session had been programmed as a collective work on the first draft for the policy brief; however, couldn’t be implemented because the second and third sessions took longer than expected. There was a roll call asking participants whether they would like to be included in follow-up meetings where the policy brief would be written.

The first session of the lab featured two experts who delivered in-depth presentations on the structure and functioning of the European Commission, European Parliament, and European Council, highlighting challenges and opportunities for feminist advocacy within these bodies. They emphasised the European Commission’s rotating bureaucratic system, designed to ensure transparency and prevent entrenched biases, but noted that it poses challenges for advocacy efforts, requiring activists to continually educate incoming officials on feminist priorities. Additionally, rigid institutional structures necessitate engaging

with multiple units beyond those focused explicitly on gender equality, demanding significant resources. The experts also observed shifting priorities in the European Parliament and Council, where gender equality has been overshadowed by issues like security, migration, and resilience, further complicating advocacy efforts.

Particular challenges were noted for feminists from Turkey, who face limited access to central EU funding programmes like Daphne and CERV due to their government's policies, and encounter complex bureaucratic and regulatory hurdles. The experts proposed strategic approaches, including mainstreaming gender within all EU priorities, ensuring gender-focused funding distribution, advocating for pro-equality candidates during commissioner appointments and parliamentary elections, and fostering global feminist networks to promote solidarity and share effective practices.

In the second session, participants were divided into three groups to discuss how the EU can better support feminist civil society advocacy. The discussion centred on three key questions: assessing the current support mechanisms, critiquing their sufficiency, and proposing policy improvements. The policy suggestions emphasised the need for strengthening state accountability and addressing structural barriers that hinder feminist civil society's effectiveness. Participants highlighted the importance of improving access to information by dismantling language barriers and ensuring local actors are informed about international mechanisms. They called for reducing bureaucratic obstacles that limit civil society's engagement with international bodies and for the introduction of effective sanctions to hold states accountable for human rights violations. Encouraging the development of new policies was seen as critical, along with conducting advocacy audits to ensure funding is utilised for its intended purposes. Financial transparency, easing access to funding—particularly for grassroots organisations—and including indemnity as a budget item were identified as key measures to enhance capacity building and resilience. Furthermore, the participants emphasised the importance of perceiving civil society organisations as active participants and stakeholders in decision-making processes, fostering collaboration with semi-public organisations such as bar associations, professional chambers, and local governing bodies, and ensuring genuine implementation of public-civil society and inter-civil society collaborations. They also recommended mainstreaming gender equality in local administrations by making such measures permanent in their structures. To further enhance accountability, they proposed introducing monitoring and complaint mechanisms, such as a GREVIO-like model at the EU level, and systematically monitoring gender-related action plans to evaluate outcomes and budget allocation. Lastly, they stressed the need to prevent practices that offload state responsibilities, such as social services, onto civil society organisations.

During the third session, participants developed proposals to strengthen feminist civil society's capacity to hold public institutions accountable. They assessed the current status quo, critiqued it by highlighting good and bad examples, and proposed measures to improve existing mechanisms. The identified policy proposals were: financial monitoring, monitoring of political connections of funded organisations, transparency and accountability, transform projects into long-run sustainable programmes, reconsider the funding distribution criteria, among others.

4.9. Transnational lab

The third transnational lab took place on November 4th 2024 during the FIERCE week, event organised in Venice (November 4th-7th), combining also the winter school (T5.1) and the launch of the FIERCE transnational network (T5.1). The lab was focused on the analysis of the results of the “Five FIERCE Claims for a Feminist Europe Campaign” for the EP 2024 elections, that had been the result of the co-creation process of the previous lab sessions. In addition, the sessions were focused on deciding next steps and giving recommendations for future actions of the FIERCE transnational network—to be launched on November 7th, the last day of the FIERCE week—.

The lab was organised as a half-day session, which started with a first session summarizing the work of all the national labs. Specific posters had been elaborated by the FIERCE team displaying the collectives in each lab, as well as the main characteristics of each lab’s outcome. Following, the facilitators of the meeting —Italian partners from SV and French partners from EA— presented the main results of the campaign and briefly summarised some highlights on the new political landscape to trigger some reflections on the future of the campaign. To see the campaign results, please go to section 6.9.

After implementing the feedback questionnaire and coffee break, the work focused on analysing the future scenarios of the campaign. Three scenarios were presented: (i) discontinue the campaign, (ii) continue it as an independent initiative, (iii) integrate it with other initiatives. The pool of available resources developed in the previous labs available to possibly continue the campaign are: the FIERCE charter, which is the manifesto detailing the five claims of the campaign, the graphic materials developed and a dedicated section in the FIERCE project website with a form to sign the charter.

During the dynamics, the limitations were made present to be as transparent as possible about the existing resources to continue the campaign. In particular, it was emphasised that the budget assigned for the implementation of the campaign had already been spent; therefore, there would not be a team available to actively support the implementation of the campaign financed by the project.

Three groups were formed to work on the three possible future scenarios for the campaign. A brainstorming exercise with guided questions was proposed to then present the results in plenary. Some Following, the most relevant conclusions are presented:

- The general opinion was that it would be a pity to discontinue the campaign, considering all the work that has been already implemented. Therefore, it was recommended to continue the campaign as part of the initiatives pursued in the transnational network.
 - One group recommended to temporarily pause the campaign until the establishment of the network and the definition of its political strategy.
 - Another group mentioned that, even though integrating it with other initiatives would be the optimal solution, it would be more realistic to continue it as an independent initiative.
- Participants raised that the campaign and the network formed in the lab is strong because it is the only European feminist network specifically formed around the aim of fighting the anti-gender backlash.
- Some recommendations given by participants were:
 - Find a source of “pressure” for the political advocacy, similar to the EP elections. It was proposed to focus the campaign on national elections, presenting the claims and charter as a manifesto supported by a transnational coalition behind.
 - It was recommended to communicate to the newly elected Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) showing the process that was followed to implement the campaign and to lobby on different levels.
 - Promote training and new capacities on advocacy as part of the work on the transnational network.
 - An option for funding that was proposed was to present the campaign as a “cost action” project. This option was later dismissed during the FIERCE week because one of the French collectives has presented the proposal on a similar project.

During the last day of the FIERCE week, November 7th during the launch of the transnational network, these recommendations were presented to inspire the work on the objectives and configuration of the network. French FIERCE partners, leading the implementation of the transnational network (T5.1) will consider these during the upcoming meetings of the network, scheduled for the first trimester of 2025.

5. Analysis of lab’s internal dynamics

5.1. Denmark

Decision-making inside the lab and power dynamics

Collaboration and respectful dialogue, as well as the inclusionary and participatory approach adopted in the communication and meetings have been among the most valued aspects by the participants in the Danish lab. Despite this, considering the four replies to the feedback questionnaire, problems with an uneven distribution of time in the participants’ interventions were highlighted in particular by one respondent:

“Another respondent mentions that it was surprisingly difficult to agree among the participants even though they all have the same aim (equality and non-discrimination). One respondent points out that some had more of a say at the meetings because of the difference in level of activity and investment in the network activities as well as the generalized need for someone to make a decision after debating for a long time. This reflects the fact that ESPD to a large extent took the lead on many of the initiatives in the network and invested time and energy in this, to a larger extent than the other organisations”.

AAU made different efforts to try dealing with power imbalances in the network, mainly actively trying to involve the organisations representing people with disabilities during the discussions and having sign language interpreters during the meetings.

Danish FIERCE partners reflected about their power privilege in the lab: *“We have, during both this lab as well as the previous ones, been continuously aware and reflective about the power privilege coming with being able to set the agenda and frame the way that a problem is discussed, as we have literally done several times by, for instance, elaborating presentations of the network and proposing agendas for all the national labs. At the same time, we do not believe that we have been the ones putting forward the concrete ideas for the different labs’ outcomes, such as facilitating a workshop at the Danish Youth Democracy Festival. Instead, it has indeed been many of the other participants who have repeatedly come up with relevant ideas about, for instance, doing a social media campaign, as the network initiated in Spring 2024, or specifically engaging young people, which several organisations have proposed themselves. However, even though we have repeatedly encouraged the organisations and participants to collaborate as much as possible outside of the more formal settings that we establish through the FIERCE project, the participants have to our knowledge primarily followed our activities. In this way, the participants might still perceive our role as being the ones who are supposed to push the network and its activities forward, which is a potential point of concern regarding future activities after the end of the FIERCE project in 2025. In a certain sense, our facilitating role in the network has been taken for granted, and it is currently not clear whether the network can continue without our supportive role”.*

Controversial issues and tensions/debates

No explicit conflicts and no disagreements on substantial issues were reported in the third Danish lab. There were some disagreements on the different strategies and public communication though, in particular, regarding the engagement of the target population (teenagers) at the Danish Youth Democracy Festival, about the difficulty of engaging them: *“One participant was a high school teacher and emphasized that young people’s attention span can be very short, necessitating a lot more interaction during the workshop as well as strategic engagement on issues relating to, for instance, sexuality which might spark their interest. In response, a representative from ESPD mentioned that they have been visiting many high schools over the years, and that they have not experienced significant difficulties in getting the students’ attention”.*

Other points of disagreement were the pedagogical approach to take during the workshop and how the workshop should look like. No decisions were made about these points during the lab and a final

decision was made during the meeting in May, where only few participants attended. During this meeting no voting was made and decisions were taken by asking participant’s opinions. It is worth highlighting that all disagreements in the lab were managed as respectful exchanges between the participants.

Emotions

Danish FIERCE partners reported similarities between the expressed emotions during the workshops with the results of the critical frame analysis carried out in WP2. In particular, it was possible to identify a mix of positive and negative emotions. On the one side, indignation and frustration related to the persistence of the sexist behaviour, stereotypes and broader societal structures. On the other hand, they mix with a sense of joy and gratitude about the possibility of sharing experiences and engage in meaningful collaborations withing the network.

Establishment of new alliances

The lab has been built on the basis of some of already existing alliances between ESPD and a leading member of Disabled People’s Organisations Denmark around an article they had written together. During the setting-up process of the Danish lab, AAU contacted ESPD and after some exchanges it was decided to focus on sexism under a minority perspective as theme of the lab. After ineffectively trying to involve organisations focusing ethnic minorities, they decided to invite organisations focused on disabilities, after considering the aforementioned article as an interesting starting point to go in-depth. The establishment of the lab has created a network creating new alliances with organisations that had not been in contact before, such as Sabaah and The Danish Association of Youth with Disabilities.

Final considerations

Comments on intersectionality

The Danish lab is the lab addressing intersectionality in a most explicit way as part of the lab’s theme, with sexism under a minority perspective. The focus has been made specifically in being diversely abled and having an ethnic/migratory background.

In terms of the lab composition, all of the 4 lab participants who replied to the feedback questionnaire mentioned belonging to organisations that implement an intersectional approach, while only 2 self-defined as feminist. Regarding the self-identification with intersectional identities, 2 participants mentioned having a disability. One of them also self-identified as LGBTIQ+ and having an ethnic/migratory background.

Comments on democratic innovations

As reported by AAU, the outcome is innovative in the Danish context with regard to the formation of the network and intersectional alliances, promoting the collaboration of organisations which usually address their themes as independent stances. In addition, addressing sexism under an intersectional perspective, collecting the experience of population belonging to different minorities can also be considered innovative because the awareness raising of this topic is still largely unknown and unclear. Despite this, the organisation of the panel conversation in November 2023 and the social media campaign have followed similar formats as other political campaigns and have not involved a broader audience. The bystander workshop at The Danish Youth Festival is more innovate because even though it is built “*on an already existing concept developed by ESPD but still engages participants in the workshop about sexism in a whole new manner by presenting them with different scenarios, showcasing how sexism at times targets and affects people from different minorities. In this sense, the innovative character of such a workshop consists in a sort of democratic role-playing*”.

5.2. Greece

Decision-making inside the lab and power dynamics

All of the decisions inside the lab were made without voting, with participants discussing and agreeing in open plenary discussions. The agenda of the third lab had already been agreed by consensus of the participants during the second lab. In addition, modifications had been proposed under a participatory approach via email exchanges with the FIERCE researchers. All three respondents of the questionnaire of the lab’s feedback mentioned having actively participated in the labs’ sessions.

It was reported by FIERCE Greek partners that almost all issues on which decisions had to be made during the third lab meeting concerned time-management due to delays in the proposed agenda:

“The first session on the first day as well as the first session of the second day ended later than scheduled by 30 minutes. So, we had to decide how long the break would be and when the second session would begin. Moreover, due to the first delay on the second day, the last session on the lab’s outcome had to be moved later by half an hour. On all these occasions, the PI asked all the present members how we should proceed, one or two would respond that we should move later by 15 mins the break and/or the session and the rest would agree. There was almost an immediate collective understanding on these issues.”

The other decisive point in the lab in terms of decision-making was about the proposal for the lab’s outcome, which took place during the last session of the lab. After the proposal presented by AUTH, there was a unanimous expression of consent by the participants.

Regarding power dynamics inside the lab, it was reported that most members were effectively on a footing of equality. Indeed, participants self-organised in under an assembly-based approach. A power differential could be traced mainly among new members of the lab who had no prior acquaintance with the other members and had not participated in the former labs. As a result, initially they seemed to be more cautious and reserved at the outset. Despite this, as the lab went on and they experience the friendly, open and more or less egalitarian atmosphere, most new members felt at ease and took actively part. The 3 participants replying to the questionnaire emphasised that in general power dynamics were balanced and that in the cases were some participants had a more active and influential role in the discussions was because of their specific experience and expertise in the discussed themes.

It is important to mention that FIERCE Greek partners, were aware of the horizontal dynamics established since the first lab and deliberately decided to take a less active role in the lab in order to avoid affecting the power dynamics. As reported by them: *“My firm decision from the first lab was that decisions would be made in common by all participants on equal terms so that the labs would emerge from near-horizontal (i.e. non-hierarchical) collaboration rather than the authority and direction of academic staff. This was actively conveyed in my communication with all participants from the outset and was manifested in the actual practice of our communication and collaboration for and in the labs.”*

Controversial issues and tensions/debates

Only one conflict was reported by Greek FIERCE partners, which took place during the second day of the lab, in particular during the presentation about the mandatory joint custody law. In particular, one of the AUTH Gender Equality Committee representatives mentioned that the law was unjust to fathers, after sharing his personal experience as a divorced father. He mentioned some statistics about the scant number of custodies awarded to fathers prior to the new law, which was intensely disputed by a member of the AUTH research team. The formed eventually conceded that the numbers may not accurate but insisted in the unfair treatment to fathers.

To solve this conflict, the principal investigator of the AUTH team, noted that the focus of the discussion was the antifeminist features of the campaign in favour of the law and not the lookout for the best legal

framework for shared custody, which was beyond our discussion. In addition, it was referred the need to finalise the discussion to mention the move towards the final item of the agenda, the ‘outcome’ of the lab, as time was finishing and some participants needed to leave.

Emotions

Most of emotions were positive inside the lab: *“The main emotions among members were sympathy, understanding, a spirit of collaboration and, occasionally, a feeling of solidarity for the actions of the participating groups. The whole ambience was friendly, open, relaxed and solidary, building on our acquaintance and prior experience in the first two labs. The new participants (Meduses, new people from the Rainbow School and AUTH Gender Equality Committee) were welcome and they soon felt at ease”*.

During the only moment of conflict, it is worth highlighting that some of the members of the labs, who openly opposed to the joint custody law showed understanding for the personal position of the AUTH Gender Equality Committee who seemed to voice his dissent from the general rejection of the legal reform. Hence, no bitterness or resentment ensued from this short incident.

Establishment of new alliances

Most of the collectives participating in the lab had not jointly worked before the lab. FIERCE Greek partners, reported that two new alliances were most likely to take place:

- Between the grassroots group ‘Meduses’ based in Larissa and Karditsa Women’s Center, which is an institutional agency based in a town next to Larissa. As they work on the same issues, they are local neighbours and acquainted themselves with each other in the lab -they had never met before- it is likely that they will work together in the future if the need arises or the circumstances call for such collaboration.
- Another possible future collaboration is between the Rainbow School who is an NGO specializing in education for LGBTQIA+ issues in schools and AUTH university, given our common activity in education.

FIERCE Greek partners reported about the difficulties to involve grassroots organisations with researched in an EU-funded projects, dismissing their participation in mostly all activities, with exception of the interviews: *“The grassroots activists and the more formal groups who accepted our invitation to participate in the lab were people whom I got to know personally from previous research and interaction or personal relationships. Furthermore, regarding all groups participating in the labs, it was nearly impossible, and seemed overly demanding, to engage them in certain activities requested for all labs of the project, mainly the participation in the international EU campaign and collective work on the ‘lab’s outcome’ beyond their contributions and participation in the labs themselves. The reason is again that they are people who are employed and spend their limited free time on activism. So, the time they can devote for extra activities not directly related to their work and their group/organisation is almost”*.

Final considerations

Comments on intersectionality

In terms of the lab composition, all of the 3 lab participants who replied to the feedback questionnaire, all of them mentioned organisations mentioned following an intersectional approach, while one mentioned not belonging to a feminist organisation. Regarding the self-identification with intersectional identities, only one person self-identified as LGBTQI+.

Respondents of the feedback questionnaire mentioned that the lab allowed different perspectives to be taken into consideration and that decision-making processes were open. One of the participants that had also attended to the transnational lab mentioned: *“The structure of our discussions and activities was designed to be inclusive and participatory, ensuring that voices from various feminist organisations*

and collectives were given ample opportunity to contribute. The lab emphasized an intersectional approach, which was evident in how different perspectives were actively solicited and integrated into the conversations. Each participant was encouraged to share their unique insights and experiences, fostering a rich dialogue that reflected the complexity and diversity of feminist movements.”

Intersectionality was addressed thematically among the thematic discussion of the third Greek lab, in particular during the presentations of the first day. During the presentation of the Karditsa Women’s Center, they mentioned to address migration issues by observing at the ethnic background and acting according to it. For instance, they made a reference to Albanian women who usually need more time to leave their home in a situation of GBV. In addition, during the second presentation of the first day of the lab, two members of the Mesopotamia Solidarity School presented how they operationalise intersectionality in their education programme.

Comments on democratic innovations

FIERCE Greek partners reported the lab’s outcome being innovative mainly in two elements: (i) the exchanges between NGOs, institutional actors and grassroots groups on particular topics pursued at some depth, which are not very common in Greece in the last years and (ii) the ‘emergent’ methodology of loosely co-ordinated and largely spontaneous, non-hierarchical interaction worked and turned out to be operative and effective”.

5.3. France

Decision-making inside the lab and power dynamics

Consensus was the most preferred method for decision-making impulse by FIERCE French facilitators, who organised long sessions for exchange and agreement to make decision inside the lab. When this was not possible, they proceeded with voting. In particular, this was implemented to decide the lab’s outcome, via an online vote, in which 80% of lab members voted. One of the participants that replied to the questionnaire, manifested their frustration of not having enough time to delve deeper into the discussions subjects throughout the lab.

Power dynamics were mainly related to age and experience, specifically with some activists from Planning Familial —one of the organisations with the longest trajectory in the French feminist movement and with a participant working full-time in the organisation— and younger activists from smaller collectives. Despite this, dynamics inside the lab were rather horizontal and participants took care on neutralizing biases.

Considering the replies to questionnaire, most participants manifested that they did not have the impression that there were more influential participants in the discussions and decisions of the lab. Despite this, one mentioned that the most experienced participants were usually sharing more during the sessions and one illustrated about their participation: *“While the discussions and debates where always encouraged when all the organisations met, I do not find that I was able to actively participate in the decision-making process. Indeed, I do feel that bigger organisations, due primarily to the extended experience they had coming into the lab and their exposure, were able to put forth more easily their ideas to the group”.*

FIERCE lab facilitators reported that there might have been some privilege dynamics between facilitators and lab participants because the former are salaried to organise the labs, while the latter were volunteers. In addition, to mitigate the position of moderator and expert/researcher, horizontal dynamics prevailed in the labs.

Controversial issues and tensions/debates

There were no tensions or debates associated with the content discussed in the lab. There were two controversial issues identified by lab participants during the third session. The most relevant one was the limited intersectional character of the lab composition in terms of race. Although this did not cause conflicts, this did raise discomfort among the lab participants as a self-critic related to the intersectional stance they claim to have. Moderators mentioned that they had tried involving an Afro-feminist association that chose not to participate because they were not interested. The other source of discomfort among the lab participants was the frustration of not having more resources to advance the lab towards sustainability with funding modalities.

This was confirmed by participants who replied to the questionnaire, none of them reported having experienced conflict. Despite this, one mentioned having felt some tension related to the urgency of implement concrete actions in the time previous to the European Parliament elections: *“I sensed some tension due to the urgency of the situation a few months before the European elections and the desire of certain structures to be as efficient as possible. So, we changed the programme a little, taking into account the comments of some organisations”*.

Emotions

Emotions expressed by participants during the lab generally fell into two categories. On the one hand, participants expressed enthusiasm and joy in being together, admiration for peers, and optimism about the feminist struggle. The collective work and the feeling of organizing to respond to attacks often experienced individually were overwhelmingly positive and widely expressed.

Three of the five participants that replied to the questionnaire, expressed more value towards the moments for collective discussion and exchange. One participant expressed: *“realising that there were so many actions and practices in different countries all working towards the same goal gave me energy and strength”*.

On the other hand, fear in the face of the scale of the attacks and frustration over the lack of resources grew towards the end of the lab, within a French political context where feminist demands seemed invisible or instrumentalised by far-right parties. As all participants were activists in real life, the political issues discussed did not particularly trigger negative emotions, except when they felt powerless, especially towards the end of the lab when confronted with the possibility of no longer coming together to organise.

Establishment of new alliances

Beyond the developments on the specific outcome as discussed during the lab sessions, the French lab has triggered the establishment of a network creating and the sharing of information on strategies for resisting the anti-feminist and anti-gender backlash. This has established new alliances between the feminist groups participating in the lab, such as the association HandsAway joining the network Alerte Féminist thanks to their encounter with #NousToutes. During the third lab participants manifested their interest in supporting FIERCE in the long term as a French network of feminist resistance.

Isolated associations were recognised as integral parts of the French feminist network, such as *HandsAway* and *IPAS*, which was known as an international association but had not engaged much with grassroots French movements. Moreover, the lab contributed to strengthening ties between feminist groups focused on sexual and GBV and LGBTQI+ rights activists, notably through the regular participation of *SOS Homophobie*. Finally, the collaboration between the journalist and the associations seems to have empowered participants by giving them access to someone from the media, which provided a reassuring connection for broadcasting their struggles.

Despite this, it is worth considering that these intersectional alliances have not include anti-racist organisations and other feminist organisations prioritising racialised identities.

Final considerations

Comments on intersectionality

Despite this, the lab was mostly represented by white, high-educated women in their 30-40s. In terms of self-identification with intersectional identities, 3 of 5 respondents to the lab questionnaire were self-identified as belonging to the LGBTIQ+ community. One of them, also identified as having an ethnic background and a disability. Despite almost all of the organisations belonging to the FIERCE lab self-identified as following an intersectional approach, the lack of diversity within the lab was identified as an aspect of criticism by lab participants who identified the need to improve their narrative between intersectionality and the actual alliances they establish. In particular, they raised the self-criticism that the lab was mainly representing the interests of white feminists, with no organisations representing feminist of different ethnic backgrounds.

Comments on democratic innovations

The most innovative component of the French lab was the establishment of new alliances between collectives and networks from different organisations backgrounds that had not collaborated before. Many lab members were familiar with meetings between associations for reports or specific demonstrations, but being brought together around a specific project on the backlash and having the moderation of a European project was an innovation for them.

5.4. Italy

Decision-making inside the lab and power dynamics

The formation of the Italian lab followed a directed/controlled approach, with FIERCE partners convoking the lab with the objective of developing the self-defence manual for teachers defined in advance after bilateral exchanges with one member of the EAD Network. Initially, four representatives of feminist collectives and organisations —Giacomo Brodolini Foundation, Progetto Alice and SCOSSE, from the Educare alle Differenze Network, and Lucha y Siesta—were invited to become part of a core group to participate in a preparatory meeting before the first lab. As a result of this meeting, there was a joint work for the identification of collectives to be invited to the lab, as well as starting an initial brainstorming on how to start to co-creative process to build the self-manual for activists.

The setting-up process of the lab established the conditions to have a rather aligned group in terms of their working and political approaches. This was reinforced because around half of the participants came belonged to three organisations which are part to the Educare alle Differenze Network, which is the largest feminist collective in Italy working in this theme. As a result, participants were usually aligned in their opinions and there were not considerably divergent opinions between them.

Throughout the three sessions, there does not appear to have been any significant power imbalances, with most of the participants having respectful positions towards the opinions of the others. A factor which might have supported horizontal balanced dynamics is the fact that most of the participants had a considerably level of expertise and practical experience in the field; therefore, they were in similar conditions to face the debates and discussions of the lab. An exception to this general climate was present in the in the third lab, where there was new more-experienced participant: she was older and had published books related to EAD. In some moments of the plenary discussions, she made reference to her book and talked as an expert, this created some tension with some of the participants, who replied, making a reference to newer developments in the field. In other limited moments (there was one particular moment) during the plenary sessions, there were some of the participants taking more

the word than others, not always giving the space to the others. In one particular moment, one of the facilitators did a general comment to kindly give the word to others.

Regarding the decision-making processes inside the lab, since the objective of the lab was defined since the first session, all the in-presence labs were action-oriented sessions, focused mainly in the sharing of experiences and the content-develop of the manual. Thus, there was limited space for voting of deliberative techniques for decision-making. The most explicit decision-making process was associated to the table of contents of the self-defence manual, which first draft was prepared by FIERCE partners in charge and was adjusted after receiving participants' feedback in an online meeting, managed as an open feedback session. All the other spaces for the content development where managed as horizontal spaces of discussion where participants could share their experiences and collectively create the content of the manual.

There were two specific questions in the questionnaire dedicated to lab participants dedicated to inquire about the decision-making processes and lab's dynamics. All respondents to the questionnaire manifested having been able to actively participate in the decision-making processes implemented in the lab. When asked to give examples they nominated specific activities, such as the role-play, during the plenary sessions. One participant declared “The environment was welcoming, so after an initial shyness, it wasn't difficult. I remember a moment when we created post-its with protection practices, during which I felt very good and very useful”.

When asked about the power dynamics and whether they had the impression that some participants had more influence in the decision-making processes, most of the respondents to the questionnaire (9) mentioned that participation was horizontal and equally distributed among the attendees, with the lab as a safe-space dynamics of respect when taking the word. Among this group of respondents, two emphasised that participants had different levels of expertise according to the topics of the labs; therefore, that participation of some of them was more active in discussions of their expertise. They emphasised the value of this diversity in the lab.

There were two divergent opinions among the respondents: one mentioned that there were some differences regarding the influence of the interventions, which could have been determined according to the collectives/organisations they were representing. In addition, one participant made a critical comment: “I believe that being in an assembly is not something to be taken for granted, and it would be good practice to always specify the best posture to adopt”.

This participant comes from a grassroots movement where assembly-based decision-making dynamics are the norm, which suggests that the dynamics of the lab may have been perceived as less horizontal. In an informal conversation with one of the facilitators, this person made a critical comment about some of the other participants not respecting an assembly-based approach and attempting to impose their point of view by referencing their expertise. See the following section for a more detailed commentary on this intervention.

Controversial issues and tensions/debates

There were no open and significative conflicts inside the lab that facilitators needed to mediate and there were not significantly divergent positions regarding the thematic considered in the lab. Indeed, most of the participants were aligned, which is not surprising since most of them are part of the Educare Alle Differenze Network or self-identify as feminist and transfeminist.

Despite this, during the third lab, there were some tensions identified between some of the participants. The first situation was originated in one of the groups during the role-play with one of the participants exercising the role of a teacher implementing an EAD project, while other an anti-gender parent. The latter, who in real life is a teacher in school, was considerably provocative during the interventions. The

former, who started the role-play with a rationale and conciliative tone, finally fell in the provocations and replied with an altered tone giving an extreme not common example to expose her point, which lead to the instrumentalization of the discourse by the participant playing the role of the anti-gender parent.

In terms of content-development this was positive because it led to a series of recommendations of what to avoid when discussing with anti-gender actors. In terms of the dynamics between those two participants, there was a manifestation of disagreement in the subsequent plenary by one of the persons that had participated in the role-play, mentioning that the other was trying to impose their positions due to her expertise and years of experience. This person made a comment in plenary about new more updated developments. This might be reflecting some of the existing tensions inside the feminist movement, related to generational issues.

As anticipated in the previous section, there was also some tension created between participants used to more assembly-based approached in their grassroot collectives, with respect to the others not used to them. In particular, the former identified as some of the others as trying to monopolize the discussions.

When asking participants about the presence of conflicts during the sessions, 10 of the 12 respondents to the questionnaire mentioned not having witnessed conflicts, while two differed, expressing:

- “I was annoyed by the interruptions and the lack of respect for speaking turns by other participants”.
- “I didn’t notice any tensions or conflicts. Surely, there were moments when not everyone was aligned, but I believe that is also part of the importance of this experience”.

Emotions

Discussions about the Italian context and the political situation triggered emotions of anger, frustration and disappointment towards the far-right government and the official institutions of the public Italian institutions about sex-affective education (see section 6.4 for more details on the context). Loneliness and isolation of teachers implementing EAD projects in schools was repeated throughout the three labs meetings.

Despite this, during discussions, these references were also accompanied to a call to keep fighting, paying attention to the self and collective care, establishing alliances to create community. Thus, resilience was also identified among the emotions of the lab participants.

The following question was included in the questionnaire to collect perceptions related to emotions: “What were the most significant moments in the lab? Have they triggered strong emotions (positive or negative?)”

Most of the replies were rather general, more relevant moments without including specific reflections on the emotions experienced. Among the relevant moments identified there were the group works; the plenary sessions and the role play of the third lab. Some participants identified listening to first-hand experiences of teachers suffering attacks in schools as particularly valuable and emotionally engaging.

One of the participants identified having experienced “very positive emotions” during the second transnational session where she participated in a session regarding the feminine condition during wars. One participant clearly expressed experiencing both discouragement and enthusiasm: *“I only participated in the third meeting. The most significant moment was the role play. It evoked ambivalent feelings in me: on the one hand, a certain disheartenment in recognising the effects of anti-gender propaganda and how it forces us into a defensive position; on the other hand, the enthusiasm of being*

among comrades and doing something concrete, such as preparing/training ourselves to respond to attacks”.

This last quotation greatly summarises the experience emerging in several moments by the participants throughout the sessions: they feel impotence and discouragement because they face enormous difficulties in their daily activities. Despite this, sharing experiences and strengthening bonds was described as refreshing and necessary to keep their mission.

Establishment of new alliances

Since its set-up, the Italian FIERCE lab has been closely related to different feminist networks and collectives, mainly the Educare Alle Differenze Network. As a result, many of the organisations/collectives/networks participating were already working together. Indeed, most of the respondents to the questionnaire, when asked about the alliances of their organisations, most of them reported already working with some of the realities included in the lab. Despite this, when asked about the establishment of new alliances, 8 of 12 responded positively about the establishment of new alliances.

Final considerations

Comments on intersectionality

In terms of composition, almost all of the organisations conforming the lab follows an intersectional approach: 11 of 12 respondents declared it in the questionnaire. Unfortunately, none of the respondents provided more details on the types of intersectional inequalities specifically addressed by them. In addition, as detailed in section 3.4, some of the lab participants self-identified with some intersectional identity: one person identified as having a disability or chronic condition, one as having an ethnic or migratory background and three as belonging to the LGBTIQ+ community.

Intersectionality was addressed in terms of the content of the manual. For instance, some of the most common were:

- Attacks to the LGBTIQ+ community are amongst the most common when implementing EAD projects. They take different shapes and are commonly associated with arguments, such as that EAD is homosexualising children.
- There were discussions on how anti-gender actors instrumentalise a narrative of “the otherness” associating migration and having an ethnical background with multiple problems of the Italian society. This is also affecting EAD, for instance, when the Minister Valditara recently associated GBV with illegal immigration when talking about a femicide done by a white Italian man.

Comments on democratic innovations

Theoretical developments of democratic innovations conceive as part of the literature in governance contexts, mainly focusing in new increasing the participatory and deliberative components of democracies, opening the decision-making spaces to broader actors. As established in the first version of the D4.1: *“looking at the FIERCE Labs processes and potential outcomes within the FIERCE project life-cycle, we would position them more towards the deliberative end of the democratic innovations’ spectrum. However, FIERCE is opting for an attempt at being concrete, not limiting the Labs to discussions/dialogues only. Each lab is aimed at producing a politically oriented outcome that could potentially impact within one or more steps of the political cycle”.*

Thus, in the framework of the context, co-creative democratic innovations in governance were identified as having the following attributes: collaborative, solution-oriented and pragmatic/empirical approach. In the co-creation methodology (D4.1, version 1), it is established that FIERCE focuses on

social movements and aims to connect them to institutional allies to strengthen their dialogue, as well as proposing feminist-oriented policies to contribute fighting the anti-democratic advancements implemented by anti-feminist and anti-gender actors.

All participants from the Italian labs were members from the feminist movement or researcher-activists —e.g. participants to the first lab that were part of the Fondazione Giacomo Brodolini—. In addition, to the first session, there was one participant from the CGIL (Confederazione Generale Italiana del Lavoro), one of the largest unions. There were no party representatives or representatives from public institutions, because, as previously described, the Italian government is following a generally contrary position to EAD. The Ministry itself was considered as conducting some of the attacks to the teacher throughout the sessions of the lab.

Despite following a more agonistic approach, the lab’s outcome is potentially contributing to strengthening the democracy in Italy, which is at-risk with the far-right limiting the rights on individuals. If broadly disseminated by the feminist networks conforming the lab and beyond it could also be a helpful tool to widespread the resistance towards the democratic backsliding promoted by conservative and anti-gender actors. Furthermore, the self-defence manual could work as a tool in a more institutional setting in the future in case there is a political shift in the government.

Considering that the theme and outcome was not decided in the lab as the result of a deliberative, but proposed directly by FIERCE partners, there are not identifiable characteristics of democratic innovations in terms of decision-making or the lab’s internal dynamics. Despite this, there are some recognisable elements of democratic innovations considering the lab’s outcome.

5.5. Poland

Decision-making inside the lab and power dynamics

Besides the drop-out dynamics for the reasons previously explained, the core group that remained active during the second and third in-presence labs very well and *“therefore there were no ‘difficult’ emotions in place that would jeopardise the lab’s dynamics. Also, decisions were taken unanimously after processes of deliberation”*.

When asked whether some participants had more influence on the discussions or decisions than others, the one lab participant that replied to the feedback questionnaire confirmed that some participants were more dominant in the discussions: *“Yes, some could not stop taking. But this is a case in every collective. Some enjoy higher status/experience (e.g. professional position, age) and feel they have more to share or know the right way. Although they occupied much of the deliberation time, the decision reflected a consensus rather than their sole viewpoints”*.

Polish FIERCE partners identified taming some of the participants’ personae to prevent them from dominating the lab as one of the main challenges. To manage this, they applied moderation techniques such as rounds of comments asking all attendants to participate. They also reported that participants with an academic background showed attempts to self-tame not to use their privilege to use their privilege stemming from their education or social position.

Controversial issues and tensions/debates

There were no explicit problems inside the lab; however, age was one of the division lines, specifically during the first lab which was the most populated. Older activists —aged more than years old— pointed out that movements’ memory would enhance the feeling of belonging and the actions, because the contemporary feminist movement is not aware of the history from previous decades and is usually replicating their actions and mistakes in some cases. The one participant that replied to the feedback

questionnaire mentioned that deliberation was successful and that “*participants treated each other with respect and care*”.

In addition, drop-out might have taken place due to some internal conflicts inside the feminist movement, which emerged after the presidential elections, which took place after the first lab in October 2023.

Emotions

The one participant answering to the feedback questionnaire mentioned as positive emotions experienced “*sense of community, belonging, understanding, and shared experiences*”, while negative “*realization of how divided the feminist community is on certain issues, which prevents effective collective action*”.

Establishment of new alliances

As referred in section 3.5 all of the attendees to the third Polish lab belongs to the radical fraction of the feminist movement, which is based on grassroots activism, street politics and street protests. Polish FIERCE partners did not report the establishment of new alliances; however, the one participant that replied to the feedback questionnaire did mention having established new alliances.

Final considerations

Comments on intersectionality

Attempts were made to be inclusive with one member who was Polish born, in particular, efforts to assure that her voice was heard equally to those spoken in Polish as a mother tongue. This person, who was the participant that replied to the feedback questionnaire confirmed having established new alliances.

Comments on democratic innovations

FIERCE Polish partners mentioned that some innovative elements showing patterns related to democracy in Poland were the lab’s theme and the action (“*the medium to spread it*”). In particular, the lab’s theme was changed after shifting the priorities during the second lab, passing from sexual and reproductive rights —abortion in particular— to labour rights. During the first lab, abortion had been chosen due to the restriction in abortion rights by the former ultra conservative government. After 2023 presidential elections, the centrist civil coalition (KO) formed a government; therefore, lab participants decided to change the lab’s theme to labour rights, where one of the major gaps in the feminist activism was identified. In addition, the Polish lab has shown changes in the dynamics of the Polish democracy, being more inclusive with migrants residing in Poland. This was expressed in the development of the campaign in Ukrainian and English besides Polish.

5.6. Slovenia

Decision-making inside the lab and power dynamics

Decisions regarding the lab’s content and materials were decided by Slovenian FIERCE partners and the lab’s core group in a “fluid” collaboration where contributions were organised according the expertise and experience of the members of the group. The core group was selected considering their diversity both generationally and in terms of involvement in the feminist movement and feminist groups. Decision-making did not include formal deliberation techniques or voting; however, they had an elevated number of meetings to coordinate the preparation of exhibition materials.

Regarding power dynamics, when asked about whether some of the participants were more influential than other one of the respondents to the feedback questionnaire responded affirmatively, while the other two not.

Controversial issues and tensions/debates

Slovenian FIERCE partners did not report any controversies or tensions. Discussion was used as a mechanism to solve any possible tensions regarding argumentation on diversity of opinions. According to the replies to the feedback questionnaire, two participants mentioned having experienced tensions of conflicts. One wrote: *“Yes, I had some conflicts. They were resolved by talking to each other calmly, also by apologizing when necessary.”*

The other participant reported having asked one black participant where she came from originally and realising too late that her comment was interpreted as racist. She also mentioned that she wrote her an apology email with no reply and she mentioned that she would like to meet her again to build back their mutual trust and respect.

Emotions

Slovenian FIERCE partners reported that enthusiasm was the prevailing emotion under *“the conviction that we are doing important things and that each one of us can make a significant contribution to the final goal - the exhibition. We spent a lot of time together, the atmosphere was relaxed, there was no shortage of laughter, and above all there was a positive energy.”* This was also highlighted by one of the respondents to the feedback questionnaire: *“The beginning of working on the design of the exhibition (receiving the input material). The opening of the exhibition. Both triggered positive emotions (excitement and joy).”*

Recalling to the feedback questionnaire, when asked which were the most significant moments for the participants in and what emotions the triggered, participants replied:

- Highlighting the sense of a community: *“The feeling of belonging to a group of dedicated and capable people from different EU countries and Turkey, with similar values and focus as ours”.*
- Highlighting having experienced both positive and negative emotions: *“The discussions we had while preparing the exhibition on the history of women's reproductive rights in Yugoslavia and later Slovenia were highly engaging and, yes, also emotional. Many emotions were involved, from negative to positive”*

Establishment of new alliances

Slovenian FIERCE partners reported that the lab allowed the establishment of new alliances: *“The cooperative environment, characterized by equality and horizontal power dynamics, enhanced the potential for future alliances.”* This was confirmed by the three respondents to the lab feedback questionnaire.

Final considerations

Comments on intersectionality

Intersectionality was not directly addressed in the Slovenian lab in the development of the exhibition materials. In addition, it is worth highlighting that none of the respondents to the feedback questionnaire self-identified with intersectional identities.

Comments on democratic innovations

Slovenian FIERCE partners reported considering the lab’s outcome and processes as a form of democratic innovation:

“We view both the process and outcome of the Lab as a form of democratic innovation. The feminist exhibition on reproductive rights emerged in a context where the feminist movement is responding to de-democratization processes. Although the constitutional framework safeguarding reproductive rights remains intact, significant attacks persist in informal arenas. Efforts to restrict access include past

political proposals to introduce co-payments for abortion as part of austerity measures, alongside informal practices within healthcare institutions. These practices often involve inadequate information about gynaecological procedures, intrusive questioning of women’s decisions, lack of psychological support or post-abortion counselling, and distressing conditions, such as performing abortions in the same rooms as pregnant women or those undergoing in vitro fertilization. More recently, the implementation of conscientious objection by pharmaceutical staff refusing to provide contraceptive pills has become a significant issue. Additionally, anti-gender movements continue to pose a challenge by seeking to influence public opinion.

Particularly because of these informal attacks, it is crucial for the feminist movement to engage not only in formal political processes but also in informal grassroots arenas. The exhibition, conceived as a public space intervention, stands out as both a powerful and innovative action. Moreover, it introduced new content by addressing often-overlooked topics in the public discourse on reproductive rights, such as violence within reproductive healthcare.

The feminist exhibition not only commemorates these historic achievements of the feminist movement in Slovenia but also highlights its significant and ongoing role in advocating for the protection and advancement of reproductive rights. As full access to reproductive rights is a fundamental pillar of democracy and gender equality, the exhibition serves as a democratic innovation aimed at revitalizing and strengthening democracy.

The process of creating the exhibition was itself highly significant, as it brought together core group members from diverse backgrounds, both generationally and in terms of their involvement in the feminist movement and various feminist groups. This collaboration was especially crucial in the Slovenian context, where the feminist movement is marked by pluralism and occasional ideological conflicts between groups. By fostering a cooperative environment characterized by equality and horizontal power dynamics, the process strengthened the potential for future alliances among activists from different organisations”.

5.7. Spain

Decision-making inside the lab and power dynamics

There was a broad agreement among the participants on the main issues despite the very diverse positions represented in the lab. Spanish FIERCE partners reported an overall collaborative and supportive environment in the lab sessions, with the participants manifesting the lab as a space to share interests and struggles.

Decision-making processes were mainly following a two-step structure, starting with discussions and content-development in work groups followed by plenary discussions. Decision-making processes allowed for a general consensus on the key demands of the care network, mainly about the diagnostic framing and the three core demands of the network. On the other hand, there was no consensus regarding the choice of action: while some of the participants strongly agreed with the network, other remained sceptical about it. One participant highlighted in the feedback as a critical point the lack of consensus regarding the lab’s outcome; however, acknowledged that the majority supported the creation of the network.

Spanish FIERCE partners reported that the lab was a horizontal specie where power dynamics did not influence the debate, topics and options and opinions discussed. They reported not feeling a power of asymmetry in their role as facilitators because most of lab participants had long and important experience in feminist advocacy and social movement, being used to publicly speaking and “*making their voices heard*”. To assure all voices were heard, Spanish partners implemented efforts such as taking rounds to participate and listen to all opinions and perspectives.

Controversial issues and tensions/debates

There were few conflicts and limited tension to some opposing views emerging in particular situations; however, this did not significantly affect the general agreement on the transcendental diagnosis, claims and priorities established for the action related to care.

Spanish FIERCE partners reported some of the situations of tension: *“For instance, during the first lab, one participant expressed an essentialist, biological view of gender in relation to caregiving, which was quickly challenged from a trans-inclusive perspective. The participants involved did not choose to engage in further debate, and we assumed that the essentialist expression was not intentional. Likewise, when a participant framed sex work as care work, but this viewpoint was not taken up by others. This participant did not attend the second or third lab sessions, and if conflicting positions contributed to their absence, this was not communicated to us. In the second lab, some tensions surfaced around the policy proposal for income or payments for family caregiving. Unlike the previously mentioned topics, this proposal sparked a more detailed debate within the working group, with various arguments presented. However, participants then accepted their differences on this issue. It did not hinder the broader search for common ground.”*

Emotions

Prevailing emotions were empathy and hope, derived by the sharing of experiences and the joint reflection and sharing of concerns and struggles. While discussing on the political situation, there was *“a mix of hope—rooted in past achievements and the potential for future change—and frustration and distrust, stemming from dissatisfaction with current care and migration policies, as well as with institutional political actors and contexts.”*

Establishment of new alliances

Participants highly valued the exchanges that took place in the lab, as well as the possibility to meet, share and reflect. Considering the replies of the feedback questionnaire, 5 out of 8 respondents reported that they had established new contacts and collaborations through their participation in the co-creation lab. Some express optimism regarding the potential of the network, while others have doubts but still hope it can have an impact. The participants that attended the third lab were disappointed that the participation was low.

Final considerations

Comments on intersectionality

Intersectionality has been a pivotal theme in the Spanish lab: the lab’s theme was care work understood in an intersectional and inter-territorial perspective considering both the positions of care givers and care recipients. As a result a highly variegated group of organisations and people was formed, with collectives representing diverse intersectional identities, considering the intersections of migration, ageing, and LGBTBIQ+ rights. In particular, there were organisations representing migrant care workers, representing the rights of care recipients with functional diversity and the rights of older LGBTBIQ+ people. In addition, participants had intersectional identities: at least 6 or 7 had a migrant background from Latin America, one person had functional diversity and at least 1 was an LGBTBIQ+ person. Considering the inter-territorial character of the lab, there were collectives and participants from diverse Spanish regions, mainly Madrid, Seville, the Basque Country, Barcelona and the Canary Islands.

This wide diversity was brought to the discussions in the lab, which addresses intersectionality as one of the foundational elements of the network:

“The co-creation process is grounded in intersectional feminist perspectives, with a strong emphasis on fostering cross-movement connections and alliances. These principles have been pivotal in shaping the

Spanish co-creation lab, where we aimed to explore the topic of care through an intersectional lens, incorporating the perspectives of both caregivers and care recipients. By bringing together diverse collectives and activists, the lab facilitated a dynamic exchange of viewpoints and created a collaborative environment that encouraged mutual learning and the sharing of advocacy strategies.

Comments on democratic innovations

Even though a network is not necessarily innovative in terms of the typology of the action, the network for care is potentially innovative —if it is would be implemented— in terms of the intersectional and inter-territorial approach, jointly addressing the perspectives of care givers and recipients. In the Spanish context it is not common to unite a wide variety of perspectives as it has been implemented in the Spanish lab.

5.8. Turkey

Decision-making inside the lab and power dynamics

The setting-up of the Turkish lab followed an open/inductive approach, leaving the decision of the lab’s outcome to be made inside the in-presence sessions, which took place during the second lab. After first transnational lab took place in September 2023, a core group was formed with the three participants that attended. Since then, they have had a more active role in the lab, periodically communicating with Turkish FIERCE partners and more actively contributing to the planning of the sessions and preparation work to implement the policy brief. Despite this, decisions regarding the policy brief’s content were made during the lab sessions with all participants by consensus building or by including issues on which there was no overt opposition. Voting was never used as a decision-making practice.

The third Turkish lab was more-hands one in comparison to the previous sessions: since the start of the session, when presenting the objectives, it was presented as “an ideational and problem-solving”; thus, focused on the development of the policy brief’s content. Participants mentioned in the survey that there were provided a predominant role inside the lab: *“The facilitators, during the production processes, provided the necessary information to the participants only to help generate responses, and then left the rest—from discussions to presentation and conclusions—to the participants. This allowed the participants to become active subjects of the lab”*.

Facilitators reported having observed “participants’ constructive and dialogic approach throughout the discussions, working groups, and interpersonal communications”. In particular, *“the facilitator observed that the interpersonal interactions of the participants in small group sessions were more intense and motivated than in the previous sessions. She observed an atmosphere that encouraged respect toward all participants”*.

Regarding power dynamics, 1 of the 4 respondents of the questionnaire dedicated to lab participants mentioned there were some dominant voices and that some views were ignored. When asked whether they were able to actively participate in the decision-making processes of the all of them mentioned being able to participate, with the exception of one participant who was less active because of her role as a note taker. One of the participants mentioned: *“Participation was supported and we all had our say in the final reports. Yes, we actively participated in these processes by sharing what we produced together with each other and eventually writing joint texts”*. Opinions were divided among the respondents about the influence of some participants on the discussions and decisions: 2 of them mentioned that decisions were egalitarian, while two mentioned that some were more influential in the decision-making processes: *“some participants expressed their opinions dominantly and persistently, occasionally pushing issues that were not fully agreed upon but lacked clear objections into the final decisions”*.

Controversial issues and tensions/debates

No conflicts or contradictions were presented during the third Turkish lab; therefore, Turkish FIERCE partners did not report the need to implement conflict resolution mechanisms. To handle power disparities and conflicts, Turkish FIERCE partners designated participants for the work group activities beforehand to bring together complementary expertise and experience and balance age and experience diversity inside the groups.

One of the four respondents of the questionnaire mentioned that in the previous editions of the lab there were some disagreements which were unrelated to the FIERCE workshop, which can be expected considering the existing tensions and polarization in the feminist movement. They clarified that these tensions were not present in the lab’s discussions.

Emotions

The prevailing emotions among the participants were, in general, positive. People expressed happiness to have become part of a process that spanned across time and expressed hope that some of the networks generated here could continue later. They also expressed dissatisfaction that the break periods between sessions could have been longer so that people could get to know one another on a more personal level. Frustration as an emotion was prevalent when people talked about negative experiences with project funding and other international exchanges where they hit bureaucratic brick walls. However, the shared nature of these experiences also transformed them into something almost like an inside joke.

Participants who replied to the questionnaire, specifically valued the first sessions of the labs as the most significant moments of the process:

“The most important moments of the labs were the first sessions, where we came together after a few months to briefly discuss developments and current issues in the field of gender. They were meetings that reinforced empathy and solidarity, and made me feel good.”

“In the first lab, we felt a sense of hope that a common voice for the women’s movement, which had experienced many losses of rights, could be rebuilt. We said, ‘It’s not over; we are here to start again.’”

Establishment of new alliances

The lab did not perceivably generate new alliances, but most likely contributed to resolving some old tensions and enhancing existing links. As mentioned by one of the respondents to the questionnaire, most of the participants had already collaborated in the past as they are part of the feminist movement. It is worth highlighting that one of the participants answering the questionnaire, did mention that their organisation managed to establish new alliances thanks to the lab, gaining access to the UN Headquarters with the possibility for in-person participation in the CSW68 and the High-Level Political Forum activities.

In addition, one participant expressed in the survey that more organisations could have been included from distant parts of the country, especially representing the Kurdish minority, which would have generated new alliances.

Final considerations

Comments on intersectionality

Considering the lab’s composition, of the 4 respondents, 2 self-identified with some intersectional identity: one as having some disability of chronic condition, while one as being an LGBTIQ+ person and

having an ethnic background. All of the respondents mentioned that their organisations follow an intersectional approach; however, did not specify how they address it.

Regarding the lab’s content, it did not address directly intersectionality as part of the theme; however, participants considered that the lab was not diverse enough because it did not include Kurdish feminist representatives; therefore, it was not possible their struggles were not adequately represented in the lab.

In addition, one of the experts’ presentations emphasised the importance of adopting an intersectional strategy for partnerships and advocacy. She highlighted the need for the feminist movement to integrate more effectively with European institutions and to engage beyond the usual equality units and LGBTQIA+ commissions. While radical right movements have not yet established connections with other sectors, feminists have an opportunity to build stronger relationships with areas such as climate, health, education, youth, and research. This approach could facilitate the mainstreaming of gender issues.

Comments on democratic innovations

Turkish FIERCE partners identified the potential output of the lab as a democratic innovation *“because it aims to hold accountable the international bodies from the perspective of civil society organisations. While it is often the case that this relationship is the other way around, the discussions in the labs prove to us that for true participatory democratic practices to be implemented, international governance should pay equal attention to holding itself accountable in terms of the qualitative impact of the support it ostensibly provides”*.

5.9. Transnational lab

The following section is based in the replies of the 10 external participants which replied to the feedback questionnaire during the third transnational lab.

Most of the participants reported having a positive experience during the participation in the co-creation process, valuing the diversity present in the group and the feeling of belonging to a collective with the possibility to trigger a change:

“One particularly memorable experience was engaging in discussions with a diverse array of feminist organisations and collectives. The variety of perspectives on topics such as everyday representation and European elections was incredibly enriching. Witnessing the intersectional approaches used by these groups to tackle complex issues was both inspiring and moving. The collaborative atmosphere fostered a strong sense of solidarity and purpose, evoking positive emotions and a profound sense of belonging.

Another pivotal moment was recognizing the potential for these discussions to drive real change. Observing the passion and dedication of participants committed to revitalizing democracy through feminist principles was both empowering and motivating. This experience reinforced my belief in the importance of our work and filled me with optimism for the future of feminist movements in Europe”.

Another participant mentioned:

“Getting to know the work and challenges organisations of other countries face, made me feel that we are not the only ones, and also motivated me realizing the amount of work that has to be done”.

Regarding the decision-making processes, all of the participants reported having actively participated in the decision-making processes of the lab. Some of them mentioned having contributed in specific sessions of the lab:

“Yes, I took part in the discussions and brainstorming sessions, voted on the outcome - that was important moment. My voice mattered.”

“Yes, I was able to actively participate in the decision-making processes of the lab. My contributions were particularly relevant effective during breakout group discussions, which allowed participants to switch groups at will. This flexibility enabled us to join conversations with a fresh perspective, rather than being constrained by the group's existing train of thought and reasoning; allowing every participant, including myself, to introduce new angles to the topics being discussed.

For example, in a breakout session on Health & Reproductive Rights policy, I was able to introduce a queer perspective by discussing the financial difficulties faced by trans individuals. This insight had not been deeply considered before and added significant value to the conversation, ensuring our policy recommendations were more inclusive and comprehensive.”

The most criticised aspect of the decision-making process by two of the participants —one external and one member of the FIERCE consortium— was the decision process during the first lab which led to the decision of the lab’s outcome —the campaign—:

“The decision process in Brussels was a bit too rapid, did not seem really deliberated. But it is difficult considering time constraints”

“The least [liked aspect inside the labs]: The final circle of voting for the project that would be selected (the EU election campaign) was confusing, not clear.”

There was not an agreement about the power dynamics in the lab: 4 mentioned that some participants were more influential than other in the discussions and the decisions, while 5 mentioned that all participants influenced equally the lab dynamics. The latter attributed the stronger influence of some participants due to their recognised expertise and experience where they were key contributors, as well as the some of them being *“more confident and articulate in their communication tended to dominate discussions. Their ability to express ideas clearly and persuasively allowed them to steer conversations and shape the direction of decisions more effectively.”*

One of the participants mentioned having learnt by other participants’ expertise: *“When we are part of a network, those who have stronger and more comprehensive knowledge at that moment must share it and let it take precedence. This is what happened in FIERCE. I leave with many more tools than I had when I joined.”*

In addition, 9 out of 10 respondents mentioned that the lab allowed to collect different perspectives. Participants also highlighted that the facilitation promoted an equal participation between attendees, assuring that *“discussions remained inclusive and structured (...) To address uneven influence, facilitators could implement more structured methods to ensure all voices are heard, such as using speaking tokens or time-limited contributions to balance participation (strengthening quieter or less experienced voices).”*.

Finally, all of the respondents agreed in not having witnessing any tension or conflict during the lab, as well as in having established collaborative relationships with the other participants.

6. Analysing the FIERCE lab’s outcomes

6.1. Denmark

Current status of the lab’s outcome

On September 5th 2024 the Danish lab’s outcome was implemented with the bystander workshops carried out in the Danish Youth Democracy Festival. The planning of the workshops was done within the

national network, and the implementation at the festival was carried out by ESPD and AAU. The workshop started presenting the FIERCE project and the representatives from ESPD gave a short introduction to sexism from an intersectional perspective and explained the dialogue card game. The card included six different types of responses (as a bystander) to situations of harassment and discrimination. This approach is called the 6 D's: (in Danish) Dan et overblik (Get an overview), Distahér (Distract), Del ansvaret (Share the responsibility), Dokumenter (Document), Del din støtte (share your support), Direkte konfrontation (Direct confrontation). The 6 D's are six different ways to intervene when you observe someone being discriminated.

In the game, you draw a card presenting a dilemma related to intersectional sexism, and you discuss it in the group. Since it was a bystander workshop, ESPD emphasized that even though the dynamics are focused on discussing possible actions as a bystander, the ultimate responsibility always lies with the ones harassing others. They also said that if somebody is not feeling comfortable during the game (due to the issues being discussed), they were welcome to leave the tent (and would be attended by the facilitators).

The first workshop was booked by a 10th grade class (16 girls and 4 boys; all but one ethnic majority). They were divided into four groups for the dialogue card game. In this workshop, the two teachers (one male, one female) joined the different tables and were engaged in the group discussions. Most of the students were engaged in the discussions, and apt at relating the dilemmas to own lived experiences (especially regarding gender), although at each table, one student tended to dominate and take the lead. Some of the groups had longer discussions whereas others were more focused on quickly answering the dilemma and moving on to the next card to get through the deck. Some of the key points of the discussions in the groups related to the limits as to how and when you can interfere: most students felt that it was easier to interfere if you know the aggressor as compared to if it was a stranger; and on social media, they often times would not interfere but just ignore the discriminatory comments. The facilitators posed follow-up questions to the group discussions based on curiosity and being careful not to seem judgmental of the opinions and perspectives of the students. Some of the follow-up questions contained proposals as to what you could do as a bystander. When asked, some of the students said that they liked to discuss these issues but that they do not talk about it usually with friends, etc. (i.e., the dialogue card game gave them an opportunity to do so). A few of the boys seemed quite dismissive in the beginning in terms of participating but one of the ESPD facilitators managed to get them engaged as well. All of the groups started to lose concentration after 30 minutes (the same was the case for the second workshop). At the end of the game, the groups were asked to present some interesting point of their discussions. One of the ESPD facilitators reflected on the examples; he emphasized ‘distract’ as a good strategy, and the need to support the victim rather than being confrontational with the aggressor if that would seem dangerous in the situation. In the debriefing (among the four facilitators), they how this first group was quite young (16 years), and that this was reflected in the discussions and the attention span as well.

The second workshop was booked by a high school (first year; 15 girls and 5 boys; all students were ethnic minority). Again, they were divided into four groups for the dialogue card game. The students were quite active in the game. The three teachers (all male) sat at a separate table, observing the group discussions and commenting on issues related to the game with some of the facilitators but they did not engage directly with the students most of the time. After the workshop the teachers told us that they did not participate in the group discussions on purpose: they found it to be more constructive for the students to have the facilitators engage them in the discussions, and their impression was that it worked, i.e., the students were more engaged, and we managed to avoid major resistance (to participate) from them. The teachers had chosen to book the workshop because they felt that these discussions are very necessary for the young people to have and that especially groups of students from

their particular high school (with a majority of ethnic minority students) could see themselves mirrored in the dilemmas on sexism and racism and as such feel recognized in the challenges that they face in their own lives. In the group discussions, there were a lot of difference of opinions among the students, especially related to gender and sexism. Some students thought that the examples included in the dialogue card game as illustrations of harassing behaviour were appropriate and alright (e.g., condescending remarks to a girl posing in bikini in pictures on Instagram; to this dilemma one of the boys for instance noted that he felt the comments were okay and he added “I am not sexist, I am just realist”). This was particularly the case for the boys but also one of the girls. The students very clearly identified with the questions related to racism: sometimes they were joking when the intersectional dilemma addressed other issues but for racism, it was very clear that at least one in each group would have experienced a similar dilemma (in all of the cases represented on the cards) in their own life. The students had very interesting reflections in the common discussion at the end of the session, emphasizing actions of support as important to good bystander behaviour. Several of the participants said that they did not want to have their picture taken so we do not have any photos from this session. The teachers asked for two decks of cards to use at the high school. In their debriefing, facilitators discussed the role of the male facilitator from ESPD, and how it is quite common for him in these workshop settings that the young boys mention him or side with him in their own comments (e.g., “I would do like [name of the male facilitator]”), as it was also the case in this workshop.

Everyday Sexism Project Denmark continues to do bystander workshops at high schools across the country, using also the dialogue card game with intersectional dilemmas developed as part of the FIERCE Action. It is pending to schedule a meeting to discuss next steps and the possible continuation of the network. Danish FIERCE partners will contact lab participants on January 2025.

The lab’s outcome in the national context and perceptions from lab participants

Danish lab’s outcomes have been focused on awareness-raising rather than influencing policy makers, as well as education and reflection on what sexism from a minority perspective means and how to combat it. As reported by Danish FIERCE partners:

“The complexity of various intersectional manifestations of sexism and their diverse impact on minorities is part of the reason why the primary focus has been on awareness-raising rather than influencing policy makers – that is, there does not seem to be one clear policy proposal that will solve the issue and combat these types of sexism. In this context, even though various policy proposals have been discussed during the labs – such as introducing an intersectional perspective in sexual education and including a registration of whether people are disabled or not in the annual victim studies conducted by the Danish Ministry of Justice – there has not been a clear focus on promoting a specific policy change, or the introduction of new policies, in order to combat this type of sexism”

Danish FIERCE partners reported a tacit agreement between the lab members that if the network was to propose a change in the political system, this should be as concrete as possible in order to optimise timings. Thus, it is not possible to associate the lab’s outcome as agonistic or critical towards institutional politics. In particular, the Danish feminist movement is more reformist and oriented towards collaborations with institutional actors. In particular, the critique to the Danish political system is moderate as publicly expressed by most of the organisations participating in the lab and in private conversations with Danish FIERCE partners.

Despite this, organisations involved in the Danish lab do assume some critical postures related to Danish institutional politics. ESPD is one of the most critical feminist NGOs in Denmark and, since the beginning of their involvement in the FIERCE lab, the mentioned their willingness to maintain an independent voice because they do not receive public funding. Despite this, *“they still primarily focus on influencing rather than antagonizing the political system, and their rhetoric does not include calls for any overturn*

or ‘revolution’ of Danish politics”. In addition, several of the organisations have used and uses condemnatory rhetorics when they deem it necessary.

General feedback by the participants

The following table presents the statistical measures reporting participants satisfaction from 1 to 5 according to the replies of the 4 respondents to the questionnaire. Most of them had a medium high level of satisfaction (with 3 of the 4 respondents valuing their satisfaction with a total of 3 out of 5). Positive aspects valued were finding new inspiration and concrete activities and having achieved the goals proposed as scope since the beginning of the lab.

Lab	Average	Median	Highest value	Lowest value	Standard Deviation
Danish lab	3.5	3	5	3	1.0

Table 7: Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Danish lab

6.2. Greece

Current status of the lab’s outcome

As detailed in section 4.2, since its formation, Greek lab’s participants have self-organised to develop a thematic meeting, with specific thematic presentations which were assigned to the collectives participating in the lab according to their mission, interest and areas of expertise. Thus, discussions around the lab have not been focused on producing a specific political outcome. As a result, and considering the timing, FIERCE Greek partners took the decision to propose the lab members to elaborate a zine collecting the participant experiences inside the lab. As reported: *“We decided that the best way to proceed would be to take upon ourselves the design and the production of the ‘lab’s outcome’ and to invite other members to contribute according to their availability. We would put forward our proposal and would consult with other participants during the third lab. Once a consensus had been reached, we would ask them to provide their inputs in the ways and at the time agreed.*

So, our proposal, put together by the two new AUTH researchers and presented to other lab members on the second day of the third lab, at the last session (1500-1530pm) was to invite every participating group to send us 3-4 pictures (photos, drawings, even lyrics, mottos, slogans and hashtag) whose content would express personal experiences from their participation in their collective and/or their interaction in the workshop. This idea was reinforced by the fact that a member of the Rainbow School who participated in the third lab kept drawing figures on a paper during the lab. This provided the occasion for us to ask all participants to share their experience in whichever figurative form they prefer.”

In this proposal AUTH will digitalize the materials sent with the aim to *“highlight their personal experience, aesthetics and discourse”*. This outcome would be diffused online on social media. By the end of 2024, FIERCE Greek partners reported that only one of the participants had sent some materials for the elaboration of the zine, while other mentioned they would do so before the end of the year.

As a next step, Karditsa Women’s Center proposed to the AUTH research team to organize an event in their home town to present the broader outcomes of the three labs. It is worth highlighting that, for the elaboration and implementation of the zine, FIERCE Greek partners have not applied to the FIERCE actions call.

The lab’s outcome in the national context and perceptions from lab participants

According to the three respondents who replied to the feedback questionnaire, when asked whether the lab could potentially have a positive impact on feminist activism and/or fostering policy change, the three of them had positive expectations. It is worth highlighting that none of them made an explicit reference about the zine and were referring to the content developed for the thematic presentations

of the co-created agenda as the lab’s outcomes. One of the activists mentioned that this is valuable documentation for the feminist movement, while other mentioned about their participation in the process:

“I truly believe the lab’s outcomes could have a meaningful impact on feminist activism and policy change. Seeing other passionate activists and hearing their success stories was incredibly empowering. The shared commitment and enthusiasm in our discussions made it clear that our collective efforts can drive real progress. Witnessing the dedication of fellow participants and knowing that our collaborative work has the potential to spark change was deeply motivating. It felt like we were all part of something bigger than ourselves, and that sense of solidarity and shared purpose was profoundly inspiring.”

Since the lab’s political or policy-oriented outcome was not the central focus of the lab itself, there was not specific inputs regarding the potential impact of the zine in the Greek context. Despite this, considering the lab’s broader outcomes —the thematic presentations—, all content developed was closely related to the Greek political context, as well as the rise of the anti-gender and antifeminist movements; therefore, it could potentially have a positive impact in democracy if diffused and discussed with a broader group of actors.

General feedback by the participants

The following table presents the statistical measures reporting participants satisfaction from 1 to 10 according to the replies of the 3 respondents to the questionnaire. The most valued aspects mentioned were establishing new alliances, as well as having periodic meetings spread out throughout the year: *“This extended timeline allowed us to let our ideas develop and mature more fully. It was rewarding to see our concepts evolve and gain depth, and having time to reflect and revisit discussions helped strengthen our final outcomes.”* On the other hand, the least liked features of the lab were the difficult in turning the discussions into “actionable outcomes”: *“At times, the sheer volume of issues and differing opinions made it challenging to reach consensus and finalize decisions”*.

Lab	Average	Median	Highest value	Lowest value	Standard Deviation
Greek lab	7.0	7.0	8.0	6.0	1.0

Table 8: Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Greek lab

6.3. France

Current status of the lab’s outcome

At the time when the third lab’s report was presented, the implementation of the lab’s outcome was temporarily on hold due to internal changes in the composition of the French FIERCE partners team. Thus, it was reported that developments would depend directly on the decision on how to proceed with the application and implementation of the FIERCE action according to the decision of the four considered options during the third lab.

The lab’s outcome in the national context and perceptions from lab participants

The French lab is mainly following an agonistic approach towards French institutions, since French authorities are not seriously addressing the actions of anti-gender actors and the lab’s outcome is focused in raising awareness in this issue. Furthermore, the desire to organize as an informal and autonomous network stems from a critique of feminist networks benefiting from state funding (such as the Foundation des Femmes), which cannot afford to adopt a critical stance toward the government. Nonetheless, it appears that the lab’s actions still aim to bridge the gap between institutions and feminists, as the participants’ goal is to secure resources and elicit a state response to anti-gender groups.

As detailed in section 2, all of the feminist collectives and organisations that are part of the FIERCE lab usually are in contact with public institutions since they advocate for a rights-based approach that requires constant dialogue. In this sense, the outcome seeks to have an impact in institutional policy decisions.

Lab participants seemed to have developed a sense of ownership towards the lab’s outcome, as they have validated the platform at various stages of its creation and all collectives have agreed to attach their logos to it and contribute in their name to a large-scale dissemination event.

Considering the 5 answers collected in the questionnaire to lab participant’s, all of them confirmed the perception that the outcome can generate a positive impact. In particular, three of the respondents valued mainly the creation of the network of actors and the establishment of a coalition, creating new alliances and collective intelligence. One respondent mentioned the potential to escalate the network in order to have a policy impact and another one mentioned the need to include other collectives to represent minorities, such as racialized people, in order to increase its impact.

General feedback by the participants

The following table reports the level of satisfaction expressed by the 5 French participants who replied the questionnaire sent to lab attendees. As evidenced, the level of satisfaction is considerably high, with an average level of 8.2, while more than 50% of the respondents valued their satisfaction with a level of 8 or higher out of 10.

Lab	Average	Median	Highest value	Lowest value	Standard Deviation
French lab	8.2	8	10	7	1.10

Table 9: Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – French lab

The most valued aspects of the lab where the collaborative work, the establishment of new alliances and “for defining a common vocabulary, shared values, strategy and objectives”. On the other hand, as aspect of improvement, the diversity and inclusivity were identified: one participant mentioned in the questionnaire “I regret that there were few racialized groups, and this is common in our organisations, so we have to work on that”. Facilitators were valued positively, as following a well-defined not interventionist approach. It was mentioned that it could be better to use more time to discuss about strategies and have more focused discussions on concrete actions.

6.4. Italy

Current status of the lab’s outcome

The Italian FIERCE lab’s outcome is a self-defence manual for teachers implementing EAD, understood in the Italian context as education on gender+ inequalities, encompassing awareness-raising on sexism and homo-transphobia. This process began on 29 June 2023 with the first lab session, which identified the challenges related to implementing education to differences in schools. A first proposal for the table of contents was presented on 16 October in an online meeting by FIERCE partners, following a review of similar manuals and bibliographic materials with a similar scope. The revised table of contents, which served as the starting point for planning the second and third meetings of the Italian lab, is presented in section 4.4. Both sessions were dedicated to the co-writing of the self-defence manual.

In particular, the second lab focused on identifying situations and self-defence strategies that teachers implementing EAD might face (chapters 3 and 4 of the manual), while the third lab developed the content for the remaining three chapters. All the manual’s content was developed during the three Italian lab sessions and is currently being copyedited by Chayn, a transfeminist collective combating GBV through collaborative practices and digital tools.

The stylistic editing process is being carried out as part of the FIERCE actions (T4.4) and began in late August 2024. Between September and October, coordination meetings were held between Chayn and the Italian FIERCE partners. Chayn is using summary reports from the lab sessions as the primary input for the manual's copyediting. It was agreed that specific meetings with lab participants could be organised to address questions or resolve any doubts or gaps identified in the reports.

On 27 November 27th, a meeting was held with Rete Lenford, an association for social promotion (non-profit organisation) involved in the Italian lab, which works to defend the rights of LGBTQ+ people. The purpose of this meeting was to address gaps in the report and ensure the manual's accuracy. Following this meeting, a draft will be shared with lab participants to collect their feedback and finalise the writing and edition of the manual.

The lab's outcome in the national context and perceptions from lab participants

A self-defence manual in an adverse context to implement EAD

In Italy, education is one of the fields that has been most affected by the actions of the anti-gender groups, which allege that gender ideology is “corrupting” children’s gender identity and sexual orientation. As a consequence, mistrust and disinformation is created, diversity education projects in schools are blocked and teachers are receiving attacks.

The elected far right-wing government elected in 2022 are conducting a series of policy measures with an anti-gender background —such as the revocation of the registration of same-sex couples from municipal registries— and anti-gender discourses are spreading in the cultural climate. This affects teachers, who “are confronted with material situations of discomfort and discrimination”. In addition, media attacks are becoming more common and implementing projects on gender education in schools has become more difficult or emptied from its political implications —proposing partial and incomplete content by patriarchal actors—.

Sex education initiatives in Italian schools remain limited, with significant disparities in geographical distribution and the level of education. A 2022 study analysing the policy frameworks of sex education across Italy’s 22 regions identified 34 frameworks published between 2016 and 2022. Of these, 53% were concentrated in northern Italy, while two regions—Sicily and Marche—had no frameworks at all (Chinelli et al., 2023). The study also included a survey sent to 831 entities, including institutions (primarily local health departments) and civil-society organisations. The survey revealed 232 initiatives during the study period—219 in secondary schools and 13 in primary schools. Most initiatives were concentrated in central (42.9%) and northern (39.7%) Italy, with 65% promoted by civil-society organisations (Chinelli et al., 2023).

Education to Differences (EAD) became a prominent topic on the political agenda during the second half of 2023 due to a series of GBV incidents that shocked the country. After two group rapes involving minors in Palermo and Caivano, the Minister of Education and Merit, Giuseppe Valditara, announced plans to develop a framework on “education on relationships.” In November 2023, the femicide of Giulia Cecchettin, a young university student, triggered massive protests across the country and prompted political debates about education to differences. At the time, the guidelines had yet to be published.

Two normative documents were subsequently issued by the government. The first was a memorandum of understanding ([protocollo di intesa](#)) "Prevention and combatting of male violence against women and domestic violence – initiatives aimed at the education sector" signed by three ministries (Culture; Education and Merit; and Family, Birth Rate and Equal Opportunities). In addition, two weeks after this femicide, on November 24th 2023, the Ministry of Education and Merit published [the Directive No. 83](#)

of 24 November 2023 concerning project pathways for schools on the topic of “Education on Relationships”.

These guidelines, applicable to all school levels (primary and secondary education), proposed projects, educational pathways, and activities aimed at promoting “a culture of respect, education on relationships, and combating male violence against women.” However, the guidelines are not mandatory, leaving individual schools to decide whether to implement them, with at least one teacher serving as the referent. Fifteen million euros were allocated for these initiatives. Although the directive does not specify the duration of the activities, Minister Valditara publicly stated that they would consist of 30 hours per academic year.

These guidelines faced severe criticism from actors within the feminist movement. *Non Una di Meno*, the largest Italian transfeminist movement, published a manifesto titled “*We Will Burn Valditara’s Guidelines*” ([Bruceremo le linee guida di Valditara](#)) on 25 November. Among the critiques, the optional nature of Education to Differences (EAD) was highlighted, as its implementation is limited to extracurricular hours across 12 sessions (a total of 30 hours). Furthermore, the initial technical adviser responsible for drafting these guidelines is a known anti-gender actor who has previously made controversial statements about “the evilness of women” in the context of gender-based violence.

[Other critiques](#) focus on the pedagogical components of the directive, emphasising its partiality. It only references activities for secondary education and mandates that these activities must be controlled and approved by parents' associations. Additionally, the implementation of these activities relies entirely on the goodwill of teachers, who would need to take on these additional responsibilities alongside their regular duties.

In December 2023, Valditara appointed three guarantors for the process—a lawyer, a nun, and a former politician and feminist activist. However, following criticism from right-wing parties in Parliament, the Minister [dissolved this group](#) and announced that the process would continue without guarantors.

Beyond the critiques of the intervention's optional and extracurricular nature, as well as the limited hours, several technical obstacles have severely hindered the progress of these guidelines one year after their publication. Notably, the National Forum of School Parents' Associations (ANPE) and the National Institute for Documentation, Innovation and Educational Research (INDIRE), which are integral to the implementation of the guidelines, [have not been involved by December 2024](#).

Meanwhile, civil society initiatives in 2024 have sought to address these gaps. The Order of Psychologists of Lazio, in collaboration with the Provincial Order of Physicians, Surgeons and Dentists of Rome, and academic institutions, published [guidelines “Sexual and affective education in primary and secondary schools”](#). In addition, the Working Group on the Convention on the Rights of the Child — Gruppo di Lavoro per la Convenzione sui Diritti dell’Infanzia e dell’Adolescenza ([Gruppo CRC](#))—published a policy statement on [“Education on affectivity and sexuality: why it is important to introduce Comprehensive Sexuality Education in Italian schools”](#) requesting to the Parliament for the development on a law on comprehensive sex education. There have been [denounces](#) from parents about a catholic-based sex and affective education course which was against the use of contraceptives.

During the third Italian lab, there was a consensus on the deteriorating conditions for implementing EAD in 2024. In June, Rossano Sasso a parliamentarian from the far-right Lega party, presented the [Resolution 7-00203](#), “Adoption of guidelines to promote respect for differences in the school system”. Some members of the Italian lab, including the Educare Alle Differenze Network were invited to a hearing by the Commission VII Culture, Science and Education of the Chamber of Deputies to discuss

this resolution. The resolution, aimed to eliminate “gender ideology” from schools and was approved with declarations by Sasso, mentioning that neutrality needs to be guaranteed, eliminating the influence of “self-declared experts” from the LGBTIQ+ community.

The Educare alle Differenze Network have [openly manifested](#) their rejection to the way the Italian government is managing EAD. They have also [published](#) communications against the Sasso’s resolution, as well as other feminist and LGBTIQ+ collectives such as [Tocca a Noi and Arci Gay](#). The opposition has also arrived from the largest Italian [unions](#), the [National Association of School Principals](#) (Associazione Nazionale Dirigenti Scolastici) and other [civil-society organisations](#).

The last scandal of the government publicly spreading anti-gender messages have been last November 2024. The father of Giulia Cecchettin, victim of the aforementioned femicide, [presented](#) on November 18th a foundation dedicated to her daughter, dedicated to finance dedicated to implement EAD in schools. Minister Valditara [remarked](#) criticising the fight against patriarchy as ideological and linking GBV to illegal immigration. These comments sparked protests during demonstrations on 25 November, led by feminist groups.

On December 4th 2024, Minister Valditara and Gino Cecchetin had a [meeting](#), where they agreed to establish a protocol and a common agenda to bring EAD to schools together with the Cecchetin Foundation.

Perceptions and expectations of participants

The definition of the self-defence manual for teachers on education to differences as the Italian lab’s outcome has been an attempt to contribute to the feminist agenda and the fight against the aforementioned problems. Indeed, the manual has the potentiality to increase the visibility of the anti-gender attacks on education and to provide teachers with practical tools for their self-defence while challenging gender stereotypes and inequalities. In addition, the manual aims to contribute to the dissemination of the already created knowledge and contribute to the networks of collectives working in EAD.

Most of the collectives of belonging of the lab’s participants usually collaborate to some degree with Italian public institutions, which can be expected since education to differences is implemented in public schools. Despite this, since the current Italian government is conservative and doing a series of measures to limit or restrict EAD, the self-defence manual can be understood rather as an agonistic initiative. Indeed, in several parts of the manual, the Ministry of Education and Merit has been identified as one of the actors causing the attacks and obstacles to the implementation of EAD. It is worth considering that this approach could potentially shift towards more open collaborations with the public institutions in case of a shift in the political positioning of the government and the practical guideline developed related.

Although the production of the manual is still in progress and it has not been disseminated yet, there seems to be a high level of expectation towards the lab’s outcome by the lab participants. According to the results of the survey, all 12 respondents replied positively to the question inquiring on the potential impact of the lab’s outcome in the feminist activism or to generate a political shift. Approximately half of them mentioned that, for this, it would be important to also develop a diffusion strategy, considering the promotion in the networks of the organisations participating in the lab. One participant mentioned that political changes require time; thus, that the manual will probably have more impact among the feminist activism. Another participant highlights the value of the manual in itself because it could help fighting loneliness and creating a community that resists.

Despite this, it is early to know the level of appropriation with the self-defence manual because, we have not yet asked the organisations belonging to the lab whether they want to appear as contributors to the content developed.

FIERCE Italian partners has been informed that the Educare alle Differenze Network is implementing a related initiative, process started on September 2024 in their annual meeting. On Saturday December 7th, an online self-defence [workshop](#) for teachers was organised, with three working tables on (i) ethical code of conduct in schools, (ii) internal relationships in the school and (iii) relationships between teacher and external subjects. The aim of this process is to build a vademecum focused in the self-defence of teachers. It is still to be analysed whether there will be possible overlaps between the two initiatives. It is worth noting that Italian FIERCE partners are in contact with this network and they have already agreed to provide feedback to the manual’s draft.

General feedback by the participants

The following table reports the statistical measures of the level of satisfaction reported by respondents to the questionnaire (valued from 1, as the lowest to 10, as the highest level). As evidenced in the table, the level of satisfaction is considerable high, with an average level of satisfaction of 8, while more than 50% of the respondents valuing their satisfaction with a level of 9 out of 10.

Lab	Average	Median	Highest value	Lowest value	Standard Deviation
Italian lab	8.17	9	10	4	2.12

Table 10: Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Italian lab

The most valued aspects of the process identified by participants were: the exchange between participants with experience in the field, “interactive and diverse methods in each lab”, “the sharing”, “creating a network with diverse feminist perspectives working in diverse contexts”. One participant mentioned: “I enjoyed the entire process. It was well-structured and had the effect of stimulating reflections from a new perspective compared to what we usually do with the association”.

On the other hand, time-management was the most common aspect of improvement by the participants (4 out of 12 respondents). In addition, 2 other participants mentioned that it could have been worth involving more stakeholders and creating a collective with defined appointments.

Most of the participants gave a positive evaluation to the facilitators, mentioning that the sessions were well managed, being able to put together and synthetise diverse contents and positions. One participant also valued positively the organisation of the sessions and the hearing capacity. Some respondents highlighted the need to improve the time-management and one of the participants mentioned that one of the facilitators was “not welcoming in their posture”. It is worth mentioning that this answer was giving by the participant valuing the experience with the lowest classification and belonged to the organisation of one of the persons manifesting their discomfort during the tense situations previous described.

6.5. Poland

Current status of the lab’s outcome

The campaign has not been implemented yet and the graphic material is being prepared by a graphic designer under the coordination of the UG, the Polish FIERCE partner. They presented the application to the FIERCE actions call mentioning that the campaign’s goal is “to provide information on the gender-specific labour rights and the ways to secure them. Apart from the information strictly connected to the labour code, the action will also include information on and the ways how to combat more 'soft' forms of gender-based discrimination at the workplace”.

The lab’s outcome in the national context and perceptions from lab participants

During the FIERCE Polish lab, emerged the urgency for a campaign focused on labour rights. This was indeed identified as a gap within the Polish feminist activism: *“This gap is especially crucial when analysing the reasons for electoral victories of Law and Justice Party, who have put a lot of emphasis on social issues and labour related issues. Up to this time feminist organisations have not explored this area in depth (although of course it was not ignored by them), and creating a campaign that would inform the public about gender-specific labour rights and work-related issues would be much needed. This campaign would also allow for a more gender-sensitive discussions around the topic, should more mainstream media outlets pick on this campaign. According to lab’s participants, they felt that this is the very topic that is missing from the public space and that would be the input of the lab itself.”}*

The campaign will be bilingual to be inclusive with the growing number of migrant workers —mostly Ukrainian—; thus, the campaign will be presented in Polish, Ukrainian and English simultaneously.

General feedback by the participants

Only one Polish participant filled the feedback questionnaire; therefore, it is not possible to calculate the statistical measures of the general level of satisfaction indicated. This person rated 9 out of 10 their level of satisfaction and gave the following comment regarding the lab co-creation process: *“Unfortunately, we lost many participants from Meeting one through Meeting three. It would have been great to preserve the diverse group that was there at the beginning. This is by no means a fault of the facilitators”.*

As detailed in section 5.5, there was a significant number of dropouts in the lab, due to the less time availability of some of the lab participants, mainly the most known and publicly recognisable activists and some who did not have time for activism because of changes in their personal lives, such as getting married and starting new works.

6.6. Slovenia

Current status of the lab’s outcome

The exhibition "Reproductive Rights: On Health, Sexuality, and Equality of Women" was implemented between May 7th and 20th 2024.

The lab’s outcome in the national context and perceptions from lab participants

During the exhibition, there was a convergence of theme-related activities and initiatives organised within the Slovenian feminist movement:

- A campaign by the Women’s Lobby of Slovenia for the European elections, focused on critical issues, such as ensuring parity democracy, equal representation, decent work for all, eradicating violence against women and girls, implementing sexual and reproductive rights, including women's voices in peace-building, and empowering women in green and digital transformation. The also published an exhibition on reproductive rights on their website.
- The “My Voice, My Choice” campaign by the Institute March 8.
- The FAMA conference hold in May 17-19.

That allowed gaining a significant media coverage in mainstream media such as the Slovene Press Agency, Mladina, Dnevnik, Nedelo and Delo. These articles addressed some of the aforementioned initiatives jointly, being mostly focused on four of the thematic axes of the exhibition, giving less attention to violence in reproductive health.

General feedback by the participants

Statistical measures related to participant’s satisfaction are reported in the following table, collected by the four replies to the questionnaire. The average level of satisfaction of the three participants belonging to the ore group that replied to the feedback questionnaire was of 9.

Lab	Average	Median	Highest value	Lowest value	Standard Deviation
Slovenian lab	9	9	10	8	1.0

Table 11: Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Slovenian lab

The most valued aspects by respondents of the questionnaire were the exchanges of views and experiences, the process of collaboration and the promotion of the exhibition. Regarding aspects of improvement, respondents mentioned that the agendas were packed and the promotion of the exhibition. One of the participants mentioned that she would have liked to receive a better economic compensation for her involvement: *“Better payment, especially for the team members who are not regularly employed in academic institutions”*.

6.7. Spain

Current status of the lab’s outcome

The Spanish lab’s outcome is a network for care (*Red por los cuidados*), which had been decided by participants during the second in-presence meeting of the lab. A process of downscaling of the action has taken place after the third lab, after realising the level of involvement and commitment for its implementation was lower than it had been previously foreseen. In particular, during the third lab there was a sharp decrease in the participation, reducing external participation to half of the original attendees to the lab.

This third and last session was focused in defining the operational steps to implement the network for care that had been collectively decided during the previous encounter. In particular, as next steps it had been decided to design a logo, start a Twitter/X account, an email address and an online repository, as well as to establish regular online meetings. It was also decided to apply to the FIERCE call for actions’ budget to organise an in-presence launching event of the network. During the application process to the FIERCE call for actions, a detailed Gantt chart with milestones had been planned to launch the network on January 2025.

During the third lab’s meeting, there was a session dedicated to discuss about the related challenges to implement the network. It emerged that consensus on the action had not been fully achieved and one of the participants shared a past negative and time-consuming experience of formal network-building among collectives of household and care workers. Spanish FIERCE partners reported that in discussions centred on the sustainability of the network and that that it was decided to focus on short-terms tasks and concrete steps to move forward.

After having applied to the FIERCE actions call, during autumn 2024 there were several difficulties for the implementation of the action which led to the need reassess the lab’s outcome approach and expectations. The first online to organise the launching event of the network for care was organised for early November 2024. It had been planned to outline the next steps for the launch of the event and one of the organisations expressed interest in presenting the work of their organisation (Single Mothers by Choice).

Participation to the meeting was lower than expected with 5 participants joining including two of the FIERCE Spanish partners. As a result of this meeting, it was decided to rethink the project’s outcome: *“Despite reminders, scheduling challenges remained, and attendance at the meeting was lower than anticipated, with only five participants joining (including the Fierce team, Inés and Elin). One additional*

participant expressed strong interest in attending future meetings, while another, who had previously confirmed attendance, was ultimately unable to join. Recognizing that active participation requires ongoing commitment, and observing the low turnout, we decided during the meeting to contact all participants and ask them to confirm their interest, availability, and capacity to engage with this initiative and form part of the network moving forward. The responses we received made it clear that there was insufficient support to establish the network as originally envisioned. While many participants did not respond at all, others shared that they lacked the time and energy to engage at this moment. None of the responses communicated negative views about the network itself.” As a consequence, they had decided to redirect the financial resources secured through the FIERCE actions to a more efficient action.

Spanish FIERCE partners had decided to follow a scaled-back approach with the core group that is continuously participating, which includes *“individuals working in feminist approaches to family care, new forms of families and childcare, feminist advocacy for household and care workers, and feminist academics doing research on care.”*. Their proposal is to continue organising online meetings to keep updated on specific campaigns, events and collaborations, as well as explore possibilities of future collaboration. In addition, Spanish FIERCE partners are planning to create a podcast in collaboration with the core group combining the dissemination of FIERCE research and interventions by feminist care activists. If the collaboration with the core group works well, they will rethink about the possibility of relaunching the care network in the upcoming months.

The lab’s outcome in the national context and perceptions from lab participants

The proposal to implement the care network as the lab’s outcome is aligned with the Spanish feminist movement’s priorities, after care has been one of the central topics of their activism since the feminist strikes of March 8th 2018 and 2019. This is aligned with the left-wing coalition government; therefore, the network aims to leverage the current political opportunity, contributing the critical and sustained debates on care.

The network has defined the following specific objectives:

- 1) Establishing a platform for dialogue and action on the universal right to care.
- 2) Facilitating connectivity by sharing information, activities, and strategies among network participants.
- 3) Acting as a tool for political advocacy to influence public policies.
- 4) Raising awareness of the crucial role care plays in the socio-economic system.

The approach proposed was addressing care through intersectional feminist lens, integrating the perspective of caregivers and care recipients while considering the intersections of migration, ageing, and LGBTBIQ+ rights. In line with these objectives a diverse group of participants and associations were invited to the sessions.

Regarding the influence in the institutional politics, this network has been built following a critical approach towards institutional policies/politics; however, it is not antagonistic due to the current political context: *“The lab’s dynamic reinforced the idea that care can be a strategic topic for advancing feminist policies in the current context of political conflicts, polarisation, and the rise of extreme right and anti-feminist movements. A key objective is to engage in policy debates surrounding care, sharing and proposing tools for political advocacy to influence public policies. The Fierce interview report highlights that feminist activists and politicians are pessimistic about the future, particularly in light of the rise of anti-feminist and anti-gender movements. This context has tempered expectations regarding the impact of feminist advocacy within institutional democratic spaces and policymaking. Nonetheless,*

lab participants have identified a political opportunity to advance feminist agendas in care policies, given the presence of a left-wing coalition government.”

General feedback by the participants

Statistical measures related to participant’s satisfaction are reported in the following table, collected by the eight replies to the questionnaire. The average level of satisfaction was of 8, with a minimum value of 6 and a maximum of 9 out of 10.

Lab	Average	Median	Highest value	Lowest value	Standard Deviation
Spanish lab	7.9	8.0	9.0	6.0	1.0

Table 12: Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Spanish lab

In the questionnaire, there is a general agreement between the participants that the most valued aspect was the high diversity of the lab, including diverse people and collectives from different territories in Spain, sectors working in care. Considering one of the participant’s opinions expressed in the feedback questionnaire: *“(the best thing was) the opportunity to meet people from different parts of the country, from different fields, to talk and reflect on care was undoubtedly the best thing. The worst thing was that in each meeting there were fewer of us”*.

Despite this, one of the respondents also emphasised that this high diversity might have been challenging to concretise the lab’s outcome. In addition, around half of the participants agreed that the most significant aspect of improvement was the continuity in the participation of the group. Considering one of the participant’s respondents to the questionnaire: *“Discontinuities in the participants generated moments where some previously defined consensuses were reopened for debate, generating a feeling of not making enough progress”*. Spanish FIERCE partners recognised these sustainability challenges, agreeing that the network will build on existing efforts and activism, creating synergies among participants and amplifying current efforts.

The following quote reflects the general feeling of the participants: *“(In the third lab) I was a bit disappointed to see that there was less involvement than expected, but also happy because I believe that just sharing information and contacts and having a space for debate can be very useful and enriching and I still hope to build something important together”*.

6.8. Turkey

Current status of the lab’s outcome

The Turkish lab’s outcome is a policy brief articulating the problems feminist civil society associations experience in their relations with Europe-wide international institutions. The third lab meeting was a hands-on workshop dedicated to develop the content of the policy brief, with dedicated sessions about the functioning of EU institutions, the mechanisms to currently active to support feminist civil society advocacy and proposals to strengthen feminist civil society’s capacity to hold public institutions accountable.

During the lab, Turkish FIERCE partners asked the participants about their willingness to actively participate in the writing process of the policy brief after the lab. They collected the names of the interested participants, among which the three members of the core group. These participants applied to the financing of the FIERCE actions for its improvement and dissemination.

The lab’s outcome in the national context and perceptions from lab participants

The lab’s outcome adopts an agonistic approach, proposing several possible improvements through constructive criticism: *“The potential outcome, on the one hand, has delineated very carefully the good practices of support to civil society organisations coming from international governance. In this manner,*

the grounds for constructive criticism were established. However, a good section of the discussions, as per the goals of the policy brief, focused on what to improve and how to do so to enhance participation, inclusiveness, and effective advocacy. This entailed detailing what did not work and how it could be made to work”.

Participants expressed their willingness for the final outcome to be disseminated among feminist networks. Turkish FIERCE partners noted that participants hoped this could strengthen collaborations in international advocacy and increase grassroots organisations' knowledge of international bodies.

General feedback by the participants

Statistical measures related to participant’s satisfaction are reported in the following table, collected by the four replies to the questionnaire. The average level of satisfaction was of 7.5, with most of the participants rating it with 7 out of 10 (3 of 4 respondents).

Lab	Average	Median	Highest value	Lowest value	Standard Deviation
Turkish lab	7.5	7.0	9.0	7.0	1.0

Table 13: Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Turkish lab

The most valued aspects by respondents of the questionnaire were the collaborative work. In addition, partners identified that *“participants extended their thanks for an engaging workshop with clear goals and time management. They also appreciated that the project team flexibly adapted the program, in response to the needs and preferences of those involved”*. Aspects of improvement identified by participants were the inclusion of more variegated groups inside the feminist movement, in particular Kurdish feminism and the time allocated for the discussions —one participant in the questionnaire suggested that it would have been positive to have the lab organised in two days—.

6.9. Transnational lab: Results of the FIERCE campaign

The “Five FIERCE claims for a Feminist Europe”⁶ campaign was the outcome of the transnational lab. This political action was decided as the result of a deliberative process which took place during the first transnational lab in Brussels on September 19th 2023, among other 10 options that were evaluated. A final decision was not made during the in-presence meeting of the lab; thus, the final decision was made after an online voting process.

During the second transnational lab, held in Madrid on February 7th and 8th, all the content of the campaign was developed. Proposing five main claims, which were then elaborated as part of the FIERCE charter. Following, the main claims of the campaign are detailed:

1. A Recognised European Feminist Network to Stop the Antifeminist and Anti-Gender Movement
 - 1.1 Redirect the funding to secure sustainable and transparent feminist networking
 - 1.2 Confront online democracy threats such as disinformation and hate speech
 - 1.3 Words Matter: "Words shape worlds."
2. Social, Economic and Reproductive Justice
 - 2.1 Achieve reproductive justice NOW
 - 2.2 Dignify and recognise care work as the cornerstone of life
 - 2.3 Decent work for all: Decent conditions! Decent opportunities! Decent legislation!
3. Fighting Against SGBV (Sexual and Gender-Based Violence)
 - 3.1 Implement and improve the EU directive on violence against women (VAW) and visualise

⁶ The campaign’s webpage can be accessed at the following link: <https://campaign.fierce-project.eu/>.

the bigger picture - institutional violence that creates structural discrimination

3.2 Comprehensive Sex Education (CSE) for all young people in Europe: An informed and empowered generation

4. Protect LGBTIQ+ Rights

4.1 Legal protection of LGBTIQ+ rights

4.2 Integrate LGBTIQ+ rights into foreign policies

5. Global Development, Peace and Feminist Foreign Policy

5.1 Adjusting the EU's soft power to build a global institutional framework for peace, development, and sustainability by appealing to its core values, policies, and institutions

5.2 Ceasefire everywhere NOW!

5.3 Climate, justice and economic governance

On March 2024, an open call was launched to select the communication team which would support the implementation of the campaign. This team worked in the refinement of the content elaborated in the Madrid meeting to prepare a manifesto which would be sent to the MEPs as a charter to be signed declaring their support to the campaign. On April 26th an online launching event was organised where members of the feminist movement and candidates participated. The active campaigning period lasted until June 4th with the pre-electoral event.

The campaign had three main strands:

- Strand 1: Signing the FIERCE charter, targeting candidates to the EP 2024 elections.
- Strand 2: “Partnering the campaign”: open invitation to feminist collectives from and beyond the lab were invited to sign the campaign as partners.
- Strand 3: Campaigning in social media and newsletter publications and advertisement: the target population were general voters.

Results of Strand 1

Of over 650 candidates that were contacted 70 supported the campaign of the following countries: Belgium (7), Czech Republic (1), Denmark (8), Spain (2), Finland (3), France (24), Greece (3), Italy (11), Luxembourg (1), Netherlands (1) and Slovenia (9). Of them, 14 were successfully elected to the EP and one became a member of the FEMM Committee, as presented in the following table:

	Name	Country	National party	Group in the EUP
1	Per Clausen	Denmark	Enhedlisten - De Rod-Gronne	GUE
2	Li Andersson	Finland	Vasemmistoliitto	GUE
3	Madjouline Sbai	France	EELV	Greens/EFA
4	Mounir Satouri	France	EELV	Greens/EFA
5	Melissa Camara	France	EELV	Greens/EFA
6	David Cormand	France	EELV	Greens/EFA
7	Marie Toussaint	France	EELV	Greens/EFA
8	Raphael Glucksmann	France	Place Publique	S&D
9	Aurore Lalucq	France	Place Publique	S&D
10	Aodhan O Riordain	Ireland	Labour Party	S&D
11	Marc Angel	Luxembourg	Letzebuenger Sozialistesche Aarbechterpartei	S&D
12	Kim Van Sparrentak	Netherlands	GroenLinks	Greens/EFA
13	Vladimir Prebilic	Slovenia	Vesna	Greens/EFA
14	Matjaz Nemeč	Slovenia	Socialni Demokrati	S&D

Table 14: Elected MEPs signing the FIERCE charter

Results of Strand 2

15 feminist collectives and organisations signed the campaign as partners:

- WIDE+ (EU level)
- Gender Five Plus (EU level)
- ERRC (EU level)
- IPAS (EU level)
- Women’s Lobby of Slovenia
- Hands Away (France)
- SOS Homophobie (France)
- Acufade (Spain)
- Amrita (Hungary)
- European Women’s Lobby – Bulgarian Platform (Bulgary)
- European Women’s Lobby – Turkish coordination (Turkey)
- Love My Way (Italy)
- Indici Paritari (Italy)
- Rainbow School (Greece)
- International Women* Space - IW*S (Germany)

Results of Strand 3

Posting in social media was largely challenged by the Meta security policy for the EP elections, which was considerably limiting the diffusion of political content in advertised posts. This had to be done by one verified user physically located in the countries of the publications. This was not viable by the communications team (composed of three people located in Modalvia). Therefore, the only social media where it was possible to implement paid posts was LinkedIn. Three posts from feminist influencers were published, as well as advertisements in two political magazines (El Salto and Politico) and a newsletter article in the Italian magazine Rivista InGenere.

General feedback by participants

The following table reports the statistical measures of the general level of satisfaction declared by the 10 external participants who replied to the feedback questionnaire of the transnational lab.

Lab	Average	Median	Highest value	Lowest value	Standard Deviation
Transnational lab	8.3	8.0	10.0	6.0	1.3

Table 15: Statistical measures about participant’s satisfaction – Transnational lab

The most valuable aspects were meeting participants with different perspectives from different countries and feminist realities. One participant highlighted that each lab was concrete and managed to identify *“concreate and doable outcomes as conclusion of the strategy discussions”*.

On the other hand, some aspects to be improved that were identified were the decision process on the campaign — *“The final circle of voting for the project that would be selected (the EU election campaign) was confusing, not clear.”*— and the recurrent communication — *“Too many e-mails. I would have preferred fewer, shorter information. But on the other hand the messages and information provided was useful and fulfilling.”*—. One participant also mentioned that sessions could have been more interactive instead of organising long meetings.

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8. Annex N° 1: Template to report the third lab meetings and questionnaire

Following, the updated guidelines elaborated to collect more in-depth analytical information about the third lab sessions are presented. The updated analytical dimensions included in this report are detailed in section 3. In addition, the feedback questionnaire elaborated and sent to the lab’s participants is available at the following [link](#).

1. Preparing the third Lab’s meeting

Detail the preparation process of the second lab’s meeting:

- Involvement of the core group (if any) and lab’s participants: communication channels used and feedback mechanisms implemented: brief description of communication/exchanges in between the two Labs meetings.
- In case of organisation/preparation meetings with lab’s participants or the core group, detail each meeting’s agenda, the discussions that took place and the main agreements.
- In case of the Greek lab, please detail the methodology to define the lab’s outcome.
- Detail all the performed activities conducted in-between the second and the third lab sessions dedicated to work on the lab’s outcome.

2. The third Lab’s meeting

The analytical report of lab’s meetings will be based on the final version —validated by all participants— of the instant report.

2.1. Participants and their background

2.1.1. Socio-demographics of the group

Overall description of the group of participants, focusing on the differences (if any) between the first second and third lab (in case the group composition changed), composition (movements/organisations they come from, main age ranges, gender and other socio -demographic features referring to participation from minorities groups in particular). In particular, detail the individual characteristics of new participants, as well of the new movements/organisations that might have joined. Similarly, in case of participant’s drop-out, please try to specify the reasons behind (if known).

Similarly as in the previous reports, in case of lab members participating in a personal capacity , i.e. not representing their movements/organisations, please still mention and them in the report for information purposes, including their socio-demographic information (no need to include their names). If there are changes in the participation status (individual vs representing their organisation/movement), please indicate it⁷..

2.1.2. Represented movements/organisations

Beside describing the personal characteristics of the participants, we would need more information about the organisations/movements involved in the lab independently from whether a participating person has formally represented the movement/organisation she/he is active with. Please draft this section covering the following dimensions, per each movement/organisation —including the ones that may have dropped-out their participation to the lab—:

- Type of organisation/movement (legal status: small enterprise, cooperative, NGO, no legal status, etc).

⁷ A key aspect to pay attention to is if they have asked for not including the name of their organisation/movements in project’s reports, and in such case those should be described paying attention not to make them identifiable.

- Themes addressed by the organisation/movement.
- Whether the organisation is self-defining as feminist or not; whether it adopts and intersectional and/or transfeminist approach, whether it focuses or not on one or more specific discrimination grounds beside/ other than gender
- Main type of repertoires of action and forms of mobilization used by the organisation/movement.
- Level of involvement with public institutions: describe whether the organisation/movement is involved in projects/initiatives with public institutions or most of their activities are grassroots. and/or whether a confrontational /agonistic approach towards institutions is prevailing.
- Networks (formal or informal) the organisation/movement is part of: describe any regional, national and European networks

This section has been conceived to be based in the answers to the questionnaire filled by the lab participants, where all these questions have been included. Despite this, please note that these questions are not mandatory in the questionnaire provided to lab participants. This allows participants the option to complete a simplified version of the questionnaire, which can be answered more quickly, especially when the questionnaire is sent to participants after the third national lab has taken place. In such cases, the information collected might not be sufficient to draft this section of the report. Therefore, we kindly request that partners put in additional effort to describe the organisations, providing more details than in previous reports.

2.2. Agenda and discussions within the meeting

This section presents the agenda of the third meeting of the Lab, specifying per each section and topic of the agenda the used techniques and materials. Also, discrepancies and changes between the planned agenda and the finally implemented one shall be described here shortly referring to the related reasons.

Following the agenda’s structure and based on the instant report, this section goes through the content related parts of the meeting, describing each one in details: for each section/block of the agenda it details the addressed questions and topics, evolution of the discussions, different perspectives and frames of arguments, divergences, convergences and how they were (or not) achieved, and main decisions made (including the utilized decision making mechanisms/techniques, e.g. alternatives to voting).

3. Analysing the lab’s outcome, process and next steps

3.1. Current status of the lab’s outcome

Detail the current status of implementation of the planned outcome, considering the planning that took place during the second lab session. Describe the design and implementation process (planning, knowledge co-creation, next steps), as well as the developed content. In addition, include the discussions and agreements regarding the outcome’s scope, target population, and the overall strategic considerations shared by the group that lead to identify it as a politically meaningful form of action.

3.2. Analysis of the lab’s outcome

This section is intended to analyse the lab’s outcome and its potential to generate impact. The questions below were already part of the previous report, still in the 'diagnosis' stage. The objective of this report is to delve deeper into this analysis: specifically, we aim to determine if new expectations are emerging regarding the impact of feminist claims on institutional democratic spaces and policy making of the country, and how these expectations are being translated into the outcomes of the lab.

- How the lab's outcome has been shared/disseminated across the feminist movements and was is received? Could you observe any feedback or uptake from media and or institutional actors (for the latter in relation to their political agendas)?

- Do you think the Lab’s outcome and the way it is presented/framed bends more toward a critical/agonistic approach towards institutional policies/politics, does it aim at impacting those, or does it contain elements of both approaches? Please elaborate
- Were the participants in the Lab reporting/reflecting a sense of ownership of the co-created outcome at the end of the process? Did they share it was a meaningful effort or were they (any of them) doubtful/sceptical about it?

3.3. Analysis of lab’s internal dynamics/process

Please, in the present section elaborate on the following themes:

- Controversial issues and tensions/debates
 - Were there identifiable contrasting positions inside the lab? On which specific issues and which were the contentious frames/arguments at stake?
 - Conflict resolution practices: were any specific techniques implemented, and/or actors that were catalysers/facilitators to solve the conflict, etc?
- Decision-making inside the lab
 - How were decisions taken within the lab?
 - Were there any specific deliberation techniques used?
 - Was voting a practice at any point in time in the process?
- Emotions
 - Which do you think were the prevailing emotions among participants, both in relation to the political issues at stake, and among them?
- Alliances
 - Do you think the lab facilitated/generated new (intersectional) relations and/or alliances? If yes, do you think those have chances to continue?
- Power dynamics in the lab
 - Did you observe any implicit/explicit power dynamics among the participants? Based on what privileges/disadvantages?
 - If yes how were those handled/addressed?
- Considering your experience as a facilitator (this section should consider the perceptions of all partners that participated in the lab facilitation)
 - Which were the prevailing emotions you experienced as facilitator(s) of the Lab?
 - How as facilitators/promoting organisation of the Lab did you tackled the power/privilege inherent with this role?
 - Looking at both the final output and the processes in the Lab, would you define the outcome "innovative" or representing a form of feminist democratic innovation? How/why?
 - Please add any further considerations on the Lab’s dynamics

4. Next steps of the Lab

- Include whether there are any plans to submit/apply to the FIERCE actions call or any other plans to sustain/disseminate/ replicate/further develop the outcome at national or international level.
- Are there plans to continue with the established network/new alliances which were created in the lab?
- In case the lab already implemented the outcome, are there any envisaged follow-up activities or are plans for the sustainability of the outcome in the middle or long-term (for instance, to be considered in the French and Spanish labs for the operation of the platforms that are being developed in the long term).

5. Annex-The Instant report in national language

(Same guidelines as for the previous Lab’s meeting)

Centred in a factual description of lab’s meeting and elaborated immediately afterwards. It will be managed internally in each national lab: drafted by FIERCE partners and shared and validated with the participants. It is suggested to allow editing roles to participants who might want to contribute to the process Instant reporting is a methodology originated in the Open Space Technology Technique and it consists in the objective description of all the activities that have been conducted during the lab’s meeting. The structure will follow lab’s agenda and all individual and group discussions taking place in all time slots should be detailed. In each section (time slot of lab’s agenda), there should be included:

- Participants
- Discussed themes: diverse arguments (detailed interventions by participant or topic).
- Details of each plenary and subgroup’s discussion (one rapporteur per group)
- Photos of working materials (flipcharts, sheets, etc) and of participants if communication of the Lab occurs under the “Regular exposure” scenario (see “section 6.4 Communication in and about FIERCE labs” of D4.1).
- Agreements/next steps

To assure trustworthiness of the information collected in the report, it should be instantly elaborated and shared with lab’s participants maximum one working day after the lab’s meeting takes place to be modified and validated by them. For this, an online platform for collaborative work should be chosen — see section 4.4 work in-between lab’s sessions for some proposed open-source platforms—. A deadline to finish the modifications and comments on the reporting should be agreed with participants.